

Investigation of the Mechanism and Technical Implementation of Acoustic Thermography

Dissertation

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Zusammenfassung

In dieser Arbeit wurde mit einem dafür neu entwickelten 3D-Laservibrometermesssystem gezeigt, dass die Erwärmung des rissfreien Bulk mit der lokalen Spannung im Material korreliert und durch die Dämpfung des Ultraschalls (innere Reibung) hervorgerufen wird. Für die Erwärmung von Rissen wurden neben der Dämpfung Reibung sowie plastische Verformung identifiziert. Die gemessene quadratische Abhängigkeit der Erwärmung von der lokalen Auslenkung des Prüfteils lässt sich im Bild der Reibung durch die zusätzliche Modulation der Normalkraft, die die Rissflanken aneinanderpresst, beschreiben. Wegen der kleinen Auslenkungen in den Bauteilen ist es notwendig, nicht von einem reinen Gleitreibungsfall, sondern vielmehr von einem stark von Haftreibung dominierten Modus auszugehen. Plastische Verformung wurde nur im Extremfall beobachtet. Zwar tritt an Rissspitzen eine lokale Spannungsüberhöhung auf, Rissspitzenverrundung und Riss schließen verhindern jedoch meist plastische Verformung und Risswachstum.

Für die technische Umsetzung wurden die allgemein verwendeten Systeme auf Basis von Ultraschallschweißanlagen genauer untersucht und deren Unzulänglichkeiten – insbesondere hinsichtlich der Reproduzierbarkeit – aufgezeigt und begründet. Auf diesen Ergebnissen aufbauend wurde eine neue Technik entwickelt, die durch einen abstimmbare Erreger erlaubt, die Lage der individuellen Eigenfrequenzen zu berücksichtigen und das Prüfteil resonant anzuregen. Auf diese Weise ließ sich außerdem die Effizienz steigern, da zum Erreichen derselben Auslenkungen des Prüfteils ein Piezoerreger mit geringerer Leistung genügt.

Schließlich wurden für eine technische Umsetzung notwendige Aspekte untersucht. Dazu gehören vor allem Methoden, die nicht automatisch gegebene Zerstörungsfreiheit zu charakterisieren und sicherzustellen. Daneben werden die Nachweisgrenzen, Techniken zur Aufbereitung der Infrarotdaten, die Gründe für das Auftreten von Fehlanzeigen sowie der Vergleich mit herkömmlichen ZfP-Methoden diskutiert.

Summary

In this thesis project, a newly developed 3D laser vibrometer system was used to demonstrate that heating of the defect-free bulk correlates with local stresses in the material and is caused by damping of the ultrasound. Two additional mechanisms that lead to crack heating were identified as friction and plastic deformation. The measured quadratic relationship between heating and local displacements in the specimen is explained by an additional modulation of the normal force pressing the crack faces together. Due to the small displacements in the parts, it is necessary to postulate a mechanism strongly dominated by static rather than dynamic friction. Plastic deformation was only observed in extreme cases. Although local stress concentration occurs at crack tips, crack tip blunting as well as crack closure ordinarily prevent plastic deformation and crack growth. For the technical implementation, commonly used systems based on ultrasonic welding equipment were investigated and their disadvantages—especially with regard to reproducibility—were demonstrated and explained. Based on these results, a new technique was developed, which uses a tunable exciter to account for the individual eigenfrequencies of the specimen and to achieve resonant excitation of the specimen and to achieve a resonant excitation of the specimen. This also enabled increased efficiency as a lower-power piezoelectric exciter is sufficient to achieve the same displacements of the specimen. Finally, necessary aspects for a technical implementation were investigated. Of particular interest are methods to characterize and verify the non-destructive nature of the procedure. Detection limits, post-processing methods for the infrared data, causes for false indications and a comparison with conventional NDT methods are also discussed.

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The three Axioms of NDT

1. *Every material contains defects.*
2. *Defects in a material do not necessarily render it unusable for its intended purpose.*
3. *The detectability of a defect generally grows as a function of its size.*

[YS85, p. 1516]

Chapter 1

Introduction to acoustic thermography

1.1 Status of Research and Current Questions

Acoustic thermography was developed in the late '70s under the name of vibrothermography by Edmund Hennecke et al. [HRS79, HRSR82] at the Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University, and is one of the methods of nondestructive examination (NDT)¹.

In recent years, developments in the area of infrared cameras in particular have resulted in the application of this method by various research groups, which has resulted in many different designations in the literature:

- Acoustic Thermography [HFT03], [HRBS06], [RH05]
- Elastic-wave-activated thermography [BDZ01], [DZB02]
- Sonic IR [CKR06], [MS04], [Mil01]
- Thermal vibration method [SC02]
- Thermosonic (activation) [DR03], [Han03], [MCB⁺05], [PD03]
- Ultrasound excited thermography [ZRDB03]
- Ultrasonic infrared thermography [HMZ⁺04]
- VibroIR [BM04]
- Vibrothermography [Fis87], [HRS79], [HRSR82], [HR81], [RWB96], [RHS80], [SAL04]

The term *acoustic thermography* is used in this study.² The application of this method enables the detection of surface and hidden cracks in particular as well as delamination (detachment of coatings) in the specimen. During examination, the

¹Cf. Appendix C from page 125 for a summary of other common methods

²There is also another method designated as “Acoustic Thermography” [Pas92] or “Acoustothermography” [PAI96], but which has nothing to do with the topic of this study. This instead entails the (passive) measurement of temperature in biological objects by evaluating the acoustic radiation emitted as a result of thermal atomic movement.

part is excited with a brief, powerful ultrasonic pulse at frequencies which usually range from 20–40 kHz. The electrical power draw of the ultrasonic transducer used is several hundred W up to several kW and excitation time is on the order of a second. During this time, the ultrasonic wave propagates in the specimen and results in vibrations with deflections in the μm range, corresponding to strains on the order of 10^{-4} .

This excitation results in local heating, especially at defects. The resulting surface heating can then be detected using a thermal imaging camera (infrared camera)³. If the heat generation site is beneath the surface, the time elapsing until the heat reaches the surface and thus becomes detectable for the camera is a characteristic measure of the depth of the defect. In particular, defects beneath a coating are detectable where methods such as the traditional dye penetrant examination fail.

The wide range of areas of application of acoustic thermography is evident from its use on welded connections [BM04], NASA Shuttle panels of various composites [BM04], carbon fiber reinforced silicon carbide (C/C-SiC) [BDZ01], other composite structures [DZB02, FHO⁺00], stringer structures [BDZ01], ceramics [Mil01], silicon wafers [RBR04], solar cells [RBR04] and even teeth [HFT01].

However, many of these applications have not evolved past the experimental stage. Although there are now companies offering examination systems based on acoustic thermography (such as Automation Technology [URL07a], e/de/vis [URL07b], Thermosensorik [URL07d], Thermal Wave Imaging [URL07e]), many basic questions such as that of reproducibility from one part to the next, detection sensitivity or the possibility of quantitative determination of the material loading occurring during ultrasonic excitation, have as yet remained the subject of only initial investigation, if any. In contrast to other NDT methods, acoustic thermography is not *a priori* nondestructive, as material damage or crack growth can occur on excessive vibration [CKR06].

A further open point is the mechanism of heat generation which results in heating of defects such as cracks and delamination, although bulk heating effects, such as in plastics, can also be observed in the absence of defects [RWB96]. Many possible mechanisms for this have been discussed [RHS80], but no complete understanding has yet been achieved.

Questions addressed in this study

This study examines two main points: firstly, those aspects affecting technical implementation are to be investigated in detail, and secondly the heating mechanisms.

As practical implementations to date have nearly exclusively entailed measurement systems based on ultrasonic welding units due to their simple applicability, a brief introduction to acoustic thermography by this method will be given below (Section 1.2).

Investigation of the mechanism and technical implementation necessitates information on the vibration of the specimens during ultrasonic excitation. A 3D laser vibrometer measurement system is therefore developed in this study which enables measurement of the vibration of the specimens in all spatial directions over a large

³In most cases, the object is opaque in the infrared, with the result that the camera only detects the temperature of the object surface. For partially transparent materials, the effect must be accounted for that the camera measures an integral heat value over a certain penetration depth.

area. However, knowledge of the spectrum is often also sufficient to determine the location of the resonant frequencies. Section 2 presents the theoretical and experimental basis for this.

For sufficiently plane geometries - such as turbine blade airfoils - analytical models are elaborated for Lamb waves which also enable three-dimensional conclusions to be drawn for the occurring material stresses from the considerably more easily derived one-dimensional vibration data (Section 3).

Starting from this basis, the technical implementation of acoustic thermography is discussed in Section 4. As most publications to date have used only cracked individual parts as the specimens in order to demonstrate the basic applicability of acoustic thermography, the issue of reproducibility from one part to another in series measurements has essentially remained uninvestigated. Although there have been individual attempts to determine effects of the variation of excitation parameters (such as [PD03]), these have remained in the stage of phenomenological approaches. A significantly improved approach is possible here using vibration measurement.

It proves that the study of resonance behavior of the individual specimens enables not only a coherent explanation of the results of the reproducibility investigations, but also the direct derivation of ideas for improvement. The new method developed in this study uses tunable piezoelectric exciters for resonant excitation of the specimens. Because of the resulting improved stability of the excitation, this system also enables significantly better investigation of the heat generation mechanism.

At excessive vibration amplitudes, the local material stresses can exceed the yield point, with the result that the specimen is damaged. Since non-destructiveness is simultaneously the essential aspect of NDT and a problematic aspect of acoustic thermography, a separate section is dedicated to this (Section 5). This is then followed by further technical aspects which have been investigated only little if at all to date (Section 6).

This study is concluded with a section bundling the investigations of the heating mechanisms in acoustic thermography (Section 7). The basis for this, namely knowledge of the vibration of the specimens during ultrasonic excitation, is determined with both the aforementioned laser vibrometer measurement system as well as by finite-element modeling as a supplement. These data enable the determination of local strains which can be correlated with the infrared images and finally compared with the possible physical mechanisms. In addition to the friction mechanism, other dissipative effects are also accounted for here, such as heating due to damping or local yielding.

However, the movements of crack faces in all spatial directions may also be detected with the vibrometer measurement system. This should clarify the effect of the local vibration modes on crack heating.

1.2 Acoustic Thermography with Ultrasonic Welding Systems

Systems based on ultrasonic welding units for plastic welding processes are frequently used to generate high sound power levels for acoustic thermography. These units are available from suppliers such as Branson, Rinco, Telsonic, KLN or others. Such systems are used to heat plastic parts with ultrasonic energy and weld them together

with pressure [Str95, GF94]. In addition to stationary units, manual welding guns are also available, enabling mobile use.

The advantages of these units are the use of components proven in manufacturing as well as the high available power level (up to several kW electrical power). Such a setup can be used to already obtain acceptable results with a relatively low technical expenditure, although, as will be seen, reproducibility in series testing is relatively poor and efficiency is low due to the non-resonant excitation.

Setup of ultrasonic excitation system

A Branson 2000 aef ultrasonic welding unit was used in this study (see Table 1.1).

Generator	Branson 2000 f
Feed unit	Branson 2000 aef
Converter	CJ-20
Working frequency	20,000 Hz
Frequency range	19,550 to 20,450 Hz
Electrical power	3,000 W

Table 1.1: Specifications of ultrasonic welder used

The system consists of the 2000 f generator and the welding press with 2000 ae pneumatic feed unit (Fig. 1.1). The heart of the feed unit is the converter, a resonant vibrating piezoelectric exciter which is connected via the so-called booster with the sonotrode which finally contacts the part. The booster and sonotrode provide for mechanical variation (mostly amplification) of the ultrasonic amplitude. Titanium alloys are often used as materials due to their low ultrasonic damping and high cyclic pressure loading resistance [Bra90]. Boosters with a mechanical ratio of 1:0.5 (attenuation) to 1:2 (gain) are usually used. In addition, the middle level of the booster designed as $\lambda/2$ oscillator serves to mechanically secure the entire stack in the feed unit, as it represents a vibration node.

The sonotrodes are produced in various geometries, adapted to the required amplitude, size and shape of the part to be welded [Nep58, Mer57]. Fig. 1.2 shows a schematic of the most important sonotrode geometries with vibration velocity and material stress distribution as a function of length.

Lengths vary depending on geometry, but are roughly $\lambda/2$ (length would be exactly $\lambda/2$ only for a non-amplifying 1:1 cylindrical sonotrode). Stepped sonotrodes provide high gain factors at low costs but wear more quickly due to the uneven reduction in cross section (high stresses at step, cf. Fig. 1.2 right).

Catenoid and stepped sonotrodes were used in this study, with contact areas of 50–80 mm². Contact pressures of roughly 4 to 20 MPa are obtained at contact forces of between 300 and 1000 N. The amplitudes at the sonotrode end are typically roughly 50 μm .

A peculiarity of the welding generators is their limited frequency adjustment capability. As the resonance of the stack depends on the ambient conditions (such as temperature) and welding parameters, an automatic frequency control is built in in order to ensure high amplitude stability and optimum energy conversion during the welding step. The maximum frequency range for the Branson 2000f is $\Delta f_B = 900$ Hz.

Figure 1.1: Photograph of modified Branson ultrasonic welding unit used. Left: overview, reflecting foil stickers are adhered to the blade to improve the laser vibrometer signal, right: detailed view of feed unit with sonotrode projecting through hole in table.

Figure 1.2: Most frequently used sonotrode types with velocity (solid green line) and stress curves (dashed red line); the diameter ratio of the two sonotrode ends was 6:1 in each case (from [Nep60]).

In order to ensure access to the test specimens from all sides, the welding press was mounted upside down beneath a table with the sonotrode projecting up through a hole in the table top, where it contacts the underside of the specimen (Fig. 1.1). Turbine blades are secured with a special pneumatic clamp on the root (Fig. 1.3 left, cf. Appendix D, p. 129). Parts with more complex geometry such as turbine stationary blades are secured with a clamp mount (Fig. 1.3 right).

Figure 1.3: Clamps developed for acoustic thermography. Left: universal pneumatic clamp for turbine (moving) blades with fir-tree roots, right: special clamp for parts with more complex geometry, in this case a turbine stationary blade.

Typical results

Fig. 1.4 shows typical thermal images obtained by acoustic thermography in the examination of a gas turbine blade. The sole crack in the blade root is clearly visible (arrow), while the rest of the blade is not heated. The images are shown in false color with the colors red-yellow-white corresponding to increasing heating.

Excitation time was 1 s, although the crack is already clearly visible after 40 ms (2nd image from left). It becomes increasingly blurred with increasing time as a result of lateral heat flow. The last image shows the blade one second after excitation is stopped. Only a blurred area is still detectable here at the crack location.

Figure 1.4: Examination of a gas turbine blade by acoustic thermography. The blade has an artificially created fatigue crack in the blade root (arrow).

Chapter 2

Vibration Analysis for Investigation of Ultrasonic Vibrations

The response of the examined object to external ultrasonic excitation must be investigated in order to obtain a deeper understanding of acoustic thermography, and especially to enable characterization of its non-destructiveness and reproducibility. The spectra of the specimens must also be determined for acoustic thermography with tunable exciters which makes use of resonant excitation of the specimens for increased efficiency. Finally, correlations between vibration and heating can be derived from the operation deflection shapes measured on the surface. The corresponding theoretical principles are elaborated in this section and a measurement system is presented for the determination of 3D strain data.

Accelerometers or eddy current sensors are frequently used to measure vibrations. The disadvantages of these lie in the contacting measurement or the small working distance. The use of microphones is also possible, although in this case interference in the sound field and sensitivity to other noises have a negative effect.

In contrast, laser vibrometers enable the noncontacting measurement of surfaces vibrations far into the ultrasonic range. In addition to simple single-point vibrometers, sampling scanning vibrometers as well as differential 2-point and 3D probes are also available. The analog output signal from the vibrometer is proportional to the velocity with which the measured surface section of the object moves. Peak values of deflection u_0 , velocity (particle velocity) v_0 and acceleration a_0 are calculated for a harmonic vibration of frequency $f = \omega/(2\pi)$,

$$v(t) = v_0 \cos(\omega t), \quad (2.1)$$

as

$$u_0 = \omega^{-1} v_0 \quad (2.2)$$

$$a_0 = \omega v_0 \quad (2.3)$$

A Polytec 1D scanning and Polytec 3D-CLV-300 laser vibrometer were used in this study. Both operate based on the heterodyne principle and can determine both the magnitude and sign of the vibration¹.

¹Please refer to the Polytec website (<http://www.polytec.com>) or [Her05] for a more exact technical description

The vibrometer is ordinarily aligned so that its axis is normal to the surface of the object to be measured. The conventional notation is also used according to which the normal component of the vibration on the specimen (out-of-plane component) is designated with z and the two horizontal and vertical components of the surface (in-plane components) with x and y (Fig. 2.1). While the 1D vibrometer can only measure component v_z , the 3D vibrometer acquires the complete vector $\vec{v} = (v_x, v_y, v_z)$.

For the 3D probe, the measurement is performed with three laser beams which are focused on a point (diameter roughly 80 μm). The fixed angle of the individual beams relative to each other automatically fixes the working distance to the focal length of the lens used (in this case 150 mm), which represents a certain restriction in the application. Reflecting foil is also usually bonded to the part; this increases the reflected intensity and thus improves the signal-to-noise ratio.

Figure 2.1: Coordinate system for laser vibrometer measurement system. The z component (out-of-plane) is normal to the surface, while the x and y axes define the normal plane to this and form the two horizontal and vertical in-plane components.

2.1 Resonance Analysis, Specimen Spectra

Resonant frequencies must always be determined in order to achieve efficient excitation (large deflection for low exciter power) and a stable vibration mode of the specimen. The most important concepts for the determination of spectra are explained below.

2.1.1 Determination of Spectra using Delta Pulse Excitation

The simplest means of determining the spectra is by a simple delta excitation, which can be approximated with a hammer tap. Experimentally, excitation by a short tap of duration T is achieved with a light hammer ($m < 10$ g). Excitation then corresponds to a rectangular pulse $x(t)$,

$$x(t) = \frac{1}{T} (\Theta(t) - \Theta(t - T)) \quad (2.4)$$

with the Heaviside function $\Theta(t)$:

$$\Theta(t) := \begin{cases} 0 & \text{für } t < 0 \\ 1 & \text{für } t \geq 0. \end{cases} \quad (2.5)$$

The excitation converges to a δ pulse for arbitrarily short times:

$$\lim_{T \rightarrow 0} x(t) = \delta(t). \quad (2.6)$$

The Fourier transform and thus the frequency spectrum of the excitation for (2.4) is as follows:

$$X(f) := \mathcal{F}(x(t)) = -\frac{i}{(2\pi)^{3/2} f T} (e^{2\pi i f T} - 1). \quad (2.7)$$

The shorter the contact time, the higher the frequencies which can be achieved. For arbitrarily short times (i.e. a true δ pulse), the result is

$$\lim_{T \rightarrow 0} X(f) = \lim_{T \rightarrow 0} |X(f)| = \mathcal{F}(\delta(t)) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}}, \quad (2.8)$$

or constant excitation over the entire frequency range.

In real situations, frequencies of up to the first zero of (2.7) can be used. Since $X(f)$ goes to $(2\pi)^{-1/2}$ as $f \rightarrow 0$,

$$\lim_{f \rightarrow 0} X(f) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}}, \quad (2.9)$$

the zeroes for $f > 0$ are completely determined by the exponential factor:

$$X(f)|_{f>0} = 0 \quad \xrightarrow{f \gg 0} \quad e^{2\pi i f T} - 1 = 0. \quad (2.10)$$

This is fulfilled for

$$f = \frac{n}{T} \quad n \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{0\}. \quad (2.11)$$

The first zero is thus at $1/T$, meaning that a pulse of less than 0.1 ms duration is required for frequencies up to $f = 10$ kHz. This can be just achieved in practice with small hammer masses, but excitation of high frequencies (> 20 kHz) is hardly possible.

2.1.2 Determination of Spectra using Sweep/Chirp

More efficient excitation is achieved with a transducer (shaker/piezoelectric exciter) and a suitable excitation signal. Both sweep and chirp are understood to be a sinusoidal signal for which the frequency changes monotonically with time. For the linear chirp used here, $x(t)$ is linearly interpolated between the starting frequency f_1 and the end frequency f_2 during time T ,

$$x(t) = \sin \left(2\pi \frac{t}{T} ((T-t)f_1 + t f_2) \right) (\Theta(t) - \Theta(t-T)), \quad (2.12)$$

where a *chirp* is usually designated as a fast *sweep* ($\Delta f = f_2 - f_1$),

$$\left. \frac{\Delta f}{T} \right|_{\text{Chirp}} \gg \left. \frac{\Delta f}{T} \right|_{\text{Sweep}}. \quad (2.13)$$

The response $y(t)$ of the examined object is recorded with a vibration sensor. Given the excitation and response signals $x(t)$ and $y(t)$ and the associated Fourier transforms

$$X(f) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} x(t) e^{-2\pi i f t} dt \quad \text{bzw.} \quad (2.14)$$

$$Y(f) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} y(t) e^{-2\pi i f t} dt, \quad (2.15)$$

Figure 2.2: Chirp signal, 1 s duration, $f_1 = 1$ Hz, $f_2 = 10$ Hz.

the simplest means of determining the spectrum or more exactly the so-called frequency response function [Gol91] is through the Fourier transform of the response

$$H(f) := Y(f). \quad (2.16)$$

No knowledge of the excitation signal $x(t)$ is necessary here. This approach does have the disadvantage that the spectrum $H(f)$ is thus a function of the amplitude and the exact characteristic of the excitation signal. However, as a frequency response function independent of the excitation signal is usually of interest, the estimator

$$H_0(f) = \frac{Y(f)}{X(f)} \quad (2.17)$$

is often used, although this equation only yields the exact frequency response function in noise-free systems. In real circumstances, derived estimators are therefore often resorted to, taking advantage of the property whereby cross power spectra suppress uncorrelated signals.

The H_1 estimator is thus [Gol91]:

$$H_1(f) = \frac{G_{yx}}{G_{xx}}, \quad (2.18)$$

where G_{xy} is the cross power spectrum between the excitation and response and G_{xx} is the auto power spectrum of the excitation,

$$G_{xy} = X^*(f)Y(f) \quad \text{and} \quad (2.19)$$

$$G_{xx} = X^*(f)X(f). \quad (2.20)$$

The asterisks indicate the complex conjugate values. Other estimators for the frequency response function are as follows [RCV85]:

$$H_2(f) = \frac{G_{yy}}{G_{xy}} \quad \text{and} \quad (2.21)$$

$$H_v(f) = \frac{G_{yx}}{|G_{yx}|} \sqrt{\frac{G_{yy}}{G_{xx}}}. \quad (2.22)$$

H_1 minimizes the error for background noise in the output signal $Y(t)$, but is sensitive to background noise in the input signal $X(t)$. The converse applies for H_2 . H_v is the geometric mean of H_1 and H_2 and represents a compromise [RCV85].

Fig. 2.10 shows a typical spectrum which was determined for a turbine blade from the measured data at a point using the above method. The individual resonant frequencies are clearly visible. The locations of these frequencies are identical for each point on the blade, as the resonant frequencies represent an inherent system characteristic. A single-point measurement is sufficient if only the frequencies are required. However, a more exact amplitude measurement requires averaging over several points in order to statistically even out chance measurements at nodes or antinodes.

2.2 Dependence of Spectra on External Parameters

Knowledge of the parameters affecting the specimen spectrum is especially important for acoustic thermography using tunable exciters. The spectrum for a specimen depends primarily on the external geometry, mass and the material. Even parts of the same type may exhibit significantly different spectra, as even slight changes in geometry or mass can shift the resonant frequencies, especially those above the acoustic range. Fig. 2.3 shows an example of this for two turbine blades. Even though the frequencies in the acoustic range are still close together and even coincide at 5,200 Hz, the difference increases with increasing frequency. On the other hand, the

Figure 2.3: Spectra for two turbine blades of the same type. Slight differences in mass and geometry cause differences in the spectra, the differences being greater at increasing frequency.

spectrum for one and the same part is also a function of external parameters, as is demonstrated below.

2.2.1 Clamping Conditions

An accurate resonance analysis is achieved by suspending the parts to be investigated from thin threads and exciting them with low-mass hammers. Any contact with the part changes the spectrum. The vibration amplitudes can be reduced by the application of coatings such as vibration-damping varnishes.

Fig. 2.4 shows the comparison of the resonance measurements on a blade which has been clamped with the standard clamp over a wide area on the root. The other variant was to clamp two wires between the jaws and the blade root on each side, transverse to the jaws of the clamp. This effectively holds the blade at only four “points”. It can be seen that clamping over a wide area suppresses many resonant frequencies, reducing overall amplitude and spreading out the remaining resonant peaks. Interestingly, the 4-point clamping arrangement is also more reproducible. Although a wide-area clamp is usually used for excitation with the Branson system due to its better mechanical stability, this result is important for the adaptive method.

Figure 2.4: Difference in spectrum for wide-area and 4-point clamping of a turbine blade. Each measurement was repeated several times.

2.2.2 Temperature

In order to obtain an impression of the temperature dependence of the spectra, a copper block equipped with heating resistors was heated to various controlled temperatures between 25.0 °C and 40.0 °C and the corresponding spectrum measured. A slight shift in the frequencies with temperature can be seen in Fig. 2.5 The maximum (cf. Fig. 2.6) exhibits roughly the following dependency:

$$f_R(\Delta T) \approx -14 \frac{\text{Hz}}{\text{K}} \Delta T + 36200 \text{ Hz}. \quad (2.23)$$

The resonant frequencies for a plate are given by the following, with only the coefficients being dependent on boundary conditions [Ble01]

$$f_R^{\text{Platte}} \propto \frac{1}{a^2} \sqrt{\frac{Eh^2}{12\rho(1-\nu^2)}}, \quad (2.24)$$

with length a , thickness h , density ρ , Poisson's ratio ν and Young's modulus E . Length and thickness change with temperature in accordance with $\Delta l = \alpha l \Delta T$ with thermal expansion coefficient $\alpha = 16.7 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ (value for copper from [Mes04]). Young's modulus E is roughly 117.1 GPa at 25 °C and roughly 116.5 GPa at 40 °C [URL07c]. Density changes roughly with the volume-specific thermal expansion coefficient $\kappa \approx 3\alpha$. Substituting all of these values in (2.24) yields a relative shift of the resonant frequencies of roughly -0.3% between 25 °C and 40 °C. The measured value of -0.6% is roughly double this, but the approximation with a plate was also used here.

Figure 2.5: Change in spectrum of a heated copper block with temperature. Lower diagram: temperature-dependent shift in main resonance peak.

The half-height width of the main resonance peak is roughly 370 Hz. If the block is excited at 40 °C and at the frequency of 35,854 Hz determined at 25 °C, failure to account for the frequency shift results in only 21.9 units on the vibration scale instead of 31.7, which still corresponds to a loss of nearly one third of the amplitude which could be achieved.

Although the shifts depend on the specific object under consideration, this behavior may be important in individual cases in acoustic thermography using tunable piezoelectric exciters (Section 4.2) if several resonant frequencies are to be excited

Figure 2.6: Shift in main resonance line of a heated copper block with temperature. The shift is roughly $-14 \text{ Hz}/^\circ\text{C}$.

in sequence based on a previously performed resonance analysis. If the object has already been heated by excitation at the first frequencies, the shift in the resonant frequencies can result in less efficient use of the subsequently excited frequencies. If this case is suspected, the resonance measurement would have to be performed again before each single-frequency excitation. An alternative to this is in situ measurement in which the frequencies are passed through slowly and the response of the object is fed back into a closed feedback control loop, enabling compensation for any frequency shifts.

2.3 Measurement of Operation Deflection Shapes

2.3.1 Definition and Measurement Setup

An operation deflection shape (ODS) is generally defined as the deflection of all points in an object at a given frequency. If the investigated frequency is a resonant frequency, the operation deflection shape corresponds to a locally stable standing wave and the deflection can be resolved into time and location-dependent components [Ble01],

$$\vec{u}(\vec{x}, f, t) = \vec{u}(\vec{x}, f) \tilde{u}(t). \quad (2.25)$$

Measurement of the frequency response function at specific points is insufficient for determining strain in the examined object. In this case, deflection \vec{u} of the object surface must instead be determined for a sufficiently large area, i.e.

$$\vec{u}(\vec{x}, f) = (u_x(\vec{x}, f), u_y(\vec{x}, f), u_z(\vec{x}, f)), \quad (2.26)$$

where $\vec{x} = (x, y, z)$. As above, the three components of deflection also exist here, but in general only the x and y dependence of deflection are measurable, as the z direction is directed into the body of the object. The z dependence is usually omitted below for this reason. The f dependence is also not accounted for, as conclusions are made for only one frequency at a time based on the operation deflection shape.

Let point P at coordinates (x, y) undergo harmonic motion,

$$\vec{u}(\vec{x}, t) = \vec{u}(\vec{x}) \sin(\omega t + \varphi(\vec{x})), \quad (2.27)$$

where the tilde represents the time-dependent parameter. There are thus three amplitude (u_x, u_y, u_z) and phase values ($\varphi_x, \varphi_y, \varphi_z$) at each point. Frequencies mostly on the order of 20 kHz are used in this study, resulting in a Lamb wavelength of roughly 50 mm in turbine blades.

Measurement system with 1D scanning vibrometer

The Polytec PSV-300 1D scanning vibrometer was used for measurements in which the z component of the operation deflection shapes (out-of-plane) was sufficient. This device uses a mirror to scan the surface of the specimen with an individual laser beam. The vibrometer is usually placed at a sufficient distance from the object that the beam hits normal to the surface to a good approximation, thus determining the out-of-plane vibration component. However, in-plane components are also measured as a function of the angle for curved surfaces. Because of the large depth of field (in the cm range), the object can also be deliberately oriented away from the normal to the beam for measurement of the in-plane components, but generally the z component is of interest. Fig. 2.7 shows typical operation deflection shapes for a gas turbine blade at different resonant frequencies. Despite the small frequency differences, the obtained operation deflection shapes differ significantly.

Figure 2.7: Operation deflection shapes for a gas turbine blade at various resonant frequencies, measured with a 1D scanning vibrometer. Only the out-of-plane component is shown due to the nature of the system. red indicates deflections out of the plane and green into the plane. As the blade was excited at a resonant frequency, the operation deflection shapes are stable with time, i.e. the nodal lines do not migrate.

Measurement system with 3D vibrometer and 2D mechanical scanner

As the information for a single component was not sufficient in all cases, such as where the movement of the crack faces was to be investigated, a measurement system

was also developed based on the existing CLV-3D probe. This was mounted on two linear translation stages perpendicular to each other (Fig. 2.8). This configuration enables mechanical scanning of surfaces of up to 150×150 mm at a theoretical lateral resolution of $4 \mu\text{m}$. This precision was not used in practice due to the $80 \mu\text{m}$ focal size of the beams. Because of the aforementioned beam divergence of the three beams, this method is restricted to plane surfaces unless the beams can be refocused during measurement. Crack movements can still be well investigated, as local surface curvature can usually be neglected on these small scales.

Figure 2.8: Mechanically scanning 3D laser measuring system developed in this study, based on a CLV-3D laser probe. The three laser beams are indicated by the red lines. The translation stages enable scanning of the object in two dimensions. The distance between the probe and object must remain constant due to beam divergence (locally plane surfaces).

The operation deflection shapes were visualized by displaying the measuring points at the corresponding coordinates on the screen for a specific frequency and animating these with the measured amplitude and phase values. Fig. 2.9 shows typical data acquired for the three component directions as well as the 3D superposition for a measurement on a turbine blade. If the correct information were also obtained for the frequency of 19,710 Hz with the 1D vibrometer (since the out-of-plane component dominates here), the 1D vibrometer would still measure only the information from the third image in the bottom series (corresponding to the z component) for the frequency of 24,210 Hz, thus failing to acquire the in-plane rotation dominating

here. Considerably more information can thus be obtained using the 3D measurement system described here.²

2.3.2 Determination of Operation Deflection Shapes using Frequency Response Functions

In the simplest case, the operation deflection shapes are obtained by determining the frequency response function as in 2.1.2 at each measuring point p_i . This establishes the amplitude \vec{u}_i and phase $\vec{\varphi}_i$ of the three components x , y , and z of the vibration for each frequency and at each point. Standing waves result at resonant frequencies, for which reason only two values shifted by π should be measured for the phase values for a component direction (points in the wave move either in phase or exactly out of phase).

Fig. 2.10 shows a section of the frequency response function determined for the upper right point. It can be seen that the phase values are poorly defined for low amplitudes. A method for improving data quality is described in the next section.

Figure 2.9: Example measurements on turbine blade from Fig. 2.8. A 50×80 mm section of the blade airfoil (trailing edge/tip) was measured. Where the 19710 Hz mode is dominated by an out-of-plane deflection, a significant (rotational) in-plane component can be seen in the 24210 Hz mode. The maximum deflections in the z direction are $0.25 \mu\text{m}$ and $0.08 \mu\text{m}$ here.

²A commercial 3D scanning laser vibrometer (Polytec) has also been available on the market for a short time. This consists of three synchronously scanning individual probes which are fixed in space relative to each other and, after suitable setup, enable measurement of the full 3D vibration information even for curved surfaces.

Figure 2.10: Excerpt from frequency response function for a point from the measurement in Fig. 2.9.

2.3.3 Determination of Operation Deflection Shapes using Lock-In Method

A monofrequent sinusoidal excitation should be given preference over the sweep in order to improve the signal-to-noise ratio in the measured operation deflection shapes, which is especially necessary if these values are to be used to calculate local strain, i.e. spatial derivatives. This enables data acquisition with lock-in analysis.

If the sampling rate during measurement is f_s , a given frequency f will be sampled with N_c points per cycle,

$$N_c = \frac{f_s}{f}. \quad (2.28)$$

If the buffer size of the measurement, i.e. the number of recorded measuring points, is designated as N and the measuring time as T , then $f_s T = N$ also holds. The lock-in analysis then corresponds to evaluation of the Fourier transform (2.15) only at these frequencies:

$$Y(f) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} [y(t) \cos(2\pi ft) + iy(t) \sin(2\pi ft)] dt = \quad (2.29)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} [y(t)c(t) + iy(t)s(t)] dt \quad (2.30)$$

$$\rightarrow \frac{1}{2\pi} \sum y_i c_i + iy_i s_i, \quad (2.31)$$

where the correlation is performed here with reference signal $c(t)$ or with the 90° phase-shifted counterpart $s(t)$. The arrow indicates discretization of the data in an actual measurement, where the integral becomes a sum. Values y_i correspond to the object response function $y(t)$, and c_i and s_i are the discretized reference signals.

There are two possibilities for determining these reference signals. They are either acquired directly from the excitation signal or they are generated synthetically. The first method is more easily implemented and has the advantage that the exact

frequencies f and f_s need not be known, which is also not the case in an actual measurement, as the quartz crystals in the function generator (generates signal with f_s) and the data acquisition card (sampling rate f_s) are not synchronized and small deviations can significantly falsify the result.

The second method requires that the frequencies first be determined, but this is often the only possibility for calculating higher harmonics in the signal.

Determination of reference signals from excitation signal

For direct correlation, the (cosinusoidal) excitation signal $c(t)$ from the function generator (reference signal) is discretized with frequency f from the A/D converter card to yield

$$c_i = c(t_i) = c(i/f_s) \text{ for } 0 \leq i < N \quad (2.32)$$

and system response $y(t)$ is discretized to yield

$$y_i = y(t_i) = y(i/f_s) \text{ for } 0 \leq i < N. \quad (2.33)$$

The sinusoidal signal s_i also required for the Fourier transform is obtained from the reference signal c_i , phase-shifted by $\pi/2$ by shifting the index by $Nc/4$:

$$s_i = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{for } i < \Delta i \\ c_{i-\Delta i} & \text{for } i \geq \Delta i \end{cases} \quad \text{where } \Delta i = \left\lfloor \frac{Nc}{4} \right\rfloor = \left\lfloor \frac{f_s}{4f} \right\rfloor, \quad (2.34)$$

where the floor brackets $\lfloor \cdot \rfloor$ indicate the largest whole number less than or equal to their argument.

The Fourier transform makes use of the orthogonality of the sine function [Bro99, S. 96],

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \sin f_1 t \sin f_2 t = 0, \text{ for } f_1 \neq f_2. \quad (2.35)$$

In practice, the interval over which the sum is generated in (2.31) is limited, so that (2.35) is not valid. This results in nonvanishing amplitudes for $f_1 \neq f_2$ (so-called leakage [MGT03][p. 260]) and thus to a value which is too small at point f_1 . A Hanning window (cf. Fig. 2.11) is used in further calculations to prevent this phenomenon [MGT03],

$$\mathcal{W}_{\text{Hann}}(i) := \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \cos \left(\frac{2\pi i}{N-1} \right) \right). \quad (2.36)$$

There is therefore also no interference due to the few missing values $s_0 \dots s_{\Delta i-1}$, as they are already nearly zero due to the window function.

A distinction is drawn below as to whether or not $f_s/(4f)$ is a whole number. If $f_s/(4f)$ is a whole number, s_i and c_i are orthogonal, i.e.

$$\sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \mathcal{W}_{\text{Hann}}(i) c_i s_i \rightarrow 0 \quad (2.37)$$

and (2.31) with the Hanning window becomes:

$$Y(f) = \sum_{i=1}^N \mathcal{W}_{\text{Hann}}(i) y_i c_i + i \sum_{i=1}^N \mathcal{W}_{\text{Hann}}(i) y_i s_i =: C(f) + S(f). \quad (2.38)$$

Figure 2.11: Hanning window.

Amplitude A and phase angle φ of the vibration can be calculated from this:

$$A_{\perp}(f) = \sqrt{C^2 + S^2} \quad (2.39)$$

$$\varphi_{\perp}(f) = \arctan \frac{S}{C}. \quad (2.40)$$

The ratio of sampling rate and frequency does not necessarily result in a whole number for $f_s/(4f)$ under actual conditions, for which reason the largest whole number less than or equal to $f_s/(4f)$ is selected as the index shift in (2.34) with $\lfloor f_s/(4f) \rfloor$

However, this means that s_i and c_i are not exactly phase shifted by $\pi/2$; in other words the measured data are projected onto a nonorthogonal coordinate system, and equations (2.37) and (2.39) to (2.40) are no longer valid.

If $S'(f)$ is the projection onto the sine axis rotated by

$$\alpha = \frac{\pi}{2} - 2\pi \cdot \frac{f_s \bmod 4f}{4f_s} \leq \pi/2, \quad (2.41)$$

the following equations apply:

$$S = A \sin \varphi \quad C = A \cos \varphi \quad S' = A \cos(\alpha - \varphi) = A \cos \alpha \cos \varphi + A \sin \alpha \sin \varphi, \quad (2.42)$$

yielding the following in the orthogonal coordinate system (S, C) :

$$S = \frac{S' - C \cos \alpha}{\sin \alpha}. \quad (2.43)$$

Equations (2.39) and (2.40) can then be used again.

Synthetic generation of reference signals

It is expedient to synthetically generate the reference signals to detect higher harmonics in the response signal, such as for investigating the response from tapping with a hammer or other nonlinear phenomena. Because of the differences in the function generator and A/D converter card crystals, it is not sufficient to calculate the reference from the known frequency f and sampling rate f_s .

Instead, a sine function at each frequency f_j is output with the function generator and digitized with the A/D converter card at the start of a measurement. The “real” frequency \tilde{f}_j is then determined with the Hanning window and Fourier transform, from which the reference signal can then be calculated:

$$\tilde{c}_{i,j}^n = \cos(2\pi \tilde{f}_j n j / N) \quad \text{and} \quad \tilde{s}_{i,j}^n = \cos(2\pi \tilde{f}_j n j / N + \pi/2). \quad (2.44)$$

The accuracy of this measurement method is shown in Table 2.1 Ten sawtooth signals at various frequencies f_j were measured and the mean of the measured amplitudes and their harmonics calculated. The amplitude of the input signal $x_j(t)$ in each case was $U = 3,141 \text{ V} \approx \pi \text{ V}$,

$$x_j(t) = \frac{2U}{\pi} \sum_i \frac{-(-1)^i \sin(2\pi i f_j t)}{i}. \quad (2.45)$$

This results in simple numerical values for the i th harmonic, namely $A_i = 2/i$, for alternating phase values $\Phi_i = -\pi(-1)^i$.

Harmonic	A_i (theoretical)	\bar{A}_i (measured)	Rel. Error [%]
1.	2.000	2.001	+0.1
2.	1.000	0.999	-0.1
3.	0.666	0.664	-0.4
4.	0.500	0.497	-0.6
5.	0.400	0.396	-1.0
6.	0.333	0.329	-1.4

Table 2.1: Accuracy of measured higher harmonics using synthetically generated reference signals

An example in which the local nonlinearities of a defect were used for its detection (cf. [KSB01]) is shown in Fig. 2.12. In this case, a delamination can be seen which could be detected using the method described in this section. The blade was excited with a monofrequency at 20,890 Hz and the vibration evaluated in the harmonic frequencies.

2.3.4 Data Smoothing and Strain Calculation

Strain values will now be calculated from the vibration data. These consist primarily of the spatial derivatives of the deflection matrix (cf. Equation (3.1)), which are reduced to differences between adjacent points for the discretized measured data. Noisy data have a significant effect on the quality of the results due to this difference calculation. Lateral averaging, although it yields poorer spatial resolution in the strain data, results in improved accuracy.

The discretized data are designated as follows:

$$u_{ijk} := u_k(x_{ij}, y_{ij}), \text{ where } k \in \{x, y, z\} \quad (2.46)$$

Moving average

The simplest form of averaging is the moving average for the adjacent points. A new value for u_{ijk} in (2.46) is obtained by averaging over the three points $u_{i-1,jk}$, u_{ijk} and $u_{i+1,jk}$:

$$\bar{u}_{ijk} = \sqrt{S^2 + C^2} \quad \text{and accordingly} \quad \bar{\varphi}_{ijk} = \arctan S/C \quad (2.47)$$

where

$$S = \frac{1}{3} \sum_{m=i-1}^{m=i+1} u_{mjk} \sin \varphi_{mjk} \quad \text{and} \quad C = \frac{1}{3} \sum_{m=i-1}^{m=i+1} u_{mjk} \cos \varphi_{mjk}. \quad (2.48)$$

Figure 2.12: Chipped thermal barrier coating on a turbine blade with adjacent delamination. This can be detected not only by thermography (upper images), but also by nonlinear laser vibrometry, where the harmonics result from the actual defect. The area of the photograph outlined with a dashed line corresponds to the area of the laser vibrometer measurement.

Two-dimensional averaging is normally preferable, i.e.

$$\begin{pmatrix} S \\ C \end{pmatrix} = \sum_{m=1}^{m=r} \sum_{n=1}^{n=r} M_{mn} u_{i+m-(r+1)/2, j+n-(r+1)/2, k} \begin{pmatrix} \sin \varphi_{i+m-(r+1)/2, j+n-(r+1)/2, k} \\ \cos \varphi_{i+m-(r+1)/2, j+n-(r+1)/2, k} \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.49)$$

One of the following convolution matrices (also known as filter kernels) is used for M :

$$M_1 = \frac{1}{9} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad M_2 = \frac{1}{5} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad M_3 = \frac{1}{8} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 4 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.50)$$

M_1 corresponds to an equally weighted averaging of the point with its 8 nearest neighbors, whereas M_2 accounts only for the nearest 4 neighbors in addition to the actual point and M_3 places more weight on the actual point. The prefactors serve to normalize the result.

Median filter

The median of a set of data points is defined as the middle value of the ordered set, i.e.

$$\begin{aligned} \{a_i\} &= \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n\} \text{ where } a_{j+1} \geq a_j \\ \Rightarrow \text{Median}(\{a_i\}) &= \begin{cases} a_{(n+1)/2} & \text{for } n \text{ uneven} \\ \frac{1}{2}(a_{n/2} + a_{n/2+1}) & \text{for } n \text{ even} \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (2.51)$$

The median filter is a ranking filter for which no filter kernel can be given in the form of a matrix analogous to (2.50). In contrast to averaging, individual outlying data points do not falsify the results in this case.

As the vibration data are vector data, ranking or sorting by magnitude is not possible here. Instead, filtering is performed in Cartesian coordinates:

$$\begin{aligned}x_{ijk} &:= u_{ijk} \cos \varphi_{ijk} \\y_{ijk} &:= u_{ijk} \sin \varphi_{ijk}\end{aligned}\quad (2.52)$$

The average values in this study are calculated by generating the median of this point with its 4 nearest neighbors. This is sufficient to filter out individual outlying data points.

$$S = \text{Median}(\{x_{i-1,jk}, x_{i+1,jk}, x_{ijk}, x_{i,j-1,k}, x_{i,j+1,k}\}) \quad (2.53)$$

and analogously for C and y_{ijk} , after which (2.47) is again applied.

For the edge points which are not 3×3 surroundings, only a 1×3 or 3×1 averaging of the point with its 2 nearest neighbors is performed.

Multiple-step averaging

The data in this study are averaged in two steps. First individual outlying data points are filtered out using a median filter with the 4 nearest neighbors. Actual averaging is then performed with a moving average (kernel size 3×3 , matrix M_2 from Equation (2.50)).

Calculation of the local strain matrix

Strain matrix ε_{ij} is obtained in Equation (3.1) by local differentiation of the averaged deflections:

$$\varepsilon_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial j} + \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial i} \right). \quad (2.54)$$

The strain matrix is used over the further course of this study to correlate the strain values with the infrared data (Section 7). It is also suitable for drawing conclusions regarding the extent to which acoustic thermography is nondestructive (Section 5.6, p. 71).

2.3.5 Effects of Cracks on Operation Deflection Shapes

The operation deflection shape can be affected by cracks. For example, this can be seen in Fig. 2.13. The cracks give rise to two discontinuities in the deflection shape at a specific frequency (36 kHz). This is shown more exactly in Fig. 2.14. In this case, two specimens were fabricated with identical dimensions (Fig. 2.14d). One of these was cut in half and reconnected with two bolts for the measurement. The whole specimen was also provided with bolts so as to rule out any additional effect from the bolts. The spectra (Fig. 2.14c) exhibit significant differences between the two specimens, although most of the resonant frequencies are visible in both spectra. The associated operation deflection shapes (2.14a/b) exhibit three different variants as examples:

Figure 2.13: Operation deflection shape of a turbine blade measured with a scanning vibrometer. The two cracks in the blade tip are manifested by discontinuities.

- **Unchanged operation deflection shapes** for frequencies of 2.8 kHz and 11.5 kHz with minor shifts in the resonant frequencies between whole and two-part specimens
- **Changes in operation deflection shapes** for 3.8 kHz and 7.6 kHz. Significant discontinuities can be seen at the crack interface here
- **No operation deflection shape** for 8.2 kHz

2.3.6 Three-Dimensional Measurement of Transients

The specimens in acoustic thermography are generally excited uniaxially, propagating a sound wave through the body. Following a certain transient settling period, resonant excitation results in a standing wave pattern on the surface of the examined part. This transient period depends on both the exciter used as well as on the actual specimen. The transient can be registered using the 3D measurement system described above. This is done by exciting the object with a brief pulse of sinusoidal vibrations and measuring the response $y(t)$ with the laser vibrometer at the highest possible sampling rate. If the measured time data are directly visualized, this yields the time history of the transient.

As signal-to-noise ratio is significantly degraded here (the Fourier transform smoothing performed on determination of the operation deflection shapes is completely omitted), multiple pulses (typically 100) must be averaged, where it is necessary to wait sufficiently long between each of these in order to allow the vibration sufficient time to decay again. Times of several 100 ms may be necessary depending on the acoustic quality of the object.

Figure 2.14: Operation deflection shapes for two sample specimens for simulating the effect of material interfaces. a./b.: Operation deflection shapes for whole (a) and split (b) specimen, c. Associated spectra, d. Schematic of sample specimens.

A stepped brass wedge bonded axially to a piezoelectric exciter was selected as an example here. Fig. 2.15 shows the out-of-plane vibration component measured at a point during the settling period at a resonant frequency (test setup as in Fig. 2.16 left; the out-of-plane component (z) is normal on the stepped wedge). Excitation was stopped after 6.7 ms (100 cycles) to enable the vibration to decay again. The other parameters used are listed in Table 2.2; in particular, 100 individual measurements were averaged for the data in order to obtain a sufficiently good signal-to-noise ratio.

Let f_s be the sampling rate of the A/D converter card. As the sonic velocity in brass is roughly 3.4 km/s, the distance which the wave propagates during time $1/f_s$, is roughly 0.85 mm. This is the attainable local resolution.

In the steady-state condition, the operation deflection shape again corresponds to a standing wave. A standing wave of this type is shown in Fig. 2.16 for the 25 kHz vibration of the stepped wedge. Several results can be seen in this example.

First, the (highly exaggerated) out-of-plane vibration shows that the vibration amplitude increases and the wavelength decreases from the bottom upwards, i.e. with decreasing wall thickness. This is especially evident at the large reduction in

Figure 2.15: Out-of-plane vibration component for a stepped brass wedge during transient settling (up to 6.7 ms) and subsequent decay. The bottom graph shows an enlarged section of the top graph, where the applied piezoelectric voltage is also shown for comparison (dashed).

Sampling rate f_s	4 MHz
Sampling time	16 ms
Corresponding scan points	64,000
Averages	100
Excitation time	6.7 ms
Hold time	40 ms
Corresponding sampling ratio	1:6

Table 2.2: Typical parameters for visualizing sound wave propagation during transient settling.

thickness between the third and fourth steps, where the wall thickness decreases from 3 mm to 1 mm. The material is thus subjected to increased strain in two ways at the thinner point, as the amplitude increase is also associated with a decrease in wavelength.

The conversion from a compression wave to a bending wave can also be seen in this part. Fig. 2.17 shows the process. For acoustic thermography, this means that the geometry gives rise to multiple component directions even for the polar-

Figure 2.16: Stepped brass wedge and standing wave the steady-state mode at 25,009 Hz.

ized excitation applied to the object there by a vibration (axial to the excitation transducer).

Finally, the settling periods can also be estimated. A further analysis of the entire data set on which Fig. 2.17 is based reveals that a stable standing wave is established in the brass wedge after roughly 800 μs . However, the amplitude of this wave continued to grow and was not sufficiently constant until after roughly 10 times this period. At least for resonant excitation using tunable exciters, the excitation times used in acoustic thermography (~ 1 s) are roughly two orders of magnitude longer than the settling period in this example. The settling period for acoustic thermography with welding units is determined primarily by the generator control behavior (cf. Fig. 4.6) and is roughly 50 ms.

2.3.7 Further Results

Comparison of Vibrometer Measurement/FE Simulation

Fig. 2.18 shows a comparison of operation deflection shapes measured and calculated with Ansys [Sch04] for an aluminum plate clamped on both sides. The frequencies and associated operation deflection shapes agree both qualitatively and quantitatively.

The finite element simulation of the operation deflection shape of a turbine blade is shown in Fig. 2.19, which can be compared with the images in 2.7. The wavelength at the thinner left edge is also shorter than at the thicker right edge in the simulation. The blade airfoil essentially experiences a bending wave.

Figure 2.17: Mode conversion during transient in brass wedge at 25 kHz. a. The wedge is excited with a compression wave in the y direction (1), b. After 11 μs , the phase angle of the excitation wave is shifted by roughly $\pi/2$, c. After roughly 16 μs , the wave has reached interface III/IV. The transverse component (3) is also established here due to the lower thickness and the asymmetry of the wedge, d. This transverse component propagates towards the end of the wedge, while part is simultaneously reflected (4), e. At this point, the reflection at interface II/III (5) is also visible in addition to the reflection at interface III/IV (4), f. Nearly an entire cycle of the 25 kHz excitation vibration has passed after 35 μs . It can be determined from a longer measurement that a stable standing wave has developed after roughly 800 μs . However, the maximum amplitude is not yet reached during this time. This takes roughly 6 μs (cf. Fig. 2.15).

Comparison of vibrometer measurement with ESPI method

A comparison with the alternative measurement method of Electronic Speckle Interferometry (ESPI) [Sch06] is shown in Fig. 2.20 In this case, the magnitude of the particle velocity measured with the vibrometers was shown for better comparability.

In the ESPI time-average method used, the density of the interference lines is a (nonlinear) measure of deflection. Despite the nonlinearity, it can at least be seen in the qualitative comparison that the vibrometer signal is also higher at the points of higher line density. Areas of lower vibration, especially nodal lines, appear as a noisy medium gray in the ESPI image. The measured nodal lines are shown in the vibrometer image.

Figure 2.18: Comparison of FEM analysis [Sch04] and vibrometer measurement for the example of an aluminum plate clamped on both sides. The very good qualitative and quantitative agreement can be clearly seen.

Figure 2.19: Comparison between a measurement on a blade airfoil and a FEM simulation of the entire blade [Zag02]. Similar wavelengths and vibration distributions result.

Operation deflection shapes for an actual crack

For a wide crack at the tip of a gas turbine blade, the 3D measurement system enables measurement of the three-dimensional movement of the crack as a function of frequency. The result is shown in Fig. 2.21.

Figure 2.20: Comparison of operation deflection shape measured by ESPI and 3D vibrometry.

The resonance at 8,679 Hz essentially corresponds to mode III movement (cf. Fig. 5.6) of one crack face while the other face remains stationary. A mode I movement with a superimposed uniform out-of-plane vibration can be seen at 16,023 Hz. The other resonances primarily exhibit mixed movements or higher orders.

Figure 2.21: Operation deflection shapes for a wide crack in a gas turbine blade.

Chapter 3

Theory of Ultrasonic Lamb Waves

The specimen can be approximated as a thin plate for many applications. This also applies approximately for turbine blades, tubes and carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) panels. In this case, a theoretical model of the established standing Lamb wave can be generated [TH06]. This simplifies calculation of the strain components. As will be seen, all of the components of the strain matrix can be estimated from the out-of-plane deflections $u_z(\vec{x})$ with suitable assumptions.

3.1 Strain and Stress

If a homogeneous, non-piezoelectric solid is affected by an external force, the volume elements are displaced by $\vec{u}(\vec{x}, t)$. A deformation only occurs if the volume elements are displaced relative to each other, i.e. the displacement vectors are explicitly spatially dependent. The deformation is thus given by the spatial derivatives $\partial\vec{u}/\partial x_i$. To rule out pure rotation (which does not constitute any deformation), the following applies for strain [Bel88]:

$$\varepsilon_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} \right) \quad (3.1)$$

(for pure rotation, $\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} = -\frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i}$). Stress σ and strain ε are linearly related by Hooke's law,

$$\sigma_{ij} = c_{ijkl}\varepsilon_{kl} \quad (3.2)$$

The four-dimensional elasticity tensor c_{ijkl} describes the elastic properties of a material. For a homogeneous and isotropic body, this tensor is simplified to [Bel88]

$$c_{ijkl} = \lambda^* \delta_{ij} \delta_{kl} + \mu (\delta_{ik} \delta_{jl} + \delta_{il} \delta_{jk}). \quad (3.3)$$

The 81 components of the elasticity tensor have thus been reduced to two parameters, known as the Lamé parameters λ^* and μ . Hooke's law thus takes on the following form:

$$\sigma_{ij} = \lambda^* (\varepsilon_{11} + \varepsilon_{22} + \varepsilon_{33}) \delta_{ij} + 2\mu \varepsilon_{ij} \quad (3.4)$$

Based on Newton's law, the equation of motion for a wave in a homogeneous and isotropic material can be written as follows:

$$\rho \frac{\partial^2 u_i}{\partial t^2} = \frac{\partial \sigma_{ij}}{\partial j} \quad (3.5)$$

Substituting from (3.1) and (3.4) :

$$\rho \frac{\partial^2 \vec{u}}{\partial t^2} = (\lambda^* + \mu) \vec{\nabla}(\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{u}) + \mu \vec{\nabla}^2 \vec{u} \quad (3.6)$$

3.2 Determination of Deflection

This differential equation can be converted to four simple wave equations using vector algebra. This is done by representing deflection as the sum of irrotational and divergence-free components:

$$\vec{u} = \vec{u}_\alpha + \vec{u}_\beta = \vec{\nabla} f + \vec{\nabla} \times \vec{F} \quad (3.7)$$

$$\text{where } \vec{\nabla} \times \vec{u}_\alpha = 0 \text{ and } \vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{u}_\beta = 0 \quad (3.8)$$

. Physically, \vec{u}_α is the deflection component which is induced by longitudinal waves, while \vec{u}_β is accordingly the component induced by transverse waves. The arguments (x, y, z) are omitted here and below. f and $\vec{F} = (F_x, F_y, F_z)$ are scalar or vector potentials. These must satisfy the following wave equations:

$$\frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial t^2} - c_\alpha^2 \vec{\nabla}^2 f = 0 \quad (3.9)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \vec{F}}{\partial t^2} - c_\beta^2 \vec{\nabla}^2 \vec{F} = 0 \quad (3.10)$$

where

$$c_\alpha^2 = \frac{\lambda^* + 2\mu}{\rho} \quad (3.11)$$

$$c_\beta^2 = \frac{\mu}{\rho}. \quad (3.12)$$

For a planar strain state, i.e. $u_y = 0$ and $\partial[\cdot]/\partial y = 0$, f and \vec{F} are functions only of x and z , yielding

$$u_x = \frac{\partial f}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial F_y}{\partial z} \quad (3.13)$$

$$u_y = 0 \quad (3.14)$$

$$u_z = \frac{\partial f}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial F_y}{\partial x}. \quad (3.15)$$

The following solutions result for f and F_y

$$f(x, z, t) = (A \sin \eta_\alpha z + B \cos \eta_\alpha z) e^{i(kx - \omega t)} \quad (3.16)$$

$$F_y(x, z, t) = (C \sin \eta_\beta z + D \cos \eta_\beta z) e^{i(kx - \omega t)} \quad (3.17)$$

where

$$\eta_{\alpha,\beta}^2 = k^2 - \frac{\omega^2}{c_{\alpha,\beta}^2}. \quad (3.18)$$

Substituting equations (3.16) and (3.17) in (3.13) and (3.15) yields

$$u_x = (ik (A \sin \eta_\alpha z + B \cos \eta_\alpha z) - C \eta_\beta \cos \eta_\beta z + D \eta_\beta \sin \eta_\beta z) e^{i(kx - \omega t)} \quad (3.19)$$

$$u_z = (A \eta_\alpha \cos \eta_\alpha z - B \eta_\alpha \sin \eta_\alpha z + ik (C \sin \eta_\beta z + D \cos \eta_\beta z)) e^{i(kx - \omega t)}. \quad (3.20)$$

For the antisymmetric wave form, only the sine terms can appear in u_x , and only the cosine terms in u_z , and accordingly for the symmetric wave form. This finally yields the following for antisymmetric deflection \vec{u}^a

$$u_x^a = (ikA \sin \eta_\alpha z + D\eta_\beta \sin \eta_\beta z) e^{i(kx-\omega t)} \quad (3.21)$$

$$u_z^a = (A\eta_\alpha \cos \eta_\alpha z + ikD \cos \eta_\beta z) e^{i(kx-\omega t)} \quad (3.22)$$

and for symmetric deflection \vec{u}^s

$$u_x^s = (ikB \cos \eta_\alpha z - C\eta_\beta \cos \eta_\beta z) e^{i(kx-\omega t)} \quad (3.23)$$

$$u_z^s = (-B\eta_\alpha \sin \eta_\alpha z + ikC \sin \eta_\beta z) e^{i(kx-\omega t)}. \quad (3.24)$$

Standing waves generally form on the surface of the specimen in acoustic thermography. These can be constructed from waves passing back and forth, such as

$$u_x^{a,s}(x, z, t) = u_x^{a,s}(x, z, k, t) + u_x^{a,s}(x, z, -k, t), \quad (3.25)$$

and correspondingly for the other components.

3.3 Transverse Waves

Boundary conditions must be accounted for in a plate of finite thickness $d = 2h$. The surfaces of a plate are free from stress, i.e. $\sigma_{zi} = 0$ for $i \in \{x, y, z\}$. For the planar strain state, this means $\sigma_{zz} = 0$, $\sigma_{zx} = 0$. This yields the equations for an antisymmetric wave:

$$(\lambda^*(k^2 + \eta_\alpha^2) + 2\mu\eta_\alpha^2)A \sin(\eta_\alpha h) = 2\mu ik\eta_\beta D \sin(\eta_\beta h) \quad (3.26)$$

$$2ik\eta_\alpha A \cos(\eta_\alpha h) = (k^2 - \eta_\beta^2)D \cos(\eta_\beta h) \quad (3.27)$$

. The dispersion relation as well as the relationship between amplitudes A and D , which is of interest below, can be calculated from these equations,

$$A = \frac{(k^2 - \eta_\beta^2) \cos(\eta_\beta h)}{2ik\eta_\alpha \cos(\eta_\alpha h)} D. \quad (3.28)$$

Now, if $w^2/c_{\alpha,\beta}^2$ is small compared with k^2 , then (3.18) yields $\eta_{\alpha,\beta}^2 \rightarrow k^2$, thus resulting in $A \rightarrow 0$. If $A = 0$ the wave is a purely transverse wave in the sense that $\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{u} = 0$. This wave is known as a bending wave [Kut88].

For a purely bending wave, the maximum strain ε_{xx} can be calculated from the out-of-plane deflection u_z . Analogously, it can be shown that the following applies for the ratio of amplitudes of the symmetric wave:

$$B = \frac{(\eta_\beta^2 - k^2) \sin(\eta_\beta h)}{2ik\eta_\alpha \sin(\eta_\alpha h)} C. \quad (3.29)$$

The same conclusions as for the transverse wave thus hold for the symmetric wave. Fig. 3.1 shows an antisymmetric bending wave in a plate and Fig. 3.2 shows an symmetric transverse wave.

Figure 3.1: Bending wave

Figure 3.2: Deflection in a symmetric transverse wave

3.4 Calculation of Strains in Antisymmetric and Symmetric Shear Waves

As was shown in the previous section, the transverse component of the wave dominates in a plate if the excitation is controlled by $w^2/c^2 < k^2$. In the excitation of an Inconel turbine blade at a frequency of 20 kHz, $k^2 \approx 10 w^2/c_{\alpha,\beta}^2$. The transverse component is thus dominating. The longitudinal component is neglected for the calculation below, i.e. $A = 0$ und $\eta_{\alpha,\beta} = k$.

3.4.1 Antisymmetric Bending Wave

Fig. 3.1 shows an antisymmetric bending wave in a plate. Strain in the xx direction ($\varepsilon_{xx} = \partial u_x / \partial x$) is given in Fig. 3.3. As $\vec{\nabla} \vec{u} = 0$ applies for a bending wave and a planar deformation state is assumed, $\varepsilon_{zz} = -\varepsilon_{xx}$, as can be seen in Fig. 3.4.

In these and the following figures, gray indicates that strain is zero, white indicates the greatest strain and black indicates the smallest, negative strain. Negative strain values correspond to compression of the material.

Strain in the xz direction, ε_{xz} , is zero (Fig. 3.5). It can be calculated from (3.21) and (3.22) that $\partial u_x / \partial z = -\partial u_z / \partial x$, as can also be seen in Figs. 3.6 and 3.7.

A pure shear wave is an antisymmetric transverse wave in which the deflection in the x direction does not change, i.e. $\partial u_{x,z} / \partial x = 0$. The shear wave is not a solution of the wave equation for a plate, i.e., a pure shear wave does not develop in an excited plate. The shear wave is shown in Fig. 3.8 for comparison with the bending wave.

Figure 3.3: ε_{xx} strain

Figure 3.4: ε_{zz} strain

Figure 3.8: Pure shear wave

3.4.2 Symmetric Transverse Wave

A further solution of the wave equation is the symmetrical transverse wave. The deflections are shown in Fig. 3.2. As for the bending wave, strain in the xx direction is equal to negative strain in the zz direction, and there is no strain in the xz direction. The strains and deflections are shown in Figs. 3.9 to 3.13.

A symmetric transverse wave in which the x deflection does not change is a pure density wave and is shown in Fig. 3.14. As for the pure shear wave in the antisymmetric case, the density wave is not a solution of the wave equation for a plate.

Figure 3.11: ε_{xz}

Figure 3.12: $\partial u_z / \partial x$

Figure 3.13: $\partial u_x / \partial z$

Figure 3.14: Pure density wave

3.5 Estimating Wavelength in a Plate

If the thickness of the plate is small in comparison with the other two dimensions, the components σ_{zz} and σ_{xy} are small over the entire plate thickness compared with the other components of the stress tensor and can thus be taken to be zero. This condition enables derivation of the relationship between transverse wavelength and excitation frequency [Lif91]:

$$\lambda = \frac{2\pi}{\sqrt{\omega}} \sqrt[4]{\frac{d^2 E}{12\rho(1-\nu^2)}} \quad (3.30)$$

Here d is the plate thickness, ρ is density, E is Young's modulus and ν is Poisson's ratio for the material. The Lamé parameters, λ^* and μ can be converted to E and ν . These are related by the following formulas:

$$\lambda^* = \frac{E\nu}{(1+\nu)(1-2\nu)} \quad (3.31)$$

$$\mu = \frac{E}{2(1+\nu)} \quad (3.32)$$

3.6 Determining In-Plane Strains from Out-of-Plane Deflections

Even without exact knowledge of the three-dimensional vibration, at least an estimate of the strain values is possible in certain cases. An important case is in-plane strain for a bending wave,

$$u_z(x) = u_{z,\max} \sin(2\pi x/\lambda). \quad (3.33)$$

The out-of-plane deflection $u_z(x)$ results in an in-plane strain ε_{xx} at the vibration antinodes. The strain can be estimated from the ratio of the two tangent circle radii r_1 and r_2 at the plate surface and the neutral axis (Figs. 3.15 and 3.16):

$$\varepsilon_{xx} \approx \frac{r_1}{r_2} - 1. \quad (3.34)$$

Figure 3.15: Schematic representation for estimating in-plane strain for bending wave I.

Figure 3.16: Schematic representation for estimating in-plane strain for bending wave II.

Only the surface components of the vibration are measurable, i.e. Only the radius r_1 of the first tangent circle can be determined. Radius r_2 of the second circle of curvature is approximately

$$r_2 \approx r_1 \mp d/2. \quad (3.35)$$

The minus sign applies for the case shown in Fig. 3.15 and the plus sign for Fig. 3.16. Substituting this relationship into (3.34) yields

$$\varepsilon_{xx} \approx \frac{r_1}{r_1 \mp d/2} - 1 \approx \frac{1}{1 \mp d/(2r_1)} - 1 \approx \pm \frac{d}{2r_1} \quad (3.36)$$

where the geometric series [Zei96]

$$\frac{1}{1 \mp x} = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} (\pm 1)^i x^i \quad (3.37)$$

was used with the approximation $r \gg d$.

No specific x position along the wave was used for this derivation, i.e. the following generally applies:

$$|\varepsilon_{xx}(x)| \approx \frac{d}{2r(x)}, \quad (3.38)$$

where $r(x)$ indicates the radius of curvature of the $u_z(x)$ curve at point x . An analogous equation also applies for $\varepsilon_{yy}(y)$. Determination of the in-plane strains ε_{xx} and ε_{yy} is thus reduced to the more easily measured out-of-plane deflection $u_z(\vec{x})$.

Furthermore, as

$$\varepsilon_{xy} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u_x}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial u_y}{\partial x} \right) \quad (3.39)$$

yields

$$\frac{\partial^2 \varepsilon_{xy}}{\partial x \partial y} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial^3 u_x}{\partial x \partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^3 u_y}{\partial x^2 \partial y} \right) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \varepsilon_{xx}}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \varepsilon_{yy}}{\partial x^2} \right), \quad (3.40)$$

the in-plane shear strains ε_{xy} and ε_{yx} can be completely calculated from u_z .

Three methods for determining the radii of curvature $r(x)$ are described below.

Method 1. Analytical calculation of $r(x)$

The radius of curvature of a planar function $y(x)$ at point x is [Zei96]

$$r(x) = \frac{(1 + y'(x)^2)^{3/2}}{y''(x)}. \quad (3.41)$$

The spatial derivatives of (3.33) are

$$u'_z(x) = \frac{2\pi u_{z,\max}}{\lambda} \cos\left(\frac{2\pi x}{\lambda}\right) \quad (3.42)$$

$$u''_z(x) = -\frac{4\pi^2 u_{z,\max}}{\lambda^2} \sin\left(\frac{2\pi x}{\lambda}\right). \quad (3.43)$$

Substituting these results into Eq. (3.41) and evaluating at point $x = \lambda/4$ yields the following magnitude component:

$$r = \frac{\lambda^2}{4\pi^2 u_{z,\max}}. \quad (3.44)$$

In-plane strain (3.38) at this point is thus

$$\boxed{\varepsilon_{xx} \approx \frac{2\pi^2 du_{z,\max}}{\lambda^2}}. \quad (3.45)$$

Equation (3.30) can be used to determine λ , for the overall result

$$\varepsilon_{xx} \approx \xi fu \text{ mit } \xi := \frac{4\pi \sqrt{3\rho(1-\nu^2)}}{\sqrt{E}}. \quad (3.46)$$

The result for steel is $\varepsilon_{xx} \approx 4 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ s/m} \cdot fu$ bzw. $\sigma_{xx} \approx 0,83 \text{ GPa s/m} \cdot fu$.

For the case of a symmetric plate mode, i.e.

$$u_z(x, y) = u_{\max} \sin(2\pi x/\lambda_x) \sin(2\pi y/\lambda_y), \quad (3.47)$$

this yields the following with (3.38) and (3.41)

$$\varepsilon_{xx} \approx \frac{u''_z(x)d}{2(1 + u'_z(x)^2)^{3/2}}, \quad (3.48)$$

and correspondingly for ε_{yy} , so that finally (3.39) can be applied. The following results with some reformulation and neglecting the terms in u_{\max}^2 , da $u_{\max} \ll 1$:

$$\varepsilon_{xy} \approx \frac{2\pi^2 du_{\max}}{\lambda_x \lambda_y} \stackrel{\lambda_x = \lambda_y}{\approx} \varepsilon_{xx}. \quad (3.49)$$

All of the remaining strains are thus reduced to the determination of the out-of-plane vibration component. The stresses can then be calculated from $\sigma_{xx,yy} = \varepsilon_{xx,yy}E$ or $\sigma_{xy} = \varepsilon_{xy}G$, where the shear modulus G is related to Young's modulus by

$$G = \frac{E}{2(1 + \nu)}. \quad (3.50)$$

For steel, $E \approx 200$ GPa, and with $\nu \approx 0,3$: $G \approx E/2,6 \approx 80$ GPa. The shear stresses $\sigma_{xy,yy}$ are thus considerably lower than the normal stresses $\sigma_{xx,yy}$.

Equation (3.45) can also be derived from theory given suitable assumptions. Differentiation yields the following from (3.25) for a purely transverse wave ($A = 0$):

$$\varepsilon_{xx} = \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial x} = -\frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} = -2kD\eta_\beta \sin(\eta_\beta z) \sin(kx). \quad (3.51)$$

The maximum is achieved for $\sin(kx) = 1$, i.e. $\pi/2 = kx = 2\pi/\lambda x \Rightarrow x = \lambda/4$. z deflection at this point is

$$u_{\max}(z_0, x_0) = 2kD \cos(\eta_\beta z_0) \Rightarrow \eta_\beta z_0 = \arccos\left(\frac{u_{\max}}{2kD}\right). \quad (3.52)$$

Maximum x strain is thus

$$\varepsilon_{xx,\max} = 2k\eta_\beta D \sin\left(\arccos\left(\frac{u_{\max}}{2kD}\right)\right). \quad (3.53)$$

Equation (3.51) can be further simplified, as the maximum strain is reached at the edge of the plate, i.e. for $z = d/2$:

$$\varepsilon_{xx} = 2k\eta_\beta D \sin(\eta_\beta d/2) \approx 2k\eta_\beta^2 Dd. \quad (3.54)$$

The approximation $\sin(x) \approx x$ for small angles of $x \ll 1$ is used here. Applying the further definitions $k = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda}$ und $\eta_\beta^2 = k^2 - \omega^2/c_\beta^2 \approx k^2$ yields

$$\varepsilon_{xx} \approx k^3 Dd. \quad (3.55)$$

Maximum deflection in the z direction is

$$u_{\max} \stackrel{(3.52)}{=} 2kD \cos(\eta_\beta z_0) \approx 2kD, \quad (3.56)$$

where this time the approximation $\cos(x) \approx 1$ for small angles of $x \ll 1$ is used. Substituting (3.56) in (3.55) finally yields

$$\varepsilon_{xx} \approx \frac{2\pi^2 du_{\max}}{\lambda^2}. \quad (3.57)$$

Method 2. Calculation of $r(x)$ from u_z with equation for a circle

The values $u_z(\vec{x})$ are in discretized form for a measurement. The tangent circle can then be determined, for example, by constructing a circle through each point (x_1, y_1) and its two nearest neighbors (x_2, y_2) and (x_3, y_3) , where the center (x_m, y_m) and radius r follow the quadratic system of equations

$$(x_i - x_m)^2 + (y_i - y_m)^2 = r^2, \quad (3.58)$$

from which radius r can be calculated:

$$r = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{((x_1 - x_2)^2 + (y_1 - y_2)^2) ((x_1 - x_3)^2 + (y_1 - y_3)^2) ((x_2 - x_3)^2 + (y_2 - y_3)^2)}{(x_1(y_3 - y_2) + x_2(y_1 - y_3) + x_3(y_2 - y_1))^2}} \quad (3.59)$$

Method 3. Calculation of $r(x)$ from u_z by parabolic fit

The tangent circle method is suitable if only a few points per vibration cycle are available and therefore no fit can be calculated for multiple points. If the measurement has been performed with a finer grid, it is more expedient to fit a parabola $y(x) = a_2x^2 + a_1x + a_0$ through each point (x_i, y_i) and its $n-1$ nearest neighbors. The radius r of the tangent circle is taken from the radius of curvature of this parabola at its peak. Substituting the peak ordinate $x_s = (-a_1/2a_2)$ in (3.41) yields:

$$r = \frac{1}{2a_2}. \quad (3.60)$$

Coefficient a_2 is obtained from a least-squares fit:

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{j=i-(n-1)/2}^{i+(n-1)/2} (y_i - a_2x_i^2 - a_1x_i - a_0)^2 \stackrel{!}{=} \min. \quad (3.61)$$

This yields

$$a_2 = A/B \quad (3.62)$$

where

$$A = (\sum x^2)^2 \sum y - \sum x^3 (\sum x \sum y - n \sum xy) + (\sum x)^2 \sum x^2 y - \sum x^2 (\sum x \sum xy + n \sum x^2 y) \quad (3.63)$$

$$B = (\sum x^2)^3 + n (\sum x^3)^2 + (\sum x)^2 \sum x^4 - \sum x^2 (2 \sum x \sum x^3 + n \sum x^4). \quad (3.64)$$

The advantage of the parabolic fit is the improved signal-to-noise ratio.

Example

Fig. 3.17 shows the calculated strain distribution on a CFRP plate from vibrometer measurements. From top to bottom, the ε_{xx} and ε_{yy} distribution was calculated first from the $u_x(\vec{x})$ - bzw. $u_y(\vec{x})$ deflections, then from the $u_z(\vec{x})$ deflections with the circular fit and finally from the $u_z(\vec{x})$ deflections with a 5-point parabolic fit. Each grayscale plot is normalized to the same maximum, meaning that the agreement is not only qualitative but also quantitative.

As can also be clearly seen, the last method of direct calculation from the in-plane deflections is even superior. This is due to both the averaging over several points and the fact that the out-of-plane deflection can be measured with a better signal-to-noise ratio because of the laser beam geometry.

Figure 3.17: Comparison of in-plane strain data determined by various methods, a. Out-of-plane deflection u_z , maximum deflection is 10 nm, b/c. Direct calculation from 3D vibration data: $\partial u_x/\partial x$, and $\partial u_y/\partial y$, d/e. ε_{xx} and ε_{yy} from circular fit to u_z (Method 2), f/g. ε_{xx} and ε_{yy} from parabolic fit (5 points) to u_z (Method 3). Maximum strains in each case are $8 \cdot 10^{-7}$.

Chapter 4

Technical Implementation of Acoustic Thermography

4.1 Advantages and Disadvantages of using Ultrasonic Welding Systems

4.1.1 Effects of Parameter Changes

Electronically adjustable parameters

Various parameters can be changed for thermographic measurement. In addition to those which can be adjusted directly on the generator (Table 4.1), the coupling point of the sonotrode and the attachment of the specimen can also be changed. It is also possible to place a couplant such as aluminum tape to the coupling point in order to protect it.

Parameter	Value range	Standard value
Excitation time	0.001–30 s	1 s
Excitation force (contact force)	63–1600 N	500 N
Excitation amplitude	10–100 %	100 %

Table 4.1: Parameters which can be digitally adjusted on the front panel of the Branson 2000f generator.

Fig. 4.1 shows the spectrum for a turbine blade during excitation with the Branson ultrasonic welding system and the above standard values. It can be clearly seen that the spectrum includes both the 20 kHz line as well as its higher harmonics. This can be attributed to the fact that there is no solid connection between the sonotrode and the specimen. This results in “hammering” by the sonotrode. This situation can only be mitigated at low amplitudes or with a damping couplant (such as a cloth strip).

However, it proves that excitation of the higher harmonics is even useful, as this renders the resulting deflection shape more homogeneous. This is therefore not a monofrequent system, but rather a multi-frequency excitation.

Figure 4.1: Example spectrum for vibration of a turbine blade during excitation with Branson ultrasonic welding system.

Changing sonotrode position

Let $I(d)$ designate the infrared intensity measured at a defect as a function of sonotrode position d on the underside of the blade. Fig. 4.2 shows a typical measurement on a turbine blade with a crack. A piece of reflecting foil was also bonded to the blade close to the crack for determination of the vibration amplitude by laser vibrometry. This foil is also heated by internal friction, as is also shown in Fig. 4.2. A large variation in vibration and heating can be seen.

In this example, the ratio of the highest to the lowest measured infrared signal was $I_{\max}/I_{\min} = 12$. Although in this case an optimum coupling position can be found on the blade root (4.5 cm from the left end), this is not necessarily the best position for detecting defects at another position on the blade. The variation with sonotrode position is generally lower for more complex blade constructions (multiple walls), but I_{\max}/I_{\min} is typically still 2–4).

Figure 4.2: Variation in defect signal with sonotrode position.

One explanation for this can be found in the excited modes. Specific optimum frequencies for excitation of the defect can only be poorly excited depending on the position of the sonotrode. This can also be seen in qualitative comparisons with finite element simulations [HH07].

Changing contact force

A change in the contact force can tend to result in an increased vibration amplitude of the specimen. However, as is shown in Fig. 4.3, this effect is by no means monotonic. Blade vibration is shown for four blades of the same type. Depending on the blade, the optimum (i.e. the highest vibration) is at a different contact force. It can also be seen that efficiency decreases again for high contact forces.

Figure 4.3: Variation in blade vibration with contact force for four blades of the same type (different colors indicate individual blades).

As described above, in normal operating mode the generator finds the optimum frequency f_{Opt} by itself, although in addition to surrounding conditions the contact force has the greatest influence on f_{Opt} . Fig. 4.4 shows the dependence of ultrasonic frequency $f_{\text{Opt}}(F)$ on contact force. The frequency found by the generator was plotted against contact force for four different types of turbine blades (in some cases several blades for a type). Two generators and stacks of the same type were used for comparison (filled vs. outlined symbols). The approximately linear correlation between ultrasonic frequency and contact force can be clearly seen, where the slope depends on the generator or stack used and not on the specimen.

Figure 4.4: Dependence of optimum ultrasonic frequency on contact force for two different Branson systems.

This yields the explanation for the nonmonotonic change in vibration with contact force 4.3: excitation frequency changes with force. However, this means that ranges of higher or lower response are scanned depending on the spectrum for the individual blade.

Fig. 4.5 schematically shows the spectra for two blades of the same type and the frequency ranges scanned by the generator on variation of the contact forces between F_{min} and F_{max} . If $f_1 = f_{\text{Opt}}(F_{\text{min}})$ and $f_2 = f_{\text{Opt}}(F_{\text{max}})$, the frequency ranges from $n \cdot f_1$ to $n \cdot f_2$ are scanned. $n = 1$ corresponds to the range about the fundamental frequency and $n > 1$ the range about the n th harmonic. The solid lines delimit a narrow frequency range ($\Delta f = 50$ Hz) and the dashed lines a wide range ($\Delta f = 300$ Hz).

It is apparent that variation of the excitation frequencies results in differing vibration behavior of the blades. In addition, individual parts will react differently even at the same excitation frequency due to their slightly different spectra. This situation is investigated in more detail in the next section.

Figure 4.5: Spectra for two blades and frequency ranges scanned by Branson generator during variation of contact force (schematic). The frequency ranges are scanned from low to high frequencies.

4.1.2 Repeatability and Reproducibility between Parts

The above parameters are now assumed to be constant for further measurements. This enables further investigation of the following two examination properties:

- **Repeatability.** Variability of measurement results (vibration, infrared signal) from measurement to measurement with no change in measurement setup or examination parameters, especially for the identical specimen. However, changes such as unclamping and reclamping of the object are explicitly allowed.
- **Reproducibility between parts.** Variability of measurement results with no change in measurement setup or examination parameters, but with different specimens, especially as regards differences in the measured data for specimens of the same type.

Repeatability

It should first be noted that not every choice of parameters results in stable measurement results. This can be seen in Figs. 4.6 and 4.7. In each case, the vibrometer signal in the time domain was converted to spectral data with a sliding Fourier transform, thus showing the time history of the individual frequency components.

First, Fig. 4.6 shows the result for a stable excitation in which the variation in the individual frequency components is slight after a certain settling period. Taking the root sum of squares of the vibration amplitudes over all frequencies and component directions as a measure of repeatability, the variation is typically 10–20%.

In contrast, Fig. 4.7 shows the result for an unstable excitation in which a step change (from 80 to 100 kHz) occurred in the dominant vibration frequency after roughly 0.2 s. It can easily occur that such measurements exhibit qualitatively good repeatability in the sense that similar steps occur on repeated measurement, but the

Figure 4.6: Example of stable ultrasonic excitation. Bottom: time history of vibrometer signal, top: results of sliding Fourier transform with using 50 ms window in each case. Variation in the individual frequency components is low.

variation in the absolute numbers is significantly higher than for stable excitations. As was already shown in Fig. 2.7 on p. 15, different frequencies correspond to different vibration modes of the specimen. This can in turn result in a change in heating at the defect. Heat production at the defect is thus no longer constant with time for unstable excitations. This renders mathematical analysis of the infrared signal difficult.

It cannot be generally stated when the excitation is stable, as this is especially affected by clamping of the specimen. In principle, the frequency of stable excitations increases with decreasing generator amplitude and increasing stability of the clamp. A special form of unstable excitation is so-called “acoustic chaos” [HLZ04], which manifests itself by the increased occurrence of subharmonics in the spectrum. Although the model for the formation of these subharmonics discussed in the indicated article is understandable, its experimental implementation is difficult.

Reproducibility between parts

As explained above, the repeatability of examination by acoustic thermography is quite good at stable excitation conditions. However, the important aspect of reproducibility from one part to the next has remained practically uninvestigated to date. Different specimens of the same type should vibrate at similar amplitudes on ultrasonic excitation in order to enable uniformly good defect detectability.

However, it was now determined in series tests on turbine blades that to some extent, the vibration amplitudes at identical points (such as the trailing edge tip) on different blades of the same type differ greatly. Fig. 4.8 shows measurements on six turbine blades of the same type, obtained using two identically configured

Figure 4.7: Example of an unstable ultrasonic excitation. The dominant frequency changes from 80 to 100 kHz at time $t \approx 0,45$ s.

Branson 2000 systems (cf. Fig. 4.4). Vibrometer measurements were possible only with System 1.

Tesa Power Strips were bonded to all of the blades at identical positions to investigate the reproducibility of the infrared signals, as these heat on vibration due to viscoelastic damping¹. The vibration amplitudes were recorded in the immediate vicinity of the Power Strips. It is apparent that scatter in the infrared signals is different for the two systems. Especially for System 2, there is a factor of 17 between the minimum and maximum measured values! A factor of only 3.2 was calculated for System 1. Scatter in the vibration data is somewhat less than that in the infrared signals.

Figure 4.8: Variation in measured vibration amplitudes and Power Strip signals in 6 turbine blades of the same type.

As the origin of the scatter is suspected to lie in the frequency control behavior of the generator, it is expedient to first evaluate the frequency ranges. It can be seen in Fig. 4.9 that the frequency ranges of the two systems do not overlap. This can be

¹Cracks could not be used for the comparison, as the blades had defects at different locations, and the individual crack properties would have also had an effect.

easily explained from the variation in the resonant frequency of the two piezoelectric exciters used (Fig. 4.4). the blades are thus excited at different frequencies.

Figure 4.9: Variation of measured frequency ranges for ultrasonic excitation in the two systems used, start/end frequency during excitation shown in each case.

This suspicion can be corroborated by careful variation of the signal at the generator frequency offset input² to generate a sweep, enabling in-situ measurement of the blade resonant frequencies during ultrasonic examination. This yields the values summed for all harmonics at a given excitation frequency.

This derived parameter is plotted for the six investigated blades in Fig. 4.10. A log scale was used for the ordinate to enable better comparison of the scatter in vibration amplitudes. The quotient of the maximum and minimum particle velocity is also shown in the lower section. The fundamental frequency at which the blades are excited is plotted on the abscissa in each case.

It is apparent that scatter for a frequency such as $f_B = 19,750$ Hz is less than for $f_B = 19,820$ Hz. If the frequency ranges determined in Fig. 4.9 are now plotted, it can be seen that the greater scatter measured with System 2 can be attributed to the slightly shifted frequency range in which the differences in vibration amplitudes happen to be greater. As the spectra depend on the blades used in each case, no generally applicable optimum frequency range can be indicated.

This conclusively demonstrates that fundamental principles preclude the achievement of good reproducibility by multi-frequency excitation with the ultrasonic welding units, as the individual effects of the specimens cannot be accounted for. However, it should be noted that scatter would have been considerably higher still without statistical smoothing with the harmonics.

Improving reproducibility between parts

The limits of reproducibility for multi-frequency power ultrasonic excitation thus lie in the resonance spectra of the individual blades and are thus outside of the influence of the examiner. However, it follows from the above results that at least an improvement in reproducibility could still be achieved by extending the frequency range used during a measurement.

Cyclic variation of the signal at the generator frequency offset input enables scanning of regions of varying degrees of scatter during a measurement. These dif-

²A DC signal applied to the frequency offset input of the generator is interpreted by the generator as the starting point for automatic frequency scanning, enabling the search for the optimum frequency to be shortened. However, an undocumented property of the device enables continuous influencing of the control behavior with an applied AC signal where the frequency is not too high ($\lesssim 50$ Hz), with the result that a sweep can also be generated by the application of a ramp.

Figure 4.10: Overall vibration of blades calculated from measured spectra, top: log-scale spectra of 6 investigated blades, bottom: ratio of maximum and minimum values for each frequency. The frequency ranges used by System 1 and System 2 are also shown (cf. Fig. 4.9)

ferences are compensated on average, resulting in a lower effective scatter. However, the disadvantage is the reduced efficiency of the excitation. A reduction in scatter by roughly a factor of 3 can be achieved experimentally by this method.

Another interesting method is the “acoustic chaos” already mentioned above [HLZ04]. Under certain (as yet still uncontrollable) conditions, hammering results not only in the excitation of higher frequencies but also of subharmonics. This extends the spectral excitation bandwidth, resulting in improved efficiency and better reproducibility from one part to the next.

4.1.3 Summary and Consequences

The apparent main advantage of the ultrasonic welding systems is certainly the possibility of quickly constructing an excitation system for acoustic thermography using components which have been proven in manufacturing. It is for this reason that nearly all previous investigations have been performed using such systems. Because of the high mechanical output, exact parameter adjustment is usually not absolutely necessary in the first step. However, the inability to adjust the frequency significantly hampers optimization of the method, and reproducibility from one part to the next in particular is inadequate in some circumstances, as the individual spectra of the specimens cannot be accounted for.

Although the operation deflection shape is more uniform due to the excitation of higher harmonics than for monofrequent excitation, and reproducibility is improved due to the possibility of exciting several resonant frequencies, this is often still in-

sufficient. In addition, a quadratic dependence of the infrared signal on deflection can be observed in many measurements (cf. Section 7.1.1), for which reason scatter in the vibration data has an even more pronounced effect on any defect heating.

A further disadvantage is the contacting sonic coupling and especially hammering of the sonotrode, which can result in damage to the coupling point in individual cases. Parts made of plastics, CFRP or GRP are especially affected by this. However, placement of aluminum tape on the excitation point is often already sufficient to prevent surface damage.

The logical consequence of the above disadvantages is the need to develop an excitation system with a tunable exciter and to ensure the most solid possible connections between the exciter and the specimen. Only in this way can optimum adaptation of the excitation frequency to the individual specimen and protection of the coupling point be achieved.

4.2 Acoustic Thermography with Tunable Piezoelectric Exciters

As was explained in the previous section, the reproducibility issues with ultrasonic welding units can be attributed to the inability to control the frequency. An evident solution is thus to construct a system with tunable exciters which adapts itself to the respective specimen in order to achieve resonant excitation. Although electromagnetic shakers can in principle also be used as exciters, these systems can usually only be implemented in the range below 20 kHz. High-power piezoelectric crystals are therefore used instead.

4.2.1 Setup of Ultrasonic Excitation System

A wide-spectrum exciter must be used in the construction of the requisite ultrasonic excitation system. In contrast to a mechanical resonant system, although this reduces the available power level, piezoelectric exciters are available on the market (such as in the injection valve developed by Siemens for automotive construction) which can generate large stroke distances already at relatively low voltage (on the order of tens of V). This is achieved by their construction as stack actuators consisting of many thin layers of piezoelectric ceramic, enabling the generation of large deflections already at low voltages. This enables operation with an audio amplifier. Fig. 4.11 shows the spectrum for such a piezoelectric exciter.

Another possibility is certainly also the use of a piezoelectric transducer from an ultrasonic welding system. Although these exciters represent optimized resonant vibrating systems, they can still be sufficiently detuned under certain conditions to enable resonant excitation of specimens. Specifically, if the specimen is bolted to the piezoelectric exciter with a suitable clamp, the resonance condition—in this case the length of the metallic cylinders which enclose the piezoelectric ceramic—is thus changed [Her05]. This enables use of the originally narrow-band exciter over a wide frequency range. Although these exciters are generally operated at high voltages (typically 1000 V), satisfactory results can also be achieved here at lower voltages, such as with stereo audio amplifiers in which two channels are combined [Her05].

Figure 4.11: Spectrum for one of the Diesel injector piezoelectric transducers used, without coupled specimen. The wide range of resonant frequencies enables a wide-spectrum excitation of the specimens. z deflection (parallel to the transducer axis) dominates for most frequencies.

In both cases, the exciter is controlled by a function generator and an audio amplifier. By combining both end stages together, the Ecler PAM 1400 amplifier used in this study can deliver a maximum voltage difference of 160 V and can be operated at up to roughly 60 kHz.

4.2.2 Results

Fig. 4.5 on p. 48 showed the spectra for two blades of identical type. The blades are excited to forced vibrations at $n \cdot 20$ kHz ($n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$) with an ultrasonic welding unit operating at 20 kHz.

This resulted in significant scatter in the vibration amplitudes of the investigated specimens, as resonant frequencies are only achieved by chance. Although the higher harmonics result in an improvement compared with the purely monofrequent excitation, tunable excitation in which the individual blade resonant frequencies are deliberately excited is better.

For example, if a blade from an aircraft engine is bonded to a tunable piezoelectric exciter (adhesive: X-60), the resonant frequencies of the blade can then be deliberately excited. Fig. 4.12 shows several infrared images which were obtained with sweep excitation (30–50 kHz). The following conclusions are evident:

1. A sufficiently large infrared signal I_{IR} is obtained only at resonant frequencies.
2. Even for resonant excitation, both cracks in the blade cannot always be seen (see arrows above blade).

It can be further derived from the first conclusion that although sweep excitation yields good reproducibility from one part to the next (averaging over several resonant frequencies), it is relatively inefficient, as it is operated for a long time at low vibration.

The second conclusion is more serious. As was already shown in Fig. 2.7 on p. 15, different resonant frequencies correspond to very different operation deflection shapes. This results in a change in the efficiency of the modes, as differential

Figure 4.12: from aircraft engine with two cracks on blade tip excited with a tunable piezoelectric exciter.

distortion must be present at the crack for heat generation (cf. Section 7.1.2 for a more exact analysis).

Both of these conclusions taken together yield the logical consequence that the ultrasonic pulse should be used only at resonant frequencies and that several resonant frequencies should be excited simultaneously or that excitation should jump from one resonant frequency to the next in order to compensate for the different efficiency levels. The latter possibility is illustrated in Fig. 4.13. Once the spectrum of the specimen has been determined and the N highest resonant peaks found with a corresponding algorithm, these are excited in sequence for a specific time τ . Excitation is then stopped for time τ and then excitation jumps to the next frequency. The evaluation is then performed with a lock-in analysis, for example (Section 6.3.2, p. 82), over the N cycles with frequency $1/(2\tau)$.

[ZRDB03] proposes frequency modulation during the excitation of plastic parts, corresponding to the aforementioned sweep method. This is used to blur the standing wave field caused by the resonant excitation, the strain antinodes of which give rise to interference from local bulk heating (cf. Fig. 6.4, p. 80 and Section 7, where this aspect is investigated in further detail). Although this is possible in principle and is less efficient than in metals due to the higher damping in plastic (broader resonant peaks), the restriction to resonant frequencies would also be better here.

4.2.3 Advantages and Disadvantages of Adaptive Excitation

In addition to the possibility of efficient excitation, a further advantage of adaptive excitation is that smaller exciters and a lower electrical power level are sufficient, thus enabling miniaturization of the entire setup. 4.14 shows a prototype for a complete measurement system which also includes an integral structure-borne noise sensor to

Figure 4.13: Optimized flexible excitation in which the system rests at each resonant frequency for a specified time.

measure the vibration. A small uncooled infrared camera (FLIR A10) measures the emitted infrared radiation.

Figure 4.14: Prototype for a miniaturized measurement setup for adaptive acoustic thermography [Her05]

This system also reduces the load on the coupling point, as a solid connection can be implemented between the exciter and specimen, thus eliminating hammering.

The possibility of frequency selection also enables non-destructiveness of the system to be influenced within certain limits, as the resulting deflection shape—at least for parts with simple geometry—can be selected such that critical parts are not highly loaded (cf. Fig. 5.16 on p. 72). The disadvantage is the longer measuring time required to determine the spectrum and to excite the individual resonant frequencies.

The quality of reproducibility of the various methods can be ordered approximately as follows: non-tunable monofrequent excitation is the poorest, as it takes no account whatsoever of the individual spectrum. In non-tunable multi-frequency excitation (welding units) only moderately good reproducibility is still achieved. Slightly tunable multi-frequency excitation (such as using modified welding units) yields better reproducibility. Although a high degree of efficiency is achieved with resonant monofrequent excitation, the same vibration amplitude is not automatically reached from one part to the next due to the individual spectra. Adjustment of the piezoelectric voltage is also necessary here.

The best reproducibility should result from resonant multi-frequency excitation, in which all or the N highest resonant peaks are excited over a wide frequency range.

4.3 Other Alternative Excitation Possibilities

In the previous sections, ultrasonic coupling was achieved either by a pneumatic clamp (ultrasonic welding unit) or a threaded connection (adaptive system). Both methods necessitate the fabrication of a suitable clamp for the specimen. Coupling through air or water would be more convenient.

For the first case, the power transfer is so slight that no measurable heating occurs at the defect. The achievable vibration amplitude is however sufficient for defect localization by vibrometry [KSB01].

The second method, sonic coupling through liquids, has already been tested in an initial experiment at MTU [Neu05]. In this study, a 150 W cleaning bath from Rohrer Ultraschall was used to demonstrate the basic feasibility of coupling through water. Fig. 4.15 shows the results for several selected specimens. For all of the tests, the objects were immersed in the bath with a grip fixed to the table, which ensured adequate mechanical stability. The ultrasonic bath was then switched on with a timer for one second. The evaluation was performed by pulse phase analysis (Section 6.3.3) over a period of two seconds. An amplitude image is shown in each case, to which a certain percentage of the background image was added to enable recognition of the object. An interference signal due to the water waves can be seen in the background in some cases.

The top row shows cracks in two turbine blades (cf. Figs. 4.12, p. 55, and 7.1, p. 91), while the images in the bottom row demonstrate that excitation in the water bath has the advantage of enabling the investigation of mechanically fragile materials (ceramics) or parts (16-bit microchip) with less probability of damage, as there is no mechanical coupling to the hard exciter.

Results obtained using this cleaning bath with larger turbine blades ($m > 5$ kg) were unsatisfactory. It can be anticipated that resonant excitation would generate

Figure 4.15: Acoustic thermography with excitation in an ultrasonic cleaning bath. The arrows indicate the location of the cracks.

higher infrared signals here as well. Further investigations of this method appear promising, especially for specimens where solid sonic contact to the exciter is problematic.

Chapter 5

Investigation of Non-Destructiveness

An advantage of acoustic thermography is the possibility to also examine objects with complex geometry. Stress redistribution occurs in the object as a result of the geometry, increasing local material loading. This is especially the case at notched points or around holes. Cracks represent a special form of discontinuity, as in the theoretical ideal case, a crack tip represents a stress singularity.

The following sections provide a brief overview of the most important aspects of fracture mechanics within the framework of this study. These concepts are required both in interpreting the infrared signals in Section 7 as well as for estimating non-destructiveness (Section 5.6).

5.1 Stress Amplification at Discontinuities

5.1.1 Stress Concentration at Holes and Slots

If a bar of infinite length, width d and thickness t (cf. Fig. 5.1) oriented in the x direction is acted upon by a uniaxial force $\vec{F} = (F, 0, 0)$ normal to its cross-sectional area $A = td$, the stress σ in this bar at all points is

$$\sigma(x, y, z) = \frac{F}{td}. \quad (5.1)$$

Figure 5.1: Stress in an infinitely long bar.

Infinite plate with cylindrical hole

However, if this body contains a geometric opening such as a cylindrical hole with diameter a , stress is no longer spatially independent. For an infinite plate with the

center of the hole at $(x, y) = (0, 0)$, the following can be written in polar coordinates for a uniaxial stress $\vec{\sigma} = (\sigma, 0)$ acting in the x direction [TG70]:

$$\sigma(r, \theta) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{for } r < a \\ \frac{1}{2}\sigma \left(1 + \left(\frac{a}{r}\right)^2\right) - \frac{1}{2}\sigma \left(1 + 3\left(\frac{a}{r}\right)^4\right) \cos(2\theta) & \text{for } r \geq a, \end{cases} \quad (5.2)$$

see Figs. 5.2 and 5.3. The points of extreme stress are found at

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma(a, \pi/2) &= \sigma(a, 3\pi/2) = +3\sigma \\ \sigma(a, 0) &= \sigma(a, \pi) = -\sigma \end{aligned} \quad (5.3)$$

Figure 5.2: Stress distribution around a cylindrical hole in an infinite plate for uniaxial stress in the horizontal direction. The points of maximum stress are above and below the hole. $\sigma = \sigma_{\max} = 3\sigma_{\text{nom}}$ at these points (cf. Eq. (5.4)). From left to right: $\sigma(r, \theta)$, $\sigma(r, \theta)^2$ and a thermal image of a plate with a hole during ultrasonic excitation, which exhibits a qualitatively similar signature (cf. Fig. 7.18 on p. 104)

The following maximum stress thus results

$$\sigma_{\max} = 3\sigma =: K_t \sigma. \quad (5.4)$$

Factor K_t is called the stress concentration factor and in this case is independent of a .

Infinite strip with cylindrical hole

In a plate of finite width d , the hole results in remaining ligaments (residual material next to the hole, cf. Fig. 5.4) in which the reduced cross-sectional area now results in a nominal stress of

$$\sigma_{\text{nom}} = \frac{F}{t(d-a)} \quad (5.5)$$

(cf. Eq. (5.1)). Maximum stress is

$$\sigma_{\max} = K_t \sigma_{\text{nom}}, \quad (5.6)$$

where now the stress concentration factor K_t is no longer a constant, but rather can be calculated as follows [Pil05]:

$$K_t \approx 3 - 3.14 \left(\frac{a}{d}\right) + 3.667 \left(\frac{a}{d}\right)^2 - 1.527 \left(\frac{a}{d}\right)^3. \quad (5.7)$$

As $a/d \rightarrow 1$, both the nominal and maximum stress go to infinity, led by the latter (Fig. 5.4, right).

Figure 5.3: Three-dimensional diagram of stress distribution about a cylindrical hole in an infinite plate for uniaxial stress in the horizontal direction. Stress is σ_{nom} at sufficient distance from the defect. $\sigma = 3\sigma_{\text{nom}}$ above and below the hole, while $\sigma = -\sigma_{\text{nom}}$ in the perpendicular direction.

Figure 5.4: Infinite strip with hole (diameter a). The remaining ligaments of width $d - a$ have to transmit the stress, for which reason nominal stress increases (Eq. (5.5)).

Infinite strip with elliptical hole

Figure 5.5: a. Infinite strip with elliptical hole, b. Infinite strip with edge slot.

Similar conditions are also found for elliptical holes with axes $2a$ and $2b$ [Pil05, p. 291],

$$\sigma_{\text{nom}} = \frac{\sigma}{1 - 2b/d} \tag{5.8}$$

and

$$K_t \approx C_1(a, b) + C_2(a, b) \left(\frac{2a}{d} \right) + C_3(a, b) \left(\frac{2a}{d} \right)^2 + C_4(a, b) \left(\frac{2a}{d} \right)^3 \quad (5.9)$$

where

$$C_1(a, b) = 1.109 - 0.188\sqrt{a/b} + 2.086a/b \quad (5.10)$$

$$C_1(a, b) = -0.486 + 0.213\sqrt{a/b} - 2.588a/b \quad (5.11)$$

$$C_1(a, b) = 3.816 - 5.510\sqrt{a/b} + 4.638a/b \quad (5.12)$$

$$C_1(a, b) = -2.438 + 5.485\sqrt{a/b} - 4.126a/b, \quad (5.13)$$

cf. Fig. 5.5a.

Semiinfinite plate with slot perpendicular to edge

The following relationships hold for a semiinfinite plate with a slot, the tip of which is a distance h from the surface and which can be approximated by a circle with radius r [Pil05, p. 274]:

$$\sigma_{\max} = K_t \sigma \quad (5.14)$$

where

$$K_t \approx 0.855 + 2.21\sqrt{h/r} \quad \text{für } 1 \leq h/r \leq 361, \quad (5.15)$$

See Fig 5.5b.

The important conclusion here is that rounded slots produce lower and more pointed slots produce higher local peak stresses where the (lower) stress concentration in the first case is spread over a larger area [Bro88]. This concept will also be important for estimating non-destructiveness in Section 5.6.

5.1.2 Stress intensity in Cracks

In the simplest approximation, a crack can be regarded as a special case of a slot of vanishing extent ($r \rightarrow 0$). Its opposing edges are called *crack surfaces*, *crack flanks* or *crack faces* [GS01]. In this section they are taken to be free from loading, although this is usually otherwise in reality (see Section 5.2).

As $r \rightarrow 0$ in Eq. (5.15), K_t goes to infinity. A different concept must therefore be applied for cracks, namely that of stress intensity.

This requires that the different modes be distinguished in which a crack can move (Fig. 5.6), namely opening (I), in plane shearing (II) and out-of-plane shearing (III). Various terms are given in the literature, such as opening, edge sliding and tearing [Par81, Gdo04] or tensile, in-plane shear and anti-plane shear [Ric67].

In linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM), the body is regarded as elastic over the entire volume. Any inelastic phenomena (such as plastic deformations) must therefore be restricted to a negligibly small volume from a macroscopic perspective.

Mode I

The lines of force for mode I movement are sketched in Fig. 5.7. It is immediately apparent that a uniaxial stress distribution (parallel to the plate edges) becomes biaxial close to the defect [Bro88].

Figure 5.6: The three principal crack modes I–III (see text for details).

Figure 5.7: Lines of force in a plate with slot under uniaxial load. For points sufficiently far away from the defect, the lines of force are parallel to the x axis (uniaxial stress). Close to the defect this becomes a biaxial stress condition, or in the general case a triaxial one.

The stress field components can be derived for this case ([Sne46], [Gdo04]). Close to the crack tip these are¹

$$\sigma_x^I(r, \theta) = \frac{K_I}{\sqrt{2\pi r}} \cos \frac{\theta}{2} \left(1 - \sin \frac{\theta}{2} \sin \frac{3\theta}{2} \right) \quad (5.16)$$

$$\sigma_y^I(r, \theta) = \frac{K_I}{\sqrt{2\pi r}} \cos \frac{\theta}{2} \left(1 + \sin \frac{\theta}{2} \sin \frac{3\theta}{2} \right) \quad (5.17)$$

$$\tau_{xy}^I(r, \theta) = \frac{K_I}{\sqrt{2\pi r}} \cos \frac{\theta}{2} \sin \frac{\theta}{2} \cos \frac{3\theta}{2} \quad (5.18)$$

As $r \rightarrow 0$, stress goes to infinity, i.e. the ideal crack tip represents a stress singularity. The stress intensity factor (SIF) K_I defines the intensity of this singularity at the crack tip [Par81]. It is generally defined as [Pil05]

$$K = C\sigma\sqrt{\pi a}, \quad (5.19)$$

where σ is the nominal stress, a is the defect size and C is a constant which depends on the geometry and dimensions of the defect and the object. The units of the stress intensity factor are $\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$.

In addition, Irwin [Irw58] demonstrated that each crack tip stress field can be defined by Eqs. (5.16) to (5.18) regardless of the geometry of the crack or body. Only the stress intensity factor has to be adjusted according to actual conditions.

¹The system of equations (5.16)–(5.18) represents a simplification for areas close to the crack. A more exact definition can be obtained with addends in r^0 , $r^{1/2}$, r^1 etc. The first of these in particular ensures that $\sigma_y \rightarrow \sigma$ for $r \rightarrow \infty$, as at least the external stress still acts in the far field. However, σ_x decreases to zero a sufficiently large distances from the crack [Bro88]. Of course terms in r^α where $\alpha \geq 0$ can be neglected for $r \rightarrow 0$, so that Equations (5.16)–(5.18) are retained.

For given geometries, stress intensity factors can be determined analytically (such as by the Westergaard functions [Par81, Gdo04]), numerically (with Green's function or weighting functions, by integral transforms or FEM calculation) [Gdo04] or experimentally (by photoelasticity, Moiré, holography) [Gdo04, Puk87, SD96]. There are also extensive literature references [GS97, Hut68] and tables [Pil05] on this topic.

In addition to the stress components, the deflections of the crack faces in Mode I can also be defined [Par81]:

$$u_x(r, \theta) = \frac{K_I}{G} \sqrt{\frac{r}{2\pi}} \cos \frac{\theta}{2} \left(1 - 2\nu + \sin^2 \frac{\theta}{2} \right) \quad (5.20)$$

$$u_y(r, \theta) = \frac{K_I}{G} \sqrt{\frac{r}{2\pi}} \sin \frac{\theta}{2} \left(2 - 2\nu - \cos^2 \frac{\theta}{2} \right) \quad (5.21)$$

$$u_z(r, \theta) = 0, \quad (5.22)$$

where G is the shear modulus and ν is Poisson's ratio.

Fig. 5.8 shows the stress distribution $\sqrt{(\sigma_x^I)^2 + (\sigma_y^I)^2}$ and deflection of a crack in mode I (cf. Fig. 7.12, p. 100).

Figure 5.8: Stress distribution (brightness) and deflection of a crack in mode I based on Equations (5.16)–(5.17) and (5.20)–(5.22)

Mode II

In this case the stress field components can be given as follows [Gdo04, p. 24]:

$$\sigma_x^{\text{II}}(r, \theta) = -\frac{K_{\text{II}}}{\sqrt{2\pi r}} \sin \frac{\theta}{2} \left(2 + \cos \frac{\theta}{2} \cos \frac{3\theta}{2} \right) \quad (5.23)$$

$$\sigma_y^{\text{II}}(r, \theta) = \frac{K_{\text{II}}}{\sqrt{2\pi r}} \sin \frac{\theta}{2} \cos \frac{\theta}{2} \cos \frac{3\theta}{2} \quad (5.24)$$

$$\tau_{xy}^{\text{II}}(r, \theta) = \frac{K_{\text{II}}}{\sqrt{2\pi r}} \cos \frac{\theta}{2} \left(1 - \sin \frac{\theta}{2} \sin \frac{3\theta}{2} \right) \quad (5.25)$$

Mode III

Here the stress field components are given as follows [Gdo04, p. 27]:

$$\tau_{xz}^{\text{III}}(r, \theta) = -\frac{K_{\text{III}}}{\sqrt{2\pi r}} \sin \frac{\theta}{2} \quad (5.26)$$

$$\tau_{yz}^{\text{III}}(r, \theta) = \frac{K_{\text{III}}}{\sqrt{2\pi r}} \cos \frac{\theta}{2} \quad (5.27)$$

5.1.3 Estimating Size of Plastic Zone

Based on the above equations, stress goes to infinity on approaching the crack tip. This is not physically reasonable, as plastic flow takes place above the yield point σ_Y , placing an upper limit on the stress. Stress can thus only continue to increase until the yield point is reached.

The geometry and size of the resulting plastic zone can be approximated under the assumption of von Mises yield criteria [Gdo04]. However, a distinction must be drawn here as to whether the object is in a planar stress state (surface of object) or a planar strain state (in the interior of thick objects).

$$r(\theta) = \frac{1}{4\pi} \left(\frac{K_I}{\sigma_Y} \right)^2 \cdot \begin{cases} \left(\frac{3}{2} \sin^2 \theta + 1 + \cos \theta \right) & \text{Planar stress state} \\ \left(\frac{3}{2} \sin^2 \theta + (1 - 2\nu)^2 (1 + \cos \theta) \right) & \text{Planar strain state} \end{cases} \quad (5.28)$$

Fig. 5.9 shows the form of the plastic zone resulting from these estimates for the two different stress states. The shape of this form of the plastic zone in a body containing a crack is shown schematically in Fig. 5.10. The planar stress state dominates at the surface and the planar strain state in the interior of the body.

Figure 5.9: Estimated form of the plastic zone about a crack tip (from [Gdo04, p. 59]) from Eq. (5.28)

Figure 5.10: Schematic showing the form of the plastic zone in a body with a crack with continuous transition from the planar stress state (surfaces) to the planar strain state (interior of body).

Irwin [Irw60] arrived at another estimate of the size of the plastic zone under the assumption of *small-scale yielding*. Without accounting for the exact form of the plastic zone, and for an elastic/perfect plastic material, he defined the size of the

plastic zone r_p as the distance from the crack tip at which stress reaches the yield point σ_Y ,

$$\sigma_x^I(r, \theta = 0) \stackrel{(5.16)}{=} \frac{K_I}{\sqrt{2\pi r}} \stackrel{!}{=} \sigma_Y. \quad (5.29)$$

This results in

$$r_p^* = \frac{K_I^2}{2\pi\sigma_Y^2}. \quad (5.30)$$

Fig. 5.11 shows a schematic of the elastic stresses close to the crack tip. As plastic flow takes place above a certain stress, this places an upper limit on stress and results in stress redistribution. The filled area (i.e. the elastic energy) on the left in Fig. 5.11 must be distributed in the adjacent areas. This area is calculated as

$$\int_0^{r_1} \frac{K_I}{\sqrt{2\pi x}} dx = 2\sigma_Y r_1. \quad (5.31)$$

In order to compensate this, the plastic zone must be increased until the newly area resulting below the stress curve has the same size (Fig. 5.11, right). This makes the plastic zone twice as large as in (5.30):

$$r_p = 2r_p^* = \frac{K_I^2}{\pi\sigma_Y^2}. \quad (5.32)$$

Figure 5.11: Schematic of elastic stresses close to the crack tip based on [Ric67]. Left: As plastic flow takes place above a certain stress, this places an upper limit on stress. Right: With stress redistribution, σ_{pl} is above σ_{el} for $x > r_p$, an estimate of the size of the plastically deformed zone.

The above estimate is based on the planar stress state. An additional prefactor of 1/3 results for the planar strain state [Irw68]. Since plastic deformation would cause significant heating at the crack tip, its magnitude is important for acoustic thermography.

5.2 Residual Stresses in Crack, Crack Closure

Residual stresses are those stresses prevailing within a part even if no forces are acting from the outside [Pil05]. According to Elber [Elb71], a crack with residual

stresses can no longer be regarded as a slot of vanishing width (cf. Section 5.1.2). If this concept were correct, the crack faces would be free from stress and completely separate for any arbitrarily small nonzero tensile stress. This is not generally the case for actual cracks with residual stresses, as can also be verified experimentally [SKR95]. Instead, a threshold stress σ_m is required to overcome the compressive residual stresses and open the crack.

Fig. 5.12 illustrates the processes through which residual stresses can be generated and remain in the material on crack growth.

- An unloaded body with a crack (wedge-shaped opening) is shown here. The area which will be plastically deformed in the subsequent experiment (radius $r_a = r_p$), is shown with a dashed line.
- At the time of maximum stress (and strain) the plastic zone has a diameter of $r_b > r_a$.
- If the plastically deformed material were to be cut out, a cylindrical hole with $r_c = r_b$ would remain.
- Since this remaining material was only elastically deformed, it returns reversibly to the initial state after removal of the applied stress ($r_d = r_a$).
- The material cut out in step c. only fits in the hole if it is pressed together by compression forces. These must in turn be compensated by tensile forces in the further surroundings (see schematic plot).

Figure 5.12: Residual stress at crack tip (from [Bro88, p. 139]).

Other mechanisms in addition to the crack closure induced by plasticity can also have an effect [Lia88]: oxides, roughness, viscous liquids as well as phase transformations (cf. Fig. 5.13).

It is apparent that the remaining residual stresses depend especially on crack geometry, (temperature-dependent) material parameters and the stresses occurring during crack growth. For constant external stresses, the residual stresses in a crack

Figure 5.13: Mechanisms which can cause crack closure (from [Lia88]).

in a turbine blade would thus depend on whether it developed at high temperatures during operation or at room temperature on a vibration test stand (cf. also [Kum92], [SKR95]).

Based on the description in Section 5.1.2, a crack would have to continue to grow on even the slightest loading. The concept of crack closure qualitatively explains that a certain threshold stress is actually necessary for this. A further effect is the phenomenon of crack tip blunting [Bro88], which is initiated in certain crack growth processes.

Both effects are of great importance for acoustic thermography. Although no exact values can be given for residual stresses or crack tip blunting in a specific crack without elaborate measurements, it is reasonable that crack growth need not necessarily take place at the vibration amplitudes generated by acoustic thermography. The size of the plastic zone is also reduced by these mechanisms.

5.3 Fatigue Damage

Lankford provides two definitions for fatigue damage [LD83, p. 491],

- Fatigue (damage) is a chemical and physical process in which the application of cyclic strains and stresses induce an irreversible degradation of a specific [material] property.
- Fatigue damage is the physical separation of the material (cracks, cavities etc.)

In the narrower sense, fatigue damage results in a “reduction in the service life [of a part]” (Pangborn in [LD83], p. 488)). The parameters for monitoring fatigue are changes in surface and hidden microplasticity, residual stresses and dislocation density. Although these parameters can be measured quantitatively, they are functions of the material and stresses, with the result that relative changes have to be evaluated during the fatigue process.

In titanium, fatigue results in increased energy dissipation of ultrasonic waves, causing fatigued parts to heat more strongly during the application of sound power (thermoacoustic fatigue characterization) [MRKS02].

5.4 Crack Growth

For a known local stress intensity factor K , Paris' law [PE63] describes an empirical relationship between this and incremental crack growth da/dN ,

$$\frac{da}{dN} = C(\Delta K)^m, \quad (5.33)$$

where C und m are experimentally determined constants and (cf. Eq. (5.19))

$$\Delta K = K_{\max} - K_{\min} = C\Delta\sigma\sqrt{\pi a}. \quad (5.34)$$

Several values for the coefficients are given in Table 5.1. The value of m is roughly

	C	m
Aluminium 7075-T6	$1.1 \cdot 10^{-11}$	3.9
Titanium (pure)	$6.8 \cdot 10^{-12}$	4.4
Steel 18/8	$3.2 \cdot 10^{-12}$	3.1

Table 5.1: Values for coefficients from Eq. (5.34) [Hel84]

3 for steel, 3–4 for aluminum alloys [Par81, p. 126] and 4.4 for pure titanium [MDBR03].

Substituting (5.34) in (5.33) enables estimation of the number of cycles N required for a crack to grow from length a_1 to length a_2 [Par81],

$$\Delta N = \int_{a_1}^{a_2} \frac{da}{C(\Delta K)^m} = \frac{-1}{C(\Delta\sigma\sqrt{\pi})^m} \frac{a_1^d - a_2^d}{d} \quad \text{mit } d = 1 - m/2. \quad (5.35)$$

The length a of a crack can be approximately categorized according to the scale in Table 5.2, where a_0 designates the lattice constant of the crystal lattice and a_σ the length at which the crack loses its mechanical stability: The growth of cracks

Atomic-scale cracks	$a \approx a_0$
Nanocracks/submicroscopic cracks	$a_0 < a < 1 \mu\text{m}$
Microcracks	$1 \mu\text{m} < a < 1 \text{mm}$
Microcracks	$1 \text{mm} < a < a_\sigma$
Major cracks/unstable cracks	$a > a_\sigma$

Table 5.2: Categorization of cracks by length [Vla76, p. 228]

depends heavily on the base material in which the crack is embedded, resulting in a distinction between brittle, quasi-brittle and ductile crack propagation [Vla76]. This also results in different crack morphologies and especially in different roughnesses of the crack faces. It is especially difficult to determine the stress intensity factor for acoustic thermography, but estimates are possible in individual cases for favorable geometry and with the use of vibrometer measurements.

5.5 Crack Morphology

5.5.1 Linearity

The main difficulty for investigations on actual cracks is their characterization. Crack length is a factor in each of the above equations, but cracks are not ideal straight lines. Fig. 5.14 shows just one example of how the use of different lenses on the infrared camera results in a significantly more exact image of a previously apparently linear crack. In the detailed image, the crack proves to be jagged, thus also resulting in differing degrees of heating at different sections along the crack.

Figure 5.14: Acoustic thermography on a crack in a turbine blade using various IR lenses. With the 25 mm lens, the 4 mm long crack can be seen as a linear indication. Only at higher magnification can it be seen that it actually has several bends (cf. schematic on right). The inclined lines indicate the top edge of the blade in each image.

5.5.2 Roughness

The roughness of the crack faces depends on factors including the material and the crack development history (especially temperature and stress intensity factor). Theoretical considerations of contact between rough surfaces and roughness in general can be read in sources such as [GW66], [SBA03], [WC99], [VNH05], [MHH92] or [HS03].

In acoustic thermography, the maximum deflection of the crack faces is a few μm . According to (2.2), a measured particle velocity of $v = 500 \text{ mm/s}$ at $f = 20 \text{ kHz}$ thus corresponds to a deflection of $u = v/(2\pi f) = 4 \mu\text{m}$. As a result, the individual asperities (crack tips) may not slide past each other at all, but rather may only be pressed together (Fig. 5.15). The investigated material has a crucial effect on this. The validity of this model will be better for brittle materials such as aluminum as opposed to more ductile materials such as steel, where the crack faces no longer fit together exactly due to local flow. This aspect will play a determining roll in Section 7, especially for friction.

Figure 5.15: Schematic representation of a crack in brittle material.

5.6 Estimating Non-Destructiveness

Unlike methods such as dye penetrant examination, acoustic thermography is not nondestructive *a priori*, as crack initiation and growth take place above certain stresses, i.e. vibration amplitudes. The local stresses during ultrasonic excitation must therefore be at least estimated.

According to the definition on page 125, non-destructiveness in the broader sense also includes an acceptable compromise of behavior in use. The limits of applicability of a test are defined by the following conditions [Mil01]:

- Infrared intensity of the defect in question is above the detection threshold
- Predicted damage is within an acceptable range (such as where the material is further fatigued by a tolerable amount as a result of the test).

The following cases should be differentiated below for estimating the non-destructiveness of the procedure:

- **Damage to previously intact parts.** Cyclical material loading gives rise to local material fatigue (especially microplastic flow [GS01]), which finally results in defect initiation (such as the formation of cracks or delamination).
- **Growth of already existing defects**, i.e. crack growth, increased delamination, flaking of already delaminated coatings
- **Change in morphology** of already existing defects (such as wear on crack flanks without growth in crack length)

5.6.1 Damage to Previously Intact Specimens

Damage to previously intact parts is unacceptable and must be prevented. The determination of operation deflection shapes enables at least an estimate of the local strains and stresses, from which predictions of the probability of damage can be derived.

Determination of stresses from finite element simulations

In principle, the entire measurement procedure can be simulated using suitable programs for finite element analysis. Such a procedure is elaborate because of the complexity of the specimens as well as (at least for the use of welding units with sonotrodes) the additional effects of the excitation (loose coupling, hammering).

However, this enables the determination of vibration data for areas which in principle are inaccessible for measurement, such as internal structures.

It often occurs that specific areas of the specimens vibrate especially heavily even though their crack examination is not at all necessary. For example, such a zone in the turbine blades would be the platform projections (Fig. 2.19, p. 29, right), which have to withstand high vibration amplitudes as a bar supported on one end, although no crack examination is to be performed here.

However, in some circumstances excessive loading of these parts can be prevented by careful selection of the excitation frequency. Fig. 5.16 shows this procedure as an example on a fictitious H-shaped structural steel part for which the heavy vertical pipes on the outside are excited ultrasonically from below. In this case, only these external pipes are to be examined for cracks, while the thin crossbar shall not be loaded too heavily. For the resonant frequency at 14.8 kHz, the simulation yields that the crossbeam experiences especially high stresses (top row, right-hand image) and the pipes hardly vibrate at all. This frequency must therefore be avoided. In contrast, the mode at 18.9 kHz is optimal here, as the pipes vibrate especially heavily while the crossbeam experiences only slight stresses (bottom row, right-hand image).

Figure 5.16: Selection of the optimum excitation frequency for a fictitious structural steel part to protect the crossbeam. Images from left to right: undeformed part, deflection and stress (Von Mises equivalent) at the indicated frequency. Top row: mode at 14.8 kHz, which results nearly exclusively in loading of the crossbeam; bottom row: mode at 18.9 kHz with optimum distribution of vibration in the various areas

Additional simplified methods are presented below.

Determination of local stresses from operation deflection shapes

Determination of the local stress tensor requires knowledge of the 3D vibration data over a 2D area. This can in principle be measured for small planar surfaces, from which clear conclusions can be derived regarding non-destructiveness. However, this procedure is hardly possible for many parts with complex geometries.

Simplified estimation for thin plates

However, at least local simplifications can also be made under certain conditions for parts with highly curved geometry. For example, turbine blades can thus be approximated as thin plates in specific regions, offering the significant advantage of simple analytical access (Section 3). This applies especially at the trailing edges, which preferentially undergo bending vibrations due to their small thickness (cf. Fig. 2.19, p. 29). As the stresses are also highest here, an estimate at this point is especially beneficial.

It was shown in Section 3.4.1 that there are no transverse shear waves in thin plates. The components ε_{zx} and ε_{zy} in the strain matrix are thus equal to zero and do not contribute to stress in the material.

The material stresses are then induced only by the in-plane components ε_{xx} and ε_{yy} as well as shear $\varepsilon_{xy} \equiv \varepsilon_{yx}$, which can be calculated from Equations (3.46) and (3.49). Other than the material constants E , G , ρ and ν , the only parameters entering into the calculation are the excitation frequency f and the out-of-plane deflection u_z . It is sufficient for a worst-case estimate to use the highest value u_z^{\max} .

The stresses can then be calculated from $\sigma_{xx,yy} = \varepsilon_{xx,yy}E$ and $\sigma_{xy} = \varepsilon_{xy}G$.

Effect of stress concentrators

According to Section 5.1, discontinuities in the material give rise to local stress amplification. For more complex geometries, at least estimates must be made for the stress concentration factors, with which the stresses determined as described above must then be multiplied (Equation (5.6), p. 60).

5.6.2 Additional Damage to already Damaged Parts (crack growth)

Because of the stress concentration at the crack tip, cracks are especially at risk of further growing during ultrasonic excitation. However, crack growth may be tolerated in cases such as where the crack length was already above the critical size at the start of the examination, in which case further growth is irrelevant. But slight growth is unproblematic under some circumstances even for repairable cracks, as the entire crack is reclosed in the repair procedure.

Similar considerations hold for delamination. Layers which have already partially detached can no longer be repaired, with the result that any flaking of the coating does not represent any impairment, as the part must be recoated in any case.

A critical evaluation of the possible damage is recommended for each new examination.

Based on Paris' law (Equation (5.33) on page 69), crack growth can be at least estimated when the parameters are known. The critical question here is whether

determination of the parameters is at all possible, as all geometric and material data must be accounted for. Crack tip blunting and residual compressive stresses (cf. Section 5.2) can slow crack growth.

In addition to the results from this study, there are also various authors who report on possible damage in acoustic thermography. Chen et. al. [CKR06] produced one of the best substantiated investigations of crack growth in rectangular plates ($L \times B \times D = 140 \times 38 \times 3,1$ mm) of 2024-T3 aluminum, steel and titanium. Cracks of length 1.9–12.7 mm were generated with a tensile testing machine starting from a slot in the material. Ultrasonic examination was subsequently performed using a Branson 910M (1 kW, 20 kHz) with a GK5 manual welding gun which was pressed against the plates with constant force. The following results were obtained:

- Crack growth is a function of prior history, in this case the stress intensity factors used for initial crack generation (Section 5.1.2). Higher factors result in reduced crack growth, which could possibly be attributed to the increased blunting of the crack tip.
- Incremental changes in crack length between two tests with 5,000 cycles (250 ms at 20 kHz) were on average 40 μm (with pronounced scatter), corresponding to a crack growth rate of 8 nm per cycle.
- In addition to varying crack growth depending on the specimen material, varying degrees of changes in the crack faces can also be observed (see Fig. 5.17).

At given ultrasonic amplitudes, the probability of destruction depends heavily on the material parameters and the geometry of the examined object. Ceramic parts are at higher risk due to their brittleness [Mil01]. In this study, it was observed that crack growth occurred in only two intentional cases at excessive vibration amplitudes, but that already weakened points sometimes flaked off, such as projecting sawing burrs or partially detached layers.

For a deliberate crack growth experiment, a 1 mm thick aluminum sheet was provided with a sawn slot and a small crack generated by subsequent cyclic bending. This crack was then lengthened in the experiment (Fig. 5.18). The change in length was 4.8 mm in 200 ms, corresponding to a crack growth rate of 24 mm/s or roughly 1 μm per cycle and thus more than 2 orders of magnitude higher than in the experiment by Chen.

5.6.3 Changes in Crack Morphology

As can already be seen in Fig. 5.17, the surface condition of the crack faces can change due to acoustic thermography. The wear on the contact surfaces is also visible in Fig. 7.22 (page 109).

As this type of damage is only of slight practical significance, it is only pointed out here that it can result in differences in heating on repeated testing by acoustic thermography. A change in the dominant mechanism (cf. Section 7) is also conceivable based on this.

Figure 5.17: Crack growth and changes in crack face morphology due to ultrasonic excitation [CKR06]. From top to bottom: a. Aluminum (crack lengths $l_1 = 8.15$ mm and $l_2 = 9.28$ mm, $(l_2 - l_1)/l_1 \approx 14\%$), b. Aluminum (crack lengths $l_1 = 5.19$ mm and $l_2 = 7.66$ mm, $(l_2 - l_1)/l_1 \approx 48\%$), c. Steel ($l_1 = 6.29$ mm and $l_2 = 9.88$ mm, $(l_2 - l_1)/l_1 \approx 57\%$) and d. Titanium ($l_1 = 10.21$ mm and $l_2 = 10.65$ mm, $(l_2 - l_1)/l_1 \approx 4\%$).

Figure 5.18: Crack growth in an aluminum sheet. The initial crack was introduced by cyclic bending in the sheet weakened by a sawn slot. A second crack can be seen on the left side of the slot which grew considerably less. The tip of the sonotrode is at the upper right edge; the heating at the bottom edge of the image was caused by the clamp. The tip of the growing crack front is heated the most (cf. Section 7.2.4, p. 109).

Chapter 6

Further Technical Aspects of Acoustic Thermography

6.1 Detection Limits

6.1.1 Defect Size

Detection sensitivity is a fundamental characteristic of all NDT methods. For example, for magnetic particle inspection (MPI), a test block with defined cracks (such as the “MTU test block”, cf. Fig. 6.6, p. 83) is examined and the detection threshold evaluated as a function of the examination parameters. These limits then also apply for the detection of cracks in other parts.

Although these test blocks can also be used for acoustic thermography, the resulting information is not necessarily transferable to actual examination specimens. Detection sensitivity is not a defined value in this method, but rather is a function of the object and crack geometry, the individual resonant frequency and other factors. It is nevertheless necessary to at least have an indication of detection sensitivity.

Fig. 6.1 shows the detection of cracks from an indenter impression in a steel specimen. These cracks were generated by cycling the indented specimen in a tensile testing machine while monitoring crack growth in situ with a microscope [Meg05], until a crack had reached a length of at least 200 μm after 150,000 cycles (cf. Fig. 6.2). Thermographic detection of the cracks was performed with resonant excitation of the bar bonded to the coupling plate for one second at a frequency of 28,533 Hz. The defect area was coated using a black paint stick for increased emissivity.

Fig. 6.1a shows the image immediately before ultrasonic excitation (reference image). The images below this correspond to time $t = 1$ s, where 97% and 100% of the reference image have been subtracted, respectively.

A quantitative comparison of the crack lengths (Fig. 6.3) is difficult, as the resolution of the infrared images is very low (110 pixels horizontally; the left crack consists of only 5 pixels). However, the entire length of the left crack appears to have been detected, while only a portion of the right crack was heated. This also demonstrates the difficulty of specifying a specific crack length for detection sensitivity; however, it appears to be reasonable to assume a detection threshold of better than 100 μm . The detection of significantly smaller cracks is probably possible under optimum conditions. In [FTH+01], Favro et. al. demonstrated the detection of 54 μm and 20 μm long cracks in titanium test blocks.

Figure 6.1: Detection of cracks initiated from an indenter impression using acoustic thermography (cf. Fig. 6.2). Images a–c are from the infrared sequence: a. Frame($t = 0$ s) (before excitation), b. Frame($t = 1$ s) $- 0.97 \cdot$ Frame($t = 0$ s), c. Frame($t = 1$ s) $-$ Frame($t = 0$ s).

Figure 6.2: Steel specimen with indenter impression and cracks. The images show microphotographs taken in situ during crack growth in a tensile testing machine [Meg05]. The numbers indicate the number of cycles. The crack tips are each indicated with small white circles. The right-hand crack branches.

Figure 6.3: Comparison of crack lengths, optical (bottom) and thermography (top)

It is not necessary for wavelength λ of the ultrasonic wave to be on the order of magnitude of defect size a . As only differential distortion at the defect is determining, defects can also be detected for $\lambda \gg a$.

An exceptional aspect of thermography is that the heat propagates out from a defect, meaning that a defect need not be resolved in order to be detectable. If the defect generates sufficient heat, the hot spot finally becomes so large that it is detectable with the camera. This is a critical advantage for the currently still relatively low camera resolutions available (status in 2007: 640×480).

Resolution depends on the infrared lens and camera used. Sensor size of the Thermosensorik CMT256 is 256×256 pixels. Using the 2.5x Micro MWIR f/2.0 macro lens, a field of view of roughly $5 \times 5 \text{ mm}^2$ is obtained. This corresponds to a lateral resolution of roughly $20 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$. Smaller defects thus cannot in principle be resolved, but they can be detected. The physical resolution limit is on the order of magnitude of the wavelength of the IR radiation used, i.e. roughly $10 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$.

6.1.2 Distance of Defect from Coupling Point

In acoustic thermography, the defect can be a considerable distance from the ultrasonic coupling point and still be visible as long as the ultrasonic wave is not too heavily damped. This is especially the case for metals. Fig. 6.4 shows a 1.20 m long pipe from a gas turbine which was excited at the bottom end. It is clear here from the damping of the ceramic coating on the inside and the resulting heating that the entire part has been excited by the ultrasonic wave. It can be anticipated that one or a few coupling points are sufficient even for still larger parts, although the geometry of the specimen has a determining effect along with the damping.

In CFRP parts, the maximum distance from the coupling point to the defect is limited to roughly 50 cm due to the higher damping (for excitation with a 1 kW ultrasonic welding gun, [Sto05]). This distance is correspondingly lower for more heavily damping materials.

6.2 False Indications

Most NDT methods have issues with more or less heavily pronounced false indications; for example, surface roughness due to residual dye can result in incorrect interpretations in dye penetrant examination.

6.2.1 False Indications due to Burrs and Residues

In acoustic thermography, damping of the ultrasonic wave (see Section 7.2.2) is the main cause of false indications. This can manifest itself negatively through remaining dirt particles, especially viscous materials such as adhesive residues, causing detectable heating. However, damping in the substrate or an existing coating can also cause apparent indications even if the surface has been cleaned. On resonant excitation, the standing waves render a characteristic pattern visible on the object surface (see also [DZB02], for example). The only corrective measure here is a time variation of the frequency, so that the different modal patterns cancel each other out.

Several examples are listed in Section 7.2.2 in which damping was deliberately used to study the heating mechanism. It will be desirable to suppress these indications if possible for real measurements. The effect is relatively strongly pronounced in plastics or composites due to the high damping, while it is usually negligible in metals.

However, this mechanism can result in heating of the ceramic thermal barrier coating where present on turbine components. Fig. 6.4 shows this case for the example of a pipe coated on the inside. The standing shafts result in nonhomogeneous heating of the inside wall of the pipe. This heating is visible on the outside after several seconds. Although this undesirable effect cannot be eliminated by modulating the excitation frequency, it can at least be rendered homogeneous by this measure.

Figure 6.4: Gas inlet pipe in a gas turbine with a ceramic coating on the inside which is heated nonhomogeneously due to standing ultrasonic waves (cf. Section 7.2.2). The wave pattern is clearly visible for low frequency bandwidths ($\Delta f \lesssim 50$ Hz). However, heating becomes more homogeneous with increasing bandwidth. The darker areas (no heating) correlate spatially with uncoated surfaces, and the more pronounced heating of the vertical center line is caused by increased coating thickness in this area.

6.2.2 Interference Effects due to Wave Propagation

The ultrasonic waves can propagate for several decimeters in weakly damped media. If the wave impinges on a material interface, a fraction R of the wave is reflected as a function of acoustic impedances Z_1 and Z_2 of the materials,

$$R = \left(\frac{Z_2 - Z_1}{Z_2 + Z_1} \right)^2. \quad (6.1)$$

Especially for air as an interface medium, reflection is nearly 100

This results in interference between the reflected wave and the incident wave. If the ultrasonic frequency is a resonant frequency of the object, this results in standing ultrasonic waves. For simple geometric objects in air, the resulting sound field can be found by the mirror source method. For a rectangular plate with side lengths a and b and a primary source

$$u(x, y) = u_0 e^{-i\omega x/\lambda} e^{-dx} \quad (6.2)$$

with wavelength λ , rotational frequency ω and material damping d , the resulting wave pattern is

$$u_{\text{tot}}(x, y) = \sum_{i=-\infty}^{+\infty} \sum_{j=-\infty}^{+\infty} u(x - 2ai, y - 2bj). \quad (6.3)$$

The greater the damping, the fewer sources need be taken into account. The image on the left in Fig. 6.5 shows an interference pattern in a plate calculated in accordance with Equation (6.3) for excitation normal to the drawing plane. The exciter is located horizontally in the center of the plate and vertically roughly 12% of the length from the bottom. For the experiment, a piezoelectric exciter was bonded to a PVC plate, which was then resonantly excited at 31 kHz. The resulting infrared image, which agrees very well with the simulation, is shown on the right in Fig. 6.5 (damping was adjusted empirically for the left image, cf. also Section 7.2.2).

Figure 6.5: Calculated interference pattern for a plate (left) and measured experimental heating (right).

6.3 Data Processing

A thermographic sequence consists of a three-dimensional intensity data block $I(x, y, n)$, where n indicates the image number and x and y the lateral coordinates, and the corresponding time $t(n)$ is related to the camera frame rate f_c by $t(n) = n/f_c$. The data

for the currently common cameras are available in 16-bit format, i.e. $0 \leq I \leq 65535$, although often only 12–14 bits are effectively used.

The simplest analysis of the data corresponds to the display of a frame $I(x, y, n)$ as an 8-bit grayscale or color image with a corresponding 256-color palette (Section B.3.1). It can sometimes also be useful to display the “space/time rotated” data block $I(x, n, y)$ or $I(n, y, x)$, in which the time history of the heating becomes visible.

6.3.1 Averaging

A simple method for improving the signal-to-noise ratio by a factor of \sqrt{N} lies in the averaging of N individual images:

$$I_{\text{avg}}(x, y) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=z_1}^{z_1+N} I(x, y, i). \quad (6.4)$$

6.3.2 Lock-In Analysis

For amplitude-modulated excitation

$$x(t) = \sin(2\pi f't) \sin(2\pi ft) \quad (6.5)$$

at excitation frequency f and modulation frequency f_0 , where typically $f_0 \ll f$, e.g. $f = 20$ kHz and $f_0 \sim 1$ – 10 Hz, the infrared signal can be analyzed with a sine/cosine correlation as in Section 2.3.3. Values for amplitude and phase are obtained for each pixel. The phase provides information on the time offset (phase shift) of the response relative to the excitation signal and is thus a measure of the distance from the primary heat source (laterally or vertically). The selectivity of the measurement can also be increased to a certain depth by careful selection of the excitation frequency.

Fig. 6.6 shows the results of an investigation with acoustic thermography and lock-in modulation. The amplitude was varied according to

$$A(t) = A_0 \sin(2\pi ft), \quad (6.6)$$

where f was varied between 1.25 Hz and 20 Hz. The higher the selected lock-in frequency, the more heat conduction is suppressed in the evaluation, thus increasing the sharpness of the crack image.

6.3.3 Pulse Phase Analysis

Pulse phase analysis (PPA) ([Mal01], [DZB02]) is the special case of correlation of a nonharmonic signal with sine/cosine functions of frequency f_{PP} . It is expedient for acoustic thermography to select the recording time T twice as long as the excitation time τ and then to adjust frequency f_{PP} such that time T corresponds to exactly one cycle, i.e. $f = 1/T$. This enables the calculation of an amplitude $A(x, y)$ and phase $P(x, y)$ ($0 \leq P(x, y) < 2\pi$) for each pixel even with a single pulse.

Fig. 6.7 contrasts an image from the original series and the calculated amplitude image from PPA. Taking the ratio of the average of the amplitudes in region 1 to the standard deviation of the amplitudes in region 2 from Fig. 6.7c as the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), PPA yields an improvement by roughly a factor of 5, from 3.5 to 17.9.

Figure 6.6: Investigation of an MTU03 magnetic powder examination test block by acoustic thermography. The result of the magnetic powder examination is shown on the left for comparison. The acoustic thermography images were all obtained by resonant excitation and the lock-in method at different modulation frequencies.

In addition to the improved SNR in the amplitude image, PPA also yields the additional information of the phase, i.e. the time behavior of heat generation at each point. Fig. 6.8 shows both the amplitude and phase images.

6.3.4 Fitting with Reference Functions

Fitting with polynomials

Improved correlation results if polynomials instead of sinusoidal functions are fitted to the measured data, but only if a higher-order polynomial is used. The resulting advantage is the possibility of further processing the coefficients (such as calculating the derivatives), and the disadvantage is the number of coefficients, which renders the display of an individual results image more difficult.

Fitting with results from analytical models

The physically most reasonable method for data processing is to fit the analytical models (Section B.2, p. 119) to the measured data. Although this requires advance knowledge such as the wall thickness of the investigated specimen, quantitative data can then also be extracted.

A further difficulty arises from the fact that correct calculation would require knowledge of both the geometry of the part (especially wall thicknesses) as well as that of the crack (point, line or over an area). A nonlinear fit of the models, although possible for determining the coefficients, is computationally very intensive, especially as in real cases the individual solutions often must be superimposed (such as a sum over several point sources close to each other).

Figure 6.7: Improvement in signal-to-noise ratio by pulse phase analysis and original time history for a crack (region 1) and an area without defects (region 2).

Figure 6.8: Amplitude (a) and phase image (b) calculated by pulse phase analysis

6.4 Comparison with Other Methods

6.4.1 Overview

Table 6.4.1 shows an overview of common NDT methods and the defect types which they can detect (see C starting from page 125 for a brief introduction to several of these methods).

Although X-ray computer tomography offers the best range of detectable defect

types, the long measuring time often renders it unsuitable, such as for process monitoring. In addition, magnification techniques must be used for detecting cracks in the μm range, which significantly restricts the object size which can be examined. In particular, a detectable material gap is necessary here, whereas acoustic thermography can also detect these as well as cracks with their faces in contact (kissing bonds).

Nonthermographic methods	Cracks	Delam.	Coating thickness	Wall thickness	Cooling air bores
Dye penetrant examination	● ^a	–	–	–	–
X-ray CT	●	●	●	●	●
Thermographic methods	Cracks	Delam.	Coating thickness	Wall thickness	Cooling air bores
Flash thermography	– ^b	●	●	●	–
Acoustic thermography	●	●	–	– ^c	–
Induction thermography	●	●	●	●	–
Hot air thermography	–	–	–	●	●

Table 6.1: Overview of common NDT methods and defect types which they can detect; delamination is abbreviated as delam. here.

^aOnly if open at the surface

^bOnly if at an angle

^cIf a material which heats on vibration is placed against the back wall

6.4.2 Comparison with Dye Penetrant Examination

Dye penetrant examination is a classic method for detecting surface cracks (see Section C.1, p. 125). The latest investigations in the comparison of probability of detection (POD) studies¹ of acoustic thermography and fluorescent dye penetrant (FDP) examination yielded the following [DANS07]:

1. For crack lengths greater than roughly 0.75 mm, the detection probability with acoustic thermography was better than with FDP, while FDP was better for smaller cracks, although at the cost of the larger number of surface features erroneously detected as defects (false calls), as FDP is sensitive to surface variations such as scratches or porosity.
2. No false indications were obtained using acoustic thermography.
3. Detection probability for FDP was essentially independent of crack length, while smaller cracks were less detectable with acoustic thermography than large ones (limit length roughly 0.75 mm). However, an improvement could be achieved here with the use of a different lens with a smaller field of view.
4. The experiments were performed by examiners with different levels of experience. It proved that detection probability for FDP depended significantly

¹A dependency in the form of $\text{POD}(a) = \Phi(c + d \ln(a))$ is often fitted for a given crack length a , where $\Phi(x)$ is the cumulative normal distribution and c and d are the fitting parameters [DANS07].

on the respective examiner, while acoustic thermography varied less from one examiner to the next.

In addition and in contrast to the results in [CKR06], no crack growth was observed for any of the 60 specimens in these experiments despite the very similar setup. Of course the higher sensitivity in point 3 is achieved with a reduction in the testable area. Future infrared cameras with higher resolution should yield better results here (cf. Section 6.1.1). Point 4 confirms the objectivity of the results also observed by the author. This simplifies any possible subsequent automatic defect detection.

6.4.3 Comparison with Flash Thermography

Flash thermography is a long-established method for detecting defects close to the surface (C.2.1, p. 127). Fig. 6.9 shows a comparison between flash and acoustic thermography on various ceramic-coated turbine blades. Flaking of coatings (Fig. 6.9a) is already detected by flash thermography due only to the differences in emissivity, but could also be detected due to the time behavior of thermal diffusion. However, as there are no movable interfaces in this case, detection by acoustic thermography is not possible, although there are cases in which the ceramic coating is heated by damping. Uncoated areas then appear cooler (cf. Fig. 6.4, p. 80).

Figure 6.9: Comparison of indications from flash and acoustic thermography for various defects.

Delamination can be detected by both methods (Fig. 6.9b/e), although acoustic thermography primarily heats only the edges of larger areas of detachment. The situation is analogous for areas of coating flaking surrounded by delamination (Fig. 6.9d).

In contrast, the behavior of the two methods is completely different for cracks. While bounding surfaces which move against each other generate heat in acoustic thermography, no detection is possible with flash thermography at least for vertical cracks (Fig. 6.9c), as no disturbance is induced by the crack in the theoretically ideal case of one-dimensional heat flow to the interior. However, verification is possible for the converse example of a crack at an angle (cf. Fig. 6.10), as in this case the penetrating thermal front is impeded by the interface.

Figure 6.10: Schematic showing penetration of thermal front past a crack in flash thermography. A crack oriented perpendicular to the surface does not interfere with the thermal wave (left), while a crack at an angle represents a barrier which becomes visible in thermal image (right).

Fig. 6.11 shows a comparison of flash (green in larger image). And acoustic thermography (red) on a turbine blade with a fatigue crack. It was known from prior investigations (cf. Fig. C.1, p. 127) only that the blade had a crack in the blade root. Acoustic thermography also does not enable any direct conclusions regarding the course of the crack with depth. The time history of the heat generation could theoretically be used with the analytical solutions for various geometries obtained in Section B.2 to estimate the spatial structure of the crack, but the strong surface signal masks heating from deeper material here.

In this case the comparison with flash thermography yields a more elegant understanding of the material below the surface. The horizontal portion of the crack is not visible in the flash thermography image, as the crack is apparently perpendicular to the surface here. However, the subsequent diagonal portion yields a flash thermography signal on the left side in the upper area (A), and on the right side in the lower area (B). This indicates that the crack turns inside the blade and has grown further at various angles. The “wall thicknesses” are less at (A) and (B). This effect can also be seen in the cooling air bores on the blade airfoil, where a green halo is visible to the left of each opening.

6.4.4 Comparison with Induction Thermography

Induction thermography is a new method for which there have been few publications to date. However, internal experiments [Vra07] demonstrate that acoustic thermography offers advantages for complex geometries, as the current paths are difficult to control in these cases. On the other hand, induction thermography is also non-contacting on the excitation side and its non-destructiveness is easily verified for the given specimen.

Figure 6.11: Comparison of flash and acoustic thermography on a turbine blade with fatigue crack.

Further advantages of acoustic thermography in turn are its additional applicability to nonconducting materials such as plastics as well as the dark field imaging characteristic, meaning that (with the aforementioned restrictions) only the defects are heated. In contrast, all areas of elevated current density, i.e. especially also edges, are heated in induction thermography.

Chapter 7

Mechanisms of Bulk and Defect Heating

Although the method of acoustic thermography has been known since the end of the '70s [HRS79], the heating mechanism has only been partially investigated to date (e.g. [RHS80], [Bov04], [HI06]). Even if the underlying physical mechanisms are partially the same, a distinction can be drawn between two scenarios. On the one hand, bulk heating can already be observed for sufficiently high ultrasonic power levels, while on the other hand defects such as cracks or delaminations are heated especially strongly. Acoustic thermography is also known as a *dark field method* for this reason [ZRDB03]. This can be clearly seen on the top left in Fig. 6.11 on p. 88, in which only the crack is prominent in front of a homogeneous unheated background. This was achieved by subtracting the background image, i.e. the image taken before ultrasonic excitation (difference mode).

In [RHS80], Reifsnider et. al. give the following basic mechanisms resulting in heat generation,

- Energy dissipation from standing waves,
- Plastic deformation and
- Friction (Modes II/III) and clapping (Mode I) between adjacent bounding surfaces (for cracks and delamination).

While the first two cases can also occur in the bulk or in coatings (cf. indications in Fig. 6.4), the third is limited to defects in the solid with discontinuities in the material grain structure, with the further prerequisite that the surfaces can come in contact, at least under ultrasonic excitation.

For the destructive case of a growing crack front, a significant quantity of energy is also converted to heat at the plastic zone around the crack tip. This can be clearly seen experimentally (Fig. 5.18, p. 75).

The measured correlations between heating and local deflection as well as the parameters of normal force and roughness are first presented below. Subsequent sections are then concerned with the individual mechanisms which should at least qualitatively explain the measurements.

7.1 Correlation between Thermal Signal and Vibration

7.1.1 Dependence of Heating on Vibration Amplitude

If a specimen is resonantly excited, a standing wave pattern results on the surface (cf. Section 2.3, p. 14). In contrast to a propagating wave,

$$\tilde{u}(x, t) = \cos(\omega t - kx) \quad (7.1)$$

the time dependence in a standing wave can be separated and the spatially dependent deflection described as (cf. Eq. (2.25), p. 14):

$$\vec{\tilde{u}}(\vec{x}, t) = \vec{u}(\vec{x}) \cdot \cos(\omega t) = (u_x(\vec{x}), u_y(\vec{x}), u_z(\vec{x})) \cos(\omega t). \quad (7.2)$$

Here and in the following, a tilde ($\vec{\tilde{u}}$) is used to designate the time-dependent parameter. However, usually only the magnitude of the maximum deflection or velocity is of interest, so that the values (\vec{u}) are used.

The deflection is a vector value, as it is a function of the 3D coordinates in and on the object. The surface components of the vibration can be measured with a laser vibrometer. The z -dependence $\vec{\tilde{u}}(z, t)$ cannot generally be determined, as it is directed into the interior object¹. Only the x and y components are therefore accounted for in the spatial vector \vec{x} in (7.2). The vector arrow over \tilde{u} or u stands for the 3 component directions (in-plane horizontal, in-plane vertical and out-of-plane).

The particle velocity can be calculated from Equation (7.2) by taking the partial derivative with respect to t ,

$$\vec{\tilde{v}}(\vec{x}, t) = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \vec{\tilde{u}}(\vec{x}, t) = -\vec{u}(\vec{x})\omega \sin(\omega t) =: -\vec{v}(\vec{x}) \sin(\omega t). \quad (7.3)$$

The acoustic energy is then proportional to $v^2 = |\vec{v}|^2$. Fig. 7.1 shows the typical measured quadratic relationship between the thermal signal I_{IR} of a crack and the particle velocity v measured close to the crack,

$$I_{\text{IR}} \propto |\vec{v}(\vec{x})|^2 = \left(\sqrt{v_x^2 + v_y^2 + v_z^2} \right)^2, \quad (7.4)$$

i.e. the proportionality of thermal and acoustic intensity. A differential measurement of crack edge movement was also performed on the blade in Fig. 7.1, which confirmed the quadratic relationship. This is not surprising, as absolute vibration should be essentially proportional to the differential for a given operation deflection shape: at constant frequency a proportionality to velocity v also corresponds to a proportionality to deflection u .

The dependency in accordance with (7.4) was confirmed in many investigations of various cracks in metals. A further example is shown in Fig. 7.2.

7.1.2 Dependence of Heating on Operation Deflection Shape

It was demonstrated in Section 2.3 how strongly operation deflection shapes differ at different frequencies, as is manifested in the highly different crack signals in Fig. 4.12 (p. 55).

¹Although measurements can be carefully combined for the object turned at different angles in order to at least yield the surface components $U_{x,y,z}(x, y, z, t)$ of the vibration, this is seldom done.

Figure 7.1: Measured $I_{\text{IR}}(v)$ dependency for a crack in a turbine blade. The inset shows an infrared image from the sequence; vibration was measured during the ultrasonic pulse with a vibrometer targeted on reflecting foil (arrow).

Figure 7.2: Measured $I_{\text{IR}}(v)$ dependency for a crack in a fatigue specimen (property of EADS). The inset shows an infrared image from the sequence.

Examination of a Plastic Cup

A polystyrene measuring cup was selected for further investigation of this phenomenon, for which the many radial cracks in the bottom can be made visible using acoustic thermography (Fig. 7.3). The wavelength of the vibration at the frequency of roughly 34 kHz shown is very much shorter than the crack length, and two areas can be distinguished in the infrared image (center); the cracks (thin light radial lines) as well as blurred wide concentric rings. It is apparent that the cracks are not visible over their entire length and that the rings appear at the same radial

positions where the cracks are also heated (zones A).

Figure 7.3: Examination of a polystyrene cup bonded to a piezoelectric exciter for correlation of heating with vibration.

To enable correlation of this result with the operation deflection shape, the out-of-plane nodal lines were rendered visible with fine sand (see Chladni patterns in Fig. 7.3 right). The vibration causes the sand to collect at the vibration nodal lines. Based on the statements in Section 3, apparently a standing radial bending wave is established in the thin bottom of the cup.

Comparing the vibration image with the infrared image, it can be seen that no heating is manifested at the nodal lines (zones B). In contrast, both the cracks (sharply bounded radial lines) as well as the bulk (more diffuse and uniform wide annular rings) are heated in the annular rings between them (zones A). According to Section 3.4.1, all strains vanish at the nodal lines of the u_z deflection for a bending wave. There is apparently then also no heating at these locations. Conversely, ε_{xx} and ε_{yy} strain reaches a maximum at the maxima of the u_z deflection. This in-plane strain thus heats both the bulk material as well as the cracks. The mechanisms which result in this heating are discussed further below, especially on p. 106.

Examination of a Metal Turbine Blade

Specimens such as the turbine blade from Fig. 2.21 (p. 31) were used to transfer these phenomena to metals, as pronounced crack movements are detectable here. However, exactly this movement is contingent upon extensive freedom from contact of the crack faces of this wide open crack, which do not come in contact over most of the length and thus generate no heat during ultrasonic excitation.

It was therefore expedient for further investigations to examine the simplest possible linear crack with better fitting faces. Fig. 7.4 shows an aircraft turbine blade with a crack in which the edges are in such good contact that the crack can only be rendered optically visible by dye penetrant examination. Fig. 7.5 shows the rep-

resentation of the vibration measurement already known from Section 2.3 which resolves the operation deflection shapes into their individual components. The resulting infrared images are shown next to these components. It is initially apparent that there is a pronounced out-of-plane movement at all three frequencies. This is unsurprising, as the thin blade airfoil preferentially undergoes bending vibrations.

Figure 7.4: Titanium alloy aircraft turbine blade (MTU Aerospace). The arrow indicates the crack rendered visible by dye penetrant examination. The two rectangular areas correspond to the sections in Fig. 7.5.

Figure 7.5: Correlation of operation deflection shapes measured on aircraft turbine blade from Fig. 7.4 and associated infrared images for three resonant frequencies. The numerical value of the deflection of the upper right point is included for comparison.

The y component of the vibration is also very small in all cases. The crack is not detectable in the z or y component in the vibration image (in contrast to Fig. 2.13, p. 24).

In contrast, the x component exhibits a pronounced discontinuity at the crack. At 19,583 Hz and 33,939 Hz, the crack exhibits a clear mode I movement (cf. Fig. 5.6, p. 63). This is superimposed only by movement in the z direction in the same phase, i.e. there is no additional mode III movement here. Nor does any mode II or mode III movement occur in this blade at other measured frequencies. It can easily be postulated that the crack surfaces fit together too well, so that no shearing movement is possible. Only the mode I direction is free to move. The two frequencies with pronounced mode I movement thus also exhibit the strongest heating; the in-phase z movement does not contribute to heating, although its amplitude is greater than that of the x component. A possible explanation for this behavior is given in the discussion of damping on p. 105.

The resonance at 22,905 Hz hardly heats the crack at all, which can be explained from the vibration image due to the lack of any differential movement at the crack. At 33,939 Hz, differential crack movement is limited to a smaller area, which is also manifested directly in the infrared image by an apparently shorter crack length.

Two thinner piezoelectric exciters were bonded to the front and back of the blade in a further experiment (Fig. 7.6) in order to force mode III movement at the crack. A sufficiently large vibration amplitude Δu_z could only be generated at the six resonant frequencies of the piezoelectric exciters. In order to separate the effects of frequency and deflection, the piezoelectric voltage at these six frequencies was first adjusted so as to yield a constant differential deflection Δu_z of 0.8 μm . Heating as a function of frequency is shown in the lower right of Fig. 7.6. A quadratic relationship can be postulated here.

In a second step, vibration deflection was varied at constant frequency. Here as well, the resulting relationship was approximately quadratic.

Overall, the result of the experiment was thus that $I_{\text{IR}} \propto f^2 u^2 \propto v^2$, i.e. the quadratic relationship already known from Fig. 7.1. However, frequency was explicitly varied here.

It can be further determined that heating depends heavily on the vibration developing on the surface of the part to be examined. If there are no local distortions in a crack, no heating is observed. It will depend on the individual case, i.e. especially on the individual crack and the surrounding local geometry, whether mode I, II or III movements are possible and which gives rise to the strongest heating.

7.1.3 Dependency of Heating on Normal Force on Crack

Ordinarily the normal force between the crack faces can only be influenced with great difficulty. An example of a real crack in which the normal force can be adjusted nearly arbitrarily is the connecting rod in Fig. 7.7. For assembly on the crankshaft, the finished machined connecting rod is scribed with a laser beam and is then forced apart. The two halves can then be placed around the crankshaft and reassembled with two bolts (M8x1). As the connecting rod is made from a relatively brittle aluminum alloy, the crack faces fit very well on bolting together again.

For thermography, this yields the possibility of adjusting the preload force F_A via torque M on the crack, estimating the force as follows [ASS05]:

$$F_A \approx 2M (\mu_K d_A + d_2 \tan(\beta + \rho'))^{-1}, \quad (7.5)$$

Figure 7.6: Test setup for forced generation of mode III shearing movement at the crack and resulting heating as a function of deflection (top) and frequency (bottom).

Figure 7.7: Connecting rod in which the normal force on the crack can be adjusted with the bolt tensioning torque (top) and dependence of heating on this torque (bottom).

with friction angle

$$\rho' = \arctan \frac{\mu}{\cos \alpha/2}, \quad (7.6)$$

thread flank angle $\alpha = 60^\circ$ (for a metric ISO thread), lead angle $\beta = \arctan(p/d_2\pi)$ for pitch $p = 1$ mm (fine thread) and flank diameter $d_2 = 7,35$ mm as well as $d_2 = 7.35$ mm and $d_A = (D_a + D_i)/2$ for bolt head diameter $D_a = 13.4$ mm and bore diameter $D_i = 8.3$ mm. Values of between 0.1 and 0.14 are assumed for the coefficients of friction in accordance with [ASS05].

The crack area was estimated geometrically at roughly 150 mm^2 . This finally yields a value of roughly 5 MPa/Nm for the stress at the interfaces. Fig. 7.7 (bottom) shows the result in which heating at the crack is plotted against torque and estimated stress. There is apparently an optimum torque which results in maximum heating. This is plausible, as in the limiting case of the force going to zero, the crack faces are no longer in contact and can slide past each other without heating losses, while on the other hand $F_A \rightarrow \infty$ represents the transition to the continuum, i.e. freedom from cracks, where again no heat is generated [RH05].

7.1.4 Dependency of Heating on Local Roughness

Cracks do not always heat uniformly over their entire length (cf. Fig. 5.14, p. 70). Asperities result in local contact points with especially pronounced heating. Fig. 7.8 shows a plastic cap which was pressed against 100-grit sandpaper with two screw clamps. The point heating at the local contact points can be clearly seen, (Fig. 7.8b/c), as well as the dependence on the operation deflection shape described above, which results in different images at different frequencies (Fig. 7.8d shows a processed difference image where the differences are clear).

Figure 7.8: Contact points between sandpaper and plastic cap exhibit local heating on ultrasonic excitation. a. Test setup, b/c. Infrared images for two different frequencies, d. Local differences in heating can be seen in the difference image. The patch in the center is from a piece of reflecting foil used to measure the spectrum.

7.2 Discussion of Various Mechanisms

It is known from the above that cracks are only heated where there is local distortion of the material. However, this does not yet explain the actual mechanism resulting in the temperature increase. Possible mechanisms which can result in crack heating are discussed below.

7.2.1 Thermoelastic Effect

This effect, discovered by Lord Kelvin is the counterpart of thermal expansion in metals. It describes the temperature change ΔT in an object on application of an external stress $\Delta\sigma$:

$$\Delta T_{el} = -\frac{\alpha}{\rho C} T_0 \Delta\sigma + Q, \quad (7.7)$$

with linear thermal expansion coefficient α , specific heat capacity C , material density ρ and heat Q . In the adiabatic limiting case, which is well approximated at the frequencies used in acoustic thermography, Equation (7.7) simplifies to

$$\Delta T_{el} = -\frac{\alpha}{\rho C} T_0 \Delta\sigma \quad (7.8)$$

and a cyclic change in stress results in a proportional temperature change. This effect can be easily demonstrated at low frequencies $f \lesssim 50$ Hz such as can be achieved in tensile testing machines (Fig. 7.9).

Figure 7.9: Demonstration of thermoelastic effect with a steel specimen clamped in a tensile testing machine (parameters: 11 kN oscillation load superimposed on 15 kN baseline load, 20 Hz vibration frequency)

Two difficulties arise at ultrasonic frequencies. On the one hand, the achievable mechanical stress is considerably lower than for the tensile testing machines, while on the other the specimen temperature also varies at the same ultrasonic frequencies used, in this case on the order of 20 kHz, which cannot normally be resolved with an infrared camera. The infrared camera used in this study (Thermosensorik CMT 256 HS) has a maximum (full)image repeat rate of 880 Hz and is thus the fastest on the market. Excitation frequencies of less than 440 Hz would thus be required to enable resolution of the thermoelastic effect. Although these frequencies can be generated using piezoelectric and electromagnetic shakers, the resulting temperature changes cannot be detected (due to the low mechanical stresses achievable).

Frame rates of up to $f_{\max} = 20$ kHz can be achieved in crop mode, i.e. on reducing the lateral resolution of the camera image (to roughly 8×8 pixels), thus resolving excitation frequencies of up to 10 kHz. However, this entails a significant reduction in sensitivity. Where an integration time of $t_i \approx 1$ ms can be achieved in full screen mode, t_i decreases to 50 μ s at the maximum frame rate, which is manifested in poorer sensitivity.

For the piezoelectric exciters or electromagnetic shakers used in this study, the lowest frequency for which heating was detectable in full screen mode was roughly 8 kHz. For the turbine blade from Fig. 4.13, it was possible to also measure heating in subframe mode by utilizing a strong resonance at $f_R \approx 11$ kHz. The excitation frequency was rendered visible by aliasing at $f_{\max} - f_R \approx 9$ kHz. It was thus at least in principle possible to separate the reversible thermoelastic effect from irreversible effects in a measurement. After one second, the temperature amplitudes of the thermoelastic effect were on the same order of magnitude as those of the irreversible phenomena.

Stresses in materials under load can be measured at low frequencies by thermal stress analysis (TSA) ([DYP03], [HW92], [MG04], [OR85], [Puk87], [Pur87], [SKR95], [SW97], [SD96]).

7.2.2 Damping

Damping of the ultrasonic wave in the material results in local heating [ACZ03], where cracks further increase damping [BSR03]. The various mechanisms which can result in damping ([AW01a], [AW01b], [HJ72], [Gre04], [Gre87], [Kut88]), are of no consequence for this evaluation.

Various cases are shown schematically in the stress/strain diagrams in Fig. 7.10. Purely elastic and undamped phenomena (Fig. 7.10a) result in proportionality between stress and strain (Hooke's law range) and no heating.

The damped case (Fig. 7.10b) can be represented phenomenologically by a phase shift (loss angle δ) between stress σ and strain ε , or by an imaginary component in Young's modulus [Kut88],

$$E = E' + iE'' = E'(1 + i\delta) \stackrel{\delta \ll 1}{\approx} E' \exp(i\delta), \quad (7.9)$$

with storage modulus E' and loss modulus E'' . Strain ε and stress σ are then related as follows:

$$\sigma = \varepsilon E \exp(2\pi i f t) \stackrel{\delta \ll 1}{\approx} \varepsilon E' \exp(i(2\pi f t + \delta)). \quad (7.10)$$

The heat loss generated per unit volume is [Kut88]

$$P_V = E' \varepsilon^2 \pi f \delta. \quad (7.11)$$

The dissipated energy thus increases with ε^2 , at least as long as the yield point is not reached. The temperature rise ΔT is thus proportional to ε^2 . Once the stress reaches the yield point, the area only increases with ε (Fig. 7.10c) in the elastic/perfectly plastic case (which only represents an approximation, cf. Fig. 4 in [RHS80] for a real measurement on aluminum).

In this model, heating is linearly dependent on frequency, as this only indicates the number of cycles in the hysteresis loop per unit time. Frequency dependence is generally a function of the mechanism underlying damping.

Several authors refer to the effect of damping causing local heating. According to [Fis87] the temperature increase is proportional to the product of the damping factor, excitation frequency and the square of the local stress amplitude. Initial correlations of heating with the strain antinodes are given in [MGD⁺81].

Figure 7.10: Schematic showing various mechanisms in the stress/strain diagram. Heat loss per cycle is given in each case by the area under the curve. a. Purely elastic phenomena without dissipation, b. Damped elastic phenomena with phase shift between stress and strain. As the area under the curve increases with ε^2 , the temperature increase ΔT is also proportional to ε^2 , c. Elastic, perfectly plastic phenomena. There is an upper limit to stress, i.e. The area under the curve only increases with ε with increasing strain, e. Mixed case.

Measurements on plastics

Since plastics have higher internal friction than metals [Kut88] they are especially well suited for investigating the heating mechanism by damping. Various PVC plates with dimensions $90 \times 90 \times 5 \text{ mm}^3$ were prepared for the experiments and attached to a tunable piezoelectric exciter by bolting or bonding with X-60 adhesive (Figs. 7.11a and b).

The first experiment was performed using a slotted plate (Fig. 7.11a), in which increased heat generation was anticipated due to the stress concentration at the tip of the slot (cf. Section 5.1, p. 59). Fig. 7.12 shows the local heating at the slot tip in agreement with the theory. This area was measured using the vibrometer and the strain values calculated from the results. The increased strain at the tip of the slot in good agreement with the infrared measurement can be seen, as well as the correlation of strain in the rest of the plate with the heating points.

Figure 7.11: Schematic test setup for correlation of strain and infrared image. The dashed lines indicate the respective area of the infrared or strain image.

Figure 7.12: PVC plate with slot as shown in setup 7.11a. Heating at the tip of the slot can be clearly seen at a frequency of 30,200 Hz (left), cf. Fig. 5.8, p. 64. Strain (right) was determined from a vibration measurement, where the circular region around the slot tip was measured at higher resolution.

An intact plate was used in a second experiment (Fig. 7.11b). The operation deflection shapes were first measured at various resonant frequencies (Fig. 7.13) with the setup described in Section 2.3.

Figure 7.13: Spectrum for PVC specimen used for correlation of strain and IR signal. The following resonant frequencies were used for the measurement (all in Hz): 7,850, 8,600, 11,030, 14,470, 15,700, 18,500, 20,700, 33,400.

In-plane strains were calculated from the operation deflection shapes in accordance with

$$\varepsilon_i = \sqrt{\varepsilon_{xx}^2 + \varepsilon_{yy}^2}. \quad (7.12)$$

Fig. 7.14 shows the very good agreement of the measured infrared and strain images.

For quantitative determination of the correlation between strain and temperature, the data were extracted from the images as follows: The mean $\langle I_{\text{IR}}, \varepsilon \rangle$ for the pixels in 16 $n_x \times n_y = 12 \times 12$ pixel region of interest (ROI) of the thermal images was plotted against the mean of the pixels in the corresponding 2×2 pixel ROI of the

Figure 7.14: Comparison of infrared (top row, scale in K) and in-plane strain images calculated from measured vibration data (bottom row, all strains in 10^{-5} m/m) for selected resonant frequencies of the PVC plate (cf. Figs. 7.11 and 7.13). The lighter points in the center of the bottom edge of the image can be attributed to heating of the adhesive used to bond the piezoelectric exciter to the plate at this point). The resolution of the thermal images is 256×256 pixels (from which a section of roughly 230×230 pixels is shown here) and that of the strain images is 40×40 pixels.

strain images:

$$\langle I \rangle = \frac{1}{n_x n_y} \sum_{a=0}^{n_x-1} \sum_{b=0}^{n_y-1} I(x_i + a, y_i + b), \quad (7.13)$$

where (x_i, y_i) are the coordinates of the i th ROI (and accordingly for the strain images). As the resolution of the thermal images was 256×256 but that of the operation deflection shapes only 40×40 pixels, the position and size of the ROIs was scaled accordingly. Fig. 7.15 shows the data obtained for three selected resonant

Figure 7.15: Correlation of infrared and strain data for three selected resonant frequencies. From top left to bottom right: 7,850, 14,480, 18,513 Hz. The symbols in the images indicate where the ROI mean values in the thermal image are plotted against the corresponding ROI mean values in the strain image.

frequencies. The error bars δI were calculated from the scatter in the mean values,

$$\delta I = \frac{1}{n_x n_y} \sqrt{\sum_{a=0}^{n_x-1} \sum_{b=0}^{n_y-1} (\langle I \rangle - I(x_i + a, y_i + b))^2}. \quad (7.14)$$

As in Fig. 7.1, the following quadratic relationship results to good approximation for all three resonant frequencies:

$$\Delta T \propto I_{\text{IR}} \propto \varepsilon^2 \propto v^2 \quad (7.15)$$

In addition, the proportionality constants in $\Delta T(v, f) = c(f)v^2$ can be plotted against f in order to determine the frequency dependence of the damping. This yields the diagram shown in Fig. 7.16. These data are compatible with a proportionality between heating and frequency, i.e. overall $\Delta T \propto \sigma^2 f$ in agreement with [Fis87].

Measurements on carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP)

Analogous results were obtained for carbon fiber reinforced plastics. This time, a 20 kHz piezoelectric exciter from KLN was used, which was bonded to an area in a corner of the roughly 30×30 cm plate. A resonant frequency at 20,200 Hz was evaluated for an 8×8 cm area at the adjacent corner.

Correlating the 3D strain data obtained from a vibrometer measurement with the infrared image for the same area yields Fig. 7.17, and, as in Fig. 7.14, it can be seen that the areas of heating coincide with the maxima of the in-plane strains. It

Figure 7.16: Frequency dependence of damping. See text for details.

can also be seen in Fig. 7.17 that the in-plane strains calculated from the out-of-plane deflections using the theory from Section 3.6 exhibit a considerably improved signal-to-noise ratio compared with the directly calculated data.

Figure 7.17: a. Infrared image of part of a CFRP plate excited at 20,200 Hz. b–d. Square of in-plane strains calculated from vibration measurement b. ε_{xx} from u_x , c. ε_{xx} from u_z with circular fit, d. ε_{xx} from u_z with parabolic fit over 5 points (cf. Section 3.6).

Measurements on a metal strip

Internal friction in metals is typically significantly less than in plastics, and large vibration amplitudes are required in order to still render them visible. In order to achieve this, an M5 bolt was welded to a piezoelectric transducer for a Diesel injector by laser welding and a thin piece of steel ($90 \times 15 \times 1 \text{ mm}^3$) was attached to this. The steel strip had a transverse slot in the center. This resulted in the same

thin ligaments on both sides, which had to accommodate all of the vibration energy. Because of the stress amplification in this area (Section 5.1), heating was the highest there (Fig. 7.18a, unprocessed raw image). After subtracting the background image and increasing the contrast (Fig. 7.18b), additional transverse lines become visible parallel to the slot, which could be clearly attributed to the antinodes of the in-plane strain by subsequent vibration measurement (Fig. 7.18c). The ligaments could not be resolved in the vibration measurement.

An even better correlation is obtained on comparison with simulated finite element images (Fig. 7.18d). The color-coded stress is plotted here which clearly coincides with the zones of heating. The calculated frequencies were 17.3 kHz and 44.1 kHz, in very good agreement with the experimental results. Fig. 7.19 shows a 3D view for better visualization of the two vibration modes.

Figure 7.18: Correlation of thermal images with strain and stress images. The steel strip ($90 \times 15 \times 1 \text{ mm}^3$) was heated most at the strain antinodes (I_1). These are the most pronounced at the ligaments (above and below the transverse slot) (I_3), but could not be resolved in the vibration measurement. a. Raw thermal image, b. Thermal image after subtraction of background image, c. In-plane strain calculated from measured vibration in area outlined with dashed line, d. Stress pattern calculated from a finite element simulation.

Figure 7.19: 3D view of deflection with color-coded stress in vibration modes from Fig. 7.18

Heating values of $I_2 = 1.15$ (strain node), $I_1 = 2.13$ (strain antinode/transverse lines) and $I_3 = 2200$ (bottom ligament) result for the 42 kHz resonant frequency.

The width of the strip was 15 mm and that of the ligaments 1.2 mm, with a slot width of 0.75 mm. This yields the following from (5.8) and (5.9) (p. 62) for stress σ_2 in the ligaments:

$$\sigma_2 = \sigma_1 K_t \approx 70\sigma_1. \quad (7.16)$$

The corresponding ratio for infrared emission is

$$\frac{I_3}{I_1 - I_2} \approx 2200. \quad (7.17)$$

If the infrared emission is a function of the square of the stress, a factor of $70^2 = 4900$ would be expected for the ratio in (7.17). The deviation of roughly a factor of 2 obtained is acceptable for the estimate made here, as the slot was approximated with an ellipse, the infrared intensity at the transverse lines is only roughly a factor of 2 greater than the background value (increasing the error in the denominator of Eq. (7.17)) and finally nonlinearities in the camera would have to be taken into account for a more exact calculation at the high intensities occurring at the ligaments ($I_3 \gg I_1$).

Eq. (3.46) is useful for an estimate of heating at the transverse lines. The strain component can be estimated as $\varepsilon_{xx} = 0.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$ from the measured values for the z deflection of $u_z \approx 0.7 \mu\text{m}$.

A loss angle δ of 0.006 then yields an energy density of $w_{\text{el}} \approx 0.6 \text{ J/m}^2$ due to damping, and from

$$w_{\text{el}}VN = c\rho V\Delta T \quad \Rightarrow \quad \Delta T = \frac{Nw_{\text{el}}}{c\rho} \quad (7.18)$$

where $N = 42000$ (42 kHz at an excitation time of one second), $\rho = 7800 \text{ kg/m}^3$, $c = 0.45 \text{ kJ/(kg K)}$, a temperature increase (neglecting heat conduction) of $\Delta T \approx 7 \text{ K}$ is obtained, which corresponds to the order of magnitude of the measured value of 2 K.

Measurements on a turbine blade

At this point a plausible explanation should be given for the selective heating of the turbine blade on p. 93. This is achieved with the Lamb wave model at 19 kHz. The blade airfoil is then heated at the deflection antinodes analogously to Fig. 7.18. However, this is not observable for the turbine blade due to the lower deflection amplitudes, instead only the heating of the crack extending through the full thickness of the blade airfoil is detectable.

Assuming the crack to be in a deflection antinode (which is supported by the z deflection at this frequency in Fig. 7.5), the side can open which would ordinarily undergo the maximum strain (convex side), as no tensile forces can be transmitted across the idealized crack. In contrast, it is irrelevant whether the material is actually disconnected on the concave side, as only compression forces need be transmitted here. However, the compression forces at this point are now no longer compensated by the tensile forces on the concave side, with the result that the stress in this area increases. The resulting x deflection would be antisymmetric with the crack axis, as can also be seen in Fig. 7.5.

This can also be illustrated very clearly in a scale finite element simulation (Fig. 7.20), in which the crack is modeled as a groove of the same length but which in

contrast to the crack does not pass through the full thickness of the blade airfoil. This results in a simplified model of the situation, realistic at least for a half cycle of the vibration, which permits one-sided opening without the need to account for crack-specific effects such as friction or contact phenomena. Despite this simplification, a local zone of high stress results along the crack. Although this qualitative model cannot account for the additional friction component, it does show that heating would have to result solely due to damping.

Figure 7.20: Comparison of all data for aircraft turbine blade. a. Vibration data, b. Infrared measurement, c. Sections for measurements and FEM image of crack, d. Finite element simulation of blade airfoil with idealized crack; Von Mises stresses are shown

The contributions of damping and friction to overall heating could also at least theoretically be separately determined in this way, by calculating the temperature increase due to damping by FEM, with the difference from the measurement then corresponding to the additional contribution due to friction. The requisite finite element model for this, with contact elements and the associated difficulties as well as the need for transient analysis, go beyond the scope of this study, but could serve to improve understanding of the heating mechanism in a further study.

Supplement to measurements on polystyrene cup

Vibration of the polystyrene cup from Fig. 7.3 can be analyzed in more detail by the same approach (p. 92). To simplify the calculation, a lower-order radial vibration was simulated in order to keep the number of nodes in the model manageable. Fig. 7.21a again shows the infrared measurement, and Figs. 7.21b–d show stress images for a comparable lower-order mode. Two cracks were approximated as above for the turbine blade with grooves which only partially penetrate the bottom of the cup. The increased stress at the deflection antinodes of the bottom of the cup shall

be clearly seen, as well as the local stress amplification at the grooves. As above, friction will also play an additional role here, and the exact distribution of the heating components between damping and friction would have to be determined in more detailed investigations.

Figure 7.21: a. Infrared measurement from Fig. 7.3, showing the annular heating on the bottom of the cup as well as discontinuous heating of the cracks, c-d. Various views from finite element simulation of the stresses in a comparable mode in a thin plate with grooves

7.2.3 Friction

Kinetic friction

The apparent mechanism which results in heating of defect faces such as crack faces or delamination edges is friction. There is an abundance of literature on this subject in the professional world ranging over theoretical contact problems ([Bar76], [EI96], [Pau04]), the measurement of coefficients of friction [MLB03] and up to friction on the atomic scale [GBGM01], [RRS⁺03].

The empirical basis for tribology is Coulomb's law of friction,

$$W_F = \mu F_N s \quad (7.19)$$

(with coefficient of friction μ , normal force F_N and displacement s), which applies for kinetic friction. The displacement s transited during an ultrasonic pulse of duration T can then be expressed by the particle velocity v , enabling the following to be stated for crack opening mode II (in-plane shear, cf. p. 62) [HRBS06]:

$$W_F = \mu F_N \int_0^T |\tilde{v}'(t)| dt = \frac{2}{\pi} \mu F_N v' T \quad \text{mit} \quad \tilde{v}'(t) = v' \cos(\omega t). \quad (7.20)$$

Sinusoidal movement of the crack faces was assumed here, where the relative velocity of the crack edges is designated as v' . The absolute value accounts for the directional independence of friction. By contrast, transitions between static and kinetic friction, especially as they occur at the reversal points (stick-slip effects) are neglected in Eq. (7.20).

If all of the other parameters are constant, the heat generated for a given excitation time T is a linear function of v' , which contradicts (7.4). In order to obtain the measured quadratic dependence, at least one of the parameters would thus have to be variable with time. If the actual normal force is dependent on velocity, this would yield the proportionality to v^2 [RH05]. It was demonstrated in finite element simulations that the normal force varies with time on ultrasonic excitation [HI06].

This can also be plausibly explained. The normal force in a body is replaced by the stress per unit area σ/A . For crack opening Π , $\sigma_{yy} = \varepsilon_{yy}E$ must be applied. As strain can in turn be calculated from velocity and the wavelength,

$$F'_N = F'_N(v) = \frac{\varepsilon_y E}{A} \quad \text{mit} \quad \varepsilon_y = \frac{2\pi u}{\lambda} = \frac{2\pi v_y}{\lambda\omega} \quad (7.21)$$

and

$$v_y \propto v' \quad (7.22)$$

applies, Eq. (7.20) then becomes

$$W'_F(v) = \frac{2\pi E\mu}{\lambda\omega A} \int_0^T v_y(t)|V'(t)|dt \propto v^2. \quad (7.23)$$

An additional possibility would be dependence of the coefficient of friction on the normal force, which has been observed on microscopic levels [End00].

Static friction

Another interpretation of friction is obtained in using the measured data which yield that the deflection of the crack edges is less than roughly 5 μm in most cases and often also considerably less. This can easily be on the order of the surface roughness of a crack face, which would in turn mean that the assumptions of kinetic friction do not at all apply. Although local slip could occur at asperities (“microslip”, [MMOD52]), the quadratic dependence on deflection can also be described by a simple model in which the individual asperities are engaged in each other and are only moved against each other, causing elastic deformation. This then corresponds again to Fig. 7.10b with the known quadratic correlation between heating and deflection, and (7.4) would be automatically fulfilled.

Effect of friction on crack morphology

Friction is not a reversible process and results in wear on the bodies sliding past each other. In order to demonstrate this, a 2-Euro coin was selected, the two parts of which are pressed together securely. If this coin is excited with power ultrasonic waves from an ultrasonic welding unit, the ring of the contact surface can be seen to light up nonhomogeneously in the infrared. After several pulses, the inner disk can finally even be forced out. Zones of differing degrees of wear can be seen on a photograph of the disk. The locations of the areas of more pronounced damage can

be clearly correlated with those of highest heating (Fig. 7.22). The fact that this does not in principle call into question the non-destructiveness of acoustic thermography has already been explained in Section 5.6.

Figure 7.22: Top row: 2-Euro coin during excitation with power ultrasonic waves (infrared images); after several pulses the inner ring was finally forced out. Upper large image: infrared image during final sequence. Bottom image: photograph of inner disk after forcing out. The areas of increased wear can be clearly seen; these correlate with the locations of the thermal signals (solid lines), as well as the areas of less damage, which are also not visible in the thermal image (dashed lines).

A disadvantage of the above experiment is that the condition of the contact areas prior to ultrasonic excitation is unknown. The connecting rod in Fig. 7.7 (p. 95) proves useful here, as in this case the crack faces can be investigated under a microscope both before as well as after ultrasonic excitation. In addition to the micrographs prior to the examination, Fig. 7.23 also shows the micrograph resulting after the application of 10 pulses of 1 s each with the ultrasonic welding unit. At first glance, no differences between the micrographs are evident, for which reason the inverted difference image is also shown (Fig. 7.23 right). Differences appear as black areas here.

It can be clearly seen that there are only a few scattered differences. The local surface changes in one of these areas is plainly evident in the detail (Fig. 7.24). Individual asperities have disappeared or shifted here.

7.2.4 Plastic Deformation

According to the concepts of fracture mechanics (Section 5.1.2, p. 62), the ideal crack tip is always subject to plastic deformation. This situation is modified in real

Figure 7.23: Micrographs of crack faces of connecting rod from Fig. 7.7 before and after ultrasonic excitation.

Figure 7.24: Detailed view of micrographs from Fig. 7.23.

solids by mechanisms such as crack tip blunting or residual stresses. However, it can be experimentally verified that plastic deformation also occurs here above a certain threshold stress [SSK01].

Another aircraft turbine blade was selected for a corresponding experiment and was subjected to heavy vibration by piezoelectric excitation. The radius of the plastic zone at the crack tip can be estimated with Eq. (5.32), p. 66:

$$r_p \approx \frac{K_I^2}{\pi\sigma_Y^2}. \quad (7.24)$$

Taken with

$$K_I = \sigma\sqrt{\pi a}F(a/b) \approx 1.1\sigma\sqrt{\pi a}, \quad (7.25)$$

and

$$\sigma = \varepsilon E = \frac{2\pi Eu}{\lambda}, \quad (7.26)$$

this leads to

$$r_p \approx a \left(\frac{2.2\pi Eu}{\lambda\sigma_Y} \right)^2. \quad (7.27)$$

For typical values of $u = 2 \mu\text{m}$, $\lambda = 5 \text{ mm}$, $a = 2 \text{ mm}$, $\sigma_Y = 900 \text{ MPa}$ and $E = 120 \text{ GPa}$, a radius of roughly 0.3 mm is obtained for the plastic zone. As all of

the parameters with the exception of crack length a are included in the quadratic term, Eq. (7.27) can only be an estimate of the order of magnitude. The infrared camera would have had a pixel resolution of roughly $20\ \mu\text{m}$ with the lens used, so plastic effects would have to be detectable.

Heating of the blade is plotted as a function of particle velocity in Fig. 7.25. Interestingly, two areas can be distinguished:

- At low vibrations ($v \lesssim 900\ \text{mm/s}$), heating increases roughly quadratically with velocity.
- At higher vibrations, the exponent in $I_{\text{IR}} \propto v^\alpha$ is close to 1.

It is also apparent that absolute heating in this second area depends on the prior history and decreases with increasing number of measurement series. A possible explanation for this is that the processes are purely elastic for low vibrations, while plastic terms cannot be neglected for higher vibration cycles. This would also plausibly explain the fact that the slope changes between the measurement series. Plastic deformation results in irreversible changes in the material, which are then manifested in reduced heating in subsequent measurements at high amplitudes.

Figure 7.25: Correlation between infrared and vibration data. See text for details.

7.2.5 Conclusion

It can be determined from the above investigations that bulk heating is induced by damping of the ultrasonic wave, with a quadratic dependence on local strain. This was demonstrated for plastics, composites (qualitatively) and metals. The observation that coatings are heated during ultrasonic excitation can be explained by the same mechanism.

In none of the measurements could plastic deformation be detected in the bulk, as the stresses achieved were always far lower than the yield point. Plastic effects are most likely to be demonstrable in the vicinity of high stress concentration (crack tips). At least one experiment could be interpreted in this way.

The mechanism of friction also plays a role at interfaces in the material (cracks, delamination). The quadratic dependence of heating on deflection of the crack edges measured in most of the experiments is explained by classic Coulomb's law behavior if an additional dependence of the normal force acting on the crack edges is accounted for. Initial steps have been taken to demonstrate this by finite element simulations [HI06]. On the other hand, the simple static friction model presented would also explain the qualitative v^2 dependence.

Several of the above mechanisms will usually play a role due to the roughness of the crack edges and their in part complex geometry. A quantitative resolution of the individual effects could possibly be achieved using finite element simulations, but this is only possible in the scope of further studies.

Chapter 8

Summary and Outlook

Two aspects of acoustic thermography are examined in this study for which there have previously been no detailed investigations, namely technical implementation of the method as well as the mechanism which causes heat generation in the examined object.

In publications to date, the laboratory systems based on ultrasonic welders due to their simple applicability are used only for examining individual parts containing defects, for which reason investigations of the reproducibility of the method in series tests have not been performed. The large scatter in vibration amplitudes and heating determined between the individual specimens in series testing on turbine blades in this study can be clearly attributed to the different blade spectra using laser vibrometric measurements. Even parts of the of the same type exhibit resonant peaks of different magnitude and especially at different frequencies within the frequency range under consideration (20–60 kHz), which can be caused by even slight fabrication tolerances. This results in the large scatter observed from the usual fixed-frequency excitation from ultrasonic welding systems (typically 20 kHz). However, where there is no solid sonic coupling, hammering of the sonotrode on the specimen results in the excitation of higher harmonics (up to 10th order and above), and statistical coincidence with the resonant frequencies in these areas thus results in adequate usability (multi-frequency excitation) despite the generator-specific monofrequency exciter.

However, improved reproducibility is possible only by tuning of the excitation frequency to the resonant frequencies of the respective part. It can be demonstrated with the newly developed method using tunable exciters that this also enables a dramatic increase in the efficiency of the method, as lower electrical power is sufficient to achieve adequate vibration of the specimen.

A quadratic dependence of heating on vibration amplitude is also determined in these investigations, which further contributes to the efficiency of resonant excitation compared with forced non-resonant excitation. The resulting problem that the defect signals depend heavily on the deflection shape associated with a resonant frequency can be resolved by the excitation of multiple resonant frequencies. This aspect is less important for excitation with ultrasonic systems for plastic welding processes, as the higher harmonics ensure a more balanced vibration image.

Regardless of the exact excitation method, excessive stresses in the material can result in crack initiation or growth, as can be experimentally verified. However, the risk of part damage can be reduced by using vibration data. Firstly, specific

modes which excessively load structures which are especially at risk can be avoided already in excitation. This can be optimized in specific cases by means such as finite element simulations. Furthermore, an in-situ procedure is possible in which the exciter amplitude is controlled with the vibration data. The phenomena of crack closure, which is induced by compression stresses in fatigue cracks, and crack tip blunting are two explanations for the fact that a certain minimum stress must first be exceeded for crack growth to occur.

A newly developed 3D laser vibrometer measuring system can be used for determining 3D material stresses, which enables derivation of the corresponding components of the strain tensor from the 3D vibration data measured over a 2D area. However, the use of a 1D vibrometer is also possible for sufficiently thin plate-like geometries. This alternative is possible with a modified Lamb wave theory which enables the calculation of the absolute 3D stresses from the 1D out-of-plane deflections given a known plate thickness. This can be experimentally verified.

Three mechanisms are identified for the heating of cracks: damping, friction and plastic deformation. As cracks represent a local weakening of the material, elevated stresses result at these points as a function of the deflection shape which then cause local heating through internal friction. Vibration modes of idealized cracks in plastic and metal parts were calculated using finite element simulations. It proved that the points of heating in the infrared image can be correlated with the areas of increased local stress even without accounting for Coulomb's law friction. It is possible to use the vibrometer measurement system to demonstrate a quadratic correlation of bulk heating with in-plane strains in plastics and metals. Energy dissipation by damping is regarded as the mechanism for bulk heating based on this.

Friction is an additional effect which increases local energy dissipation. The observed quadratic dependence of heating on deflection can be described from a friction perspective by the additional modulation of the normal force pressing the crack faces together, which also agrees with the finite element simulations by another research group. Because of the small deflections generated in the parts by ultrasonic excitation, a true case of kinetic friction cannot be assumed, but rather a mode which is heavily dominated by static friction.

Because of the individual properties of cracks, especially local geometries and roughness which depend on factors including the history of their formation, a quantitative resolution of the three mechanisms is difficult at best. However, at least one measurement indicates that plastic deformation at the crack tip or other areas of increased stress concentration also cannot be neglected above certain threshold amplitudes.

The potential of acoustic thermography lies especially in its high speed, the objective visual results and its application even to complex geometries. These aspects result in a significant competitive advantage, especially compared with classic dye penetrant examination.

Further work should concentrate on the use of tunable exciters, as, in addition to higher efficiency, this has the advantage of smaller size, which could also enable in-situ use on installed parts, such as in a gas turbine.

Appendix A

Appendix

A.1 Essential Symbols

Symbol	Meaning	Units
A	Characteristic defect parameter (e.g. length, length/2, width)	m
$a_i(x, t)$	Time and spatially dependent acceleration of a point on an object (component i as for u_i), $a_i = \partial/\partial t v_i = \partial^2/\partial t^2 u_i$	m/s ²
α	Diffusivity	m ² /s
ε_{ij}	Strain	m/m
f	Frequency	Hz
f_s	Sampling rate of A/D card for data acquisition	Hz
G_{ab}	Cross power spectrum ($a \neq b$) or auto power spectrum ($a = b$)	
H_i	Estimator for frequency response function (FRF)	
I	Infrared intensity	a.u.
$K_{\text{I-III}}$	Stress intensity factor for crack modes I–III	MPa $\sqrt{\text{m}}$
K_t	Stress concentration factor	–
λ	Wavelength	m
	Thermal conductivity	W/(K m)
λ^*	Lamé parameter	MPa
μ	Lamé parameter	MPa
σ_{ij}	Mechanical stress	MPa
σ_Y	Yield stress	MPa
$\vec{u}(\vec{x}, t)$	Time and spatially dependent deflection of a point on an object	m
$\vec{v}(\vec{x}, t)$	Time and spatially dependent velocity of a point on an object, $\vec{v} = \partial/\partial t \vec{u}$	m/s
$x(t)$	Excitation signal	
$X(f)$	Fourier transform of $x(t)$	
$y(t)$	Object response signal	
$Y(f)$	Fourier transform of $y(t)$	

Table A.1: Symbols

Appendix B

Heat Conduction in Solid Bodies

In acoustic thermography, mechanical energy is dissipated in the form of heat which then diffuses through the material. For hidden defects, heating of the surface cannot be detected with the infrared camera until after a certain time offset which is a measure of the depth of the defect.

In addition, inferences regarding the defect geometry can be obtained from the time history of the development of the surface temperature by data processing with known theoretical solutions.

B.1 Heat Transfer Mechanisms

B.1.1 Radiation

Thermal radiation is the only mechanism whereby heat energy can also be transported in vacuum, as it takes place through electromagnetic radiation. This phenomenon is used to measure the temperature of the surface of the body using thermal imaging cameras.

The spectral radiation power for a given temperature T and wavelength Λ , $P(\Lambda, T)$ can be described by Planck's law,

$$P(\Lambda, T) = \frac{2\pi hc^2}{\Lambda^5} (e^{hc/kT\Lambda} - 1)^{-1}. \quad (\text{B.1})$$

Real bodies only radiate a portion of this power, reduced by the factor ε . Emissivity ε is between 0 (perfect reflector) and 1 (cavity radiator). It is often important to artificially increase emissivity for thermography, as in particular small temperature differences at low emissivity are no longer detectable above background noise in the camera.

This increase can be achieved by measures such as spraying specimens with insufficient emission with a thin coating of graphite or paint. This enables the achievement of emissivities of roughly 0.95. Graphite was used as an emissivity enhancer for many experiments in this study.

B.1.2 Conduction

The heat conduction equation applies for the conduction of heat in materials [Mes04],

$$\vec{j} = -\lambda \vec{\nabla} T. \quad (\text{B.2})$$

Heat flux \vec{j} is proportional to the gradient of temperature T and thermal conductivity λ , which describes the power which can be transported per unit temperature difference and unit length ($[\lambda] = \text{W}/(\text{K m})$). Table B.1 shows an overview of the thermal conductivities of several substances.

Substance	λ in W/(K m)
Diamond	2300
Silver	420
Copper	390
Aluminum	230
Steel	100
Concrete	2.1
Glass	1.0
Water	0.54
Air	0.024

Table B.1: Thermal conductivity of several substances at 0 °C [Mes04]

A change in the heat content Q of a volume element dV is [Mes04]

$$(\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{j})dV = -\dot{Q}. \quad (\text{B.3})$$

Given heat capacity $C = \rho c_p dV = Q/T$, the temperature change with time is then

$$\dot{T} = -\frac{1}{\rho c_p} \vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{j}. \quad (\text{B.4})$$

Substituting (B.2) in (B.4) yields the general heat conduction equation

$$\dot{T} = \alpha \Delta T \quad (\text{B.5})$$

where

$$\Delta = \vec{\nabla}^2 = \left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2} \right) \quad (\text{B.6})$$

and diffusivity

$$\alpha = \frac{\lambda}{\rho c_p} \quad (\text{B.7})$$

with units of m^2/s , which is a measure of the time required for temperature equilibration.

B.1.3 Convection

Heat transfer by convection occurs in liquids and gases. For short measurement times, the convective heat transfer between a body and the ambient air can be neglected for thermography. Convection is therefore not further discussed here.

B.2 Solutions for the Heat Conduction Equation for Special Geometries

The heat conduction equation (B.5) will first be solved below for the simplest case of a point defect in a semiinfinite body for delta pulse excitation. The other solutions can be derived based on this. Burst excitation is of particular interest for acoustic thermography, i.e. a finite-length heating time τ . The geometries encountered most frequently, are point defects (all small defects relative to the image area), line defects (cracks) and area defects (delamination).

The following indices are used for the calculated temperature distribution $T_{i,j}^k$:

- $i \in \{P, L, A\}$ for point, line and area sources
- $j \in \{\infty, \infty\}$ for infinite and semiinfinite bodies
- $k \in \{\delta, B\}$ for a delta pulse or burst excitation.

B.2.1 Point Source in Infinite Body

Point source in infinite body with delta pulse excitation

The fundamental solution of the heat conduction equation (B.5) for a point source at coordinates (x_0, y_0, z_0) is as follows [CJ59]:

$$T_{P,\infty}^\delta(x, y, z, t) = \begin{cases} T_0 & \text{for } t < 0 \\ T_0 + \frac{Q}{(4\pi\alpha t)^{3/2}} \exp\left(-\frac{(x-x_0)^2 + (y-y_0)^2 + (z-z_0)^2}{4\alpha t}\right) & \text{for } t \geq 0, \end{cases} \quad (\text{B.8})$$

which can be easily demonstrated by substitution in (B.5). T_0 is the temperature at time zero, i.e. before the start of heating.

Placing the point source at the origin without loss of generality and integrating Eq. (B.8) over all space yields

$$\begin{aligned} T_0 + \frac{Q}{(4\pi\alpha t)^{3/2}} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \exp\left(-\frac{x^2 + y^2 + z^2}{4\alpha t}\right) dx dy dz &= \\ &= T_0 + \frac{Q}{(4\pi\alpha t)^{3/2}} \left(\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-\frac{x^2+y^2+z^2}{4\alpha t}} dx \right)^3. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.9})$$

Substituting $u := x/\sqrt{4\alpha t}$ finally yields

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} T_{P,\infty}(x, y, z, t) dx dy dz = T_0 + \frac{Q}{(4\pi\alpha t)^{3/2}} \left(\sqrt{4\pi\alpha t}\right)^3 = T_0 + Q. \quad (\text{B.10})$$

Q is thus identified as the generated temperature increase integrated over all space. The released energy is thus $E = CQ$.

Point source in infinite body with burst excitation

For thermographic excitation, especially for acoustic thermography, excitation is not a delta pulse but rather a burst, i.e. heating time $\tau > 0$. If t_0 is the time of heat generation, the desired solution is obtained by integrating $T_{P,\infty}(x, y, z, (t - t_0))$ over time:

$$T_{P,\infty}^B = \begin{cases} T_0 + \frac{1}{\tau} \int_0^t T_{P,\infty}(x, y, z, (t - t_0)) dt_0 & \text{for } t < \tau \\ T_0 + \frac{1}{\tau} \int_0^\tau T_{P,\infty}(x, y, z, (t - t_0)) dt_0 & \text{for } t > \tau. \end{cases} \quad (\text{B.11})$$

Heat Q is normalized by the factor $1/\tau$. Substituting $u := \sqrt{\frac{x^2 + y^2 + z^2}{4\alpha(t - t_0)}}$ yields

$$T_{P,\infty}^B = T_0 + \begin{cases} \frac{Q}{4\pi\alpha\tau\sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + z^2}} \left(1 - \operatorname{erf}\sqrt{\frac{x^2 + y^2 + z^2}{4\alpha t}} \right) & \text{for } t < \tau \\ \frac{Q}{4\pi\alpha\tau\sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + z^2}} \left(\operatorname{erf}\sqrt{\frac{x^2 + y^2 + z^2}{4\alpha(t - \tau)}} - \operatorname{erf}\sqrt{\frac{x^2 + y^2 + z^2}{4\alpha t}} \right) & \text{for } t > \tau, \end{cases} \quad (\text{B.12})$$

where $\operatorname{erf}(x)$ is the Gaussian error function

$$\operatorname{erf}(x) := \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^x \exp(-t^2) dt. \quad (\text{B.13})$$

B.2.2 Point Source in Semi-Infinite Body

Point source in semi-infinite body with delta pulse excitation

The semi-infinite body is bounded at a plane by vacuum. As there is no heat flow through this plane, the component of \vec{j} perpendicular to the surface, i.e. j_z , must vanish. This boundary condition is satisfied by using the method of reflected sources by analogy from electrostatics. In a coordinate system with its origin at the surface of the body and with a point source at position $(0, 0, z_0)$, i.e. at depth z_0 , this yields the following temperature distribution:

$$T_{P,\infty}^\delta = T_{P,\infty}^\delta(x, y, z_0, t) + T_{P,\infty}^\delta(x, y, -z_0, t) = T_0 + \frac{Q}{(4\pi\alpha t)^{3/2}} \left(\exp\left(-\frac{x^2 + y^2 + (z - z_0)^2}{4\alpha t}\right) + \exp\left(-\frac{x^2 + y^2 + (z + z_0)^2}{4\alpha t}\right) \right) \quad (\text{B.14})$$

B.2.3 Line and Surface Sources in Semi-Infinite Bodies

The solutions for line and surface sources can be derived by spatial integration of the solutions for the point sources along one or two coordinate axes.

B.3 Measurement of Infrared Radiation

B.3.1 Infrared Cameras

The measurements in this study were performed using a Thermosensorik CMT 256 M HS infrared camera. Table B.2 shows the most important data and the lenses used. Special emphasis should be placed on the short dead time for the camera, which is achieved using two-stage readout electronics (another exposure can be taken already during readout), and the resulting high frame rate of 880 Hz in full screen mode. This also enables the recording of fast phenomena.

Noise equivalent delta temperature (NEDT) is understood to be the temperature difference which yields a signal-to-noise ratio of 1. This temperature resolution can only be achieved by active cooling of the detector. Where cooling was previously effected using liquid nitrogen, Stirling coolers have since become commonplace.

The data are read out as 14-bit values ($0 \leq I = I_{\text{IR}} < 16383$) and can then be further processed. Infrared images are ordinarily displayed as grayscale images or are colored using color palettes. As current graphics cards provide color images with 24 bit color depth—i.e. 8 bits per RGB channel, only $2^8 = 256$ different grayscale values can be displayed. The 14-bit data from the camera must therefore be converted. A contrast adjustment is generally used which displays value I_{min} as black and I_{max} as white,

$$I'_{\text{IR}} = \left[255 \frac{I_{\text{IR}} - I_{\text{min}}}{I_{\text{max}} - I_{\text{min}}} \right]. \quad (\text{B.15})$$

The square brackets $[\cdot]$ here indicate the trimming of the result to the allowed range of $0 \dots 255$. This value can then be represented as a grayscale $(r, g, b) = I'_{\text{IR}}(1, 1, 1)$ or as a 256-color image using a lookup table.

Gamma adjustment is also conceivable to selectively emphasize the cooler or hotter areas::

$$I'_{\text{IR}} = \left[255 \left(\frac{I_{\text{IR}} - I_{\text{min}}}{I_{\text{max}} - I_{\text{min}}} \right)^{1/\gamma} \right]. \quad (\text{B.16})$$

This increases the contrast in the cooler areas for $\gamma > 1$ and in the warmer areas for $\gamma < 1$ without losing information in the other area.

B.3.2 Alternative Methoden

Individual point detectors represent a cost-effective alternative to infrared cameras, which, although they do not provide an image, can play a certain role for special cases (such as installed in a borescope).

Another method is the use of thermosensitive coatings. For example, the spray application of liquid crystal films to dark paints (for enhanced contrast) is already known since the '60s [BKC69]. The color change can then be detected with a conventional video camera. A key disadvantage is that the temperature range must be accounted for already on production of the liquid crystals. However, as the temperature range in the thermographic measurements is usually low (max. several K), room temperature must also be accounted for to enable optimum utilization of the sensitivity of the coating. The coatings also do not react especially quickly to temperature changes.

Manufacturer/name	Temperature sensor / CMT 256 M HS
Full screen frame rate	≈ 880 Hz ($T_{\text{int}} = 1$ ms)
Cropped image frame rate	≈ 20 kHz (for 8×8 Pixeln)
NETD	< 10 mK
Detector	CMT (cadmium/mercury/telluride CdHgTe)
Detector resolution	256×256 Pixel
Pixel array (active area)	$40 \mu\text{m}$ ($32 \times 32 \mu\text{m}^2$)
Spectral range	$3.4\text{--}5.1 \mu\text{m}$
Dynamic range	14 bit
28 mm lens	f/1.5, distance $0.5 \text{ m--}\infty$
Telephoto 100 mm	f/1.5, distance $1.5 \text{ m--}\infty$
Macro 2.5 \times	f/2, distance 21–22 mm

Table B.2: Key parameters for infrared camera and lens used

Tests with liquid crystal films performed in this study indicate that they could be interesting especially for induction thermography. The film is heated already solely due to vibration on ultrasonic excitation, although suitable optimization could enable area measurement of the vibration of an object without a scanning laser vibrometer.

B.4 Comparison of Theoretical Models with Measurements

Steel plates with thicknesses of 0.2–3.0 mm which were heated on the back with a laser were used for a comparison of the analytical solutions with measurements.

The laser was focused on a $300 \mu\text{m}$ spot (half-height width) using a 20 mm achromatic lens (beam collimation) and a 32x microscope lens (NA 0.09) (Fig. B.1). The normalized measured heat generation is compared with the calculated values is shown in Fig. B.2. Agreement is good with the exception of slight systematic errors.

Figure B.1: Test setup for laser excitation of steel plates.

Figure B.2: Comparison of measured (solid line) and calculated heat generation (dashed line) for the point directly above the heat source.

Appendix C

Overview of Several Nondestructive Examination Methods

Nondestructive material examination (NDT) is a “technical procedure for determining one or more specified quality characteristics of a material or product in accordance with specified process values, where the energy used interacts with the material properties *without unreasonably compromising... the intended characteristics for use.*” [Ric99, p. 10]

The different quality levels of NDT can be approximately classified starting from simple nondestructive inspection/testing (NDI/NDT) through nondestructive evaluation (NDE) to quantitative NDE (QNDE) [Ach06].

However, in all of these methods, the condition of the specimen is not investigated until after loading (such as during routine maintenance in the case of turbine blades). The optimum would be in-situ inspection of the most heavily loaded parts of a system, which is designated as structural health monitoring (SHM). For example, in the aircraft industry, sensors should be integrated in the airfoils which can then be read out on a regular basis [Ach06]. Vibration sensors are installed in many stationary gas turbines which initiate turbine trip on excessive vibration.

C.1 Non-Thermographic Methods

The non-thermographic methods include radiographic examination with X-ray, γ and neutron radiation in 2D radiography or 3D computer tomography, magnetic flux testing with magnetic field sensors or magnetic powder, ultrasonic and eddy current examination as well as dye penetrant examination.

As dye penetrant examination is in widespread use as a highly sensitive method for the examination of large areas, it is briefly explained here.¹

Usually a strongly coloring or fluorescing mineral oil is used, which is applied over a large area on the surface to be examined. Capillary forces cause this liquid penetrant to penetrate into surface defects such as cracks or pores, where it remains for a certain penetration time (depending on the material, temperature and anticipated defect type, typically 3–20 min [Ste93, p. 389]). This is followed by excess

¹Physical details are given in references such as [BS89, p. 463ff].

penetrant removal in which the excess penetrant is washed off. This is done using water or a special cleaner depending on the type of liquid penetrant used. If possible, no penetrant should remain on the surface, as this results in false indications, while on the other hand the penetrant shall not be washed out from the defects. It is expedient to perform this cleaning step under UV light for fluorescing dye penetrant examination (see below).

Immediately after drying, the penetrant begins to escape from the cracks again. A developing step follows, in which a developer contrasting with the penetrant is sprayed on to increase contrast and to visually enlarge the defect. The individual powder grains of the developer extract the dye penetrant from the defects again by capillary effects and distribute it over a larger area, rendering it easier to detect.

The following liquid penetrants are distinguished [Ste93, p. 377]:

- Dye penetrant with a dye which is also visible by daylight (dye penetrant inspection, DPI), usually red is used,
- Fluorescing liquid penetrant (fluorescent penetrant inspection, FPI) with yellow-green dyes which fluoresce under UV light (usually 365 nm),
- Fluorescing dye penetrant with both additives which can thus be seen both by daylight as well as by UV light.

The advantages of dye penetrant examination are its simple and cost-effective application, applicability to a large range of materials and the capability of examination of large areas and extensive automation.

Limitations of dye penetrant examination are that only surface defects are detectable (also requiring removal of paint coatings and surface cleaning), the requisite training of the examiner and environmental issues.

Fig. C.1 shows the example detection of an artificially generated fatigue crack in a turbine blade with a fluorescing liquid penetrant. The crack is very difficult to detect without examination equipment (Fig. C.1a). Detection is unproblematic with liquid penetrant and under UV light (Fig. C.1c). As application of the developer enhances escape of the liquid penetrant back out of the crack as explained above, in this case the crack can also be detected without a UV lamp (Fig. C.1b). A similar effect can also be achieved with alcohol, which evaporates first on defect-free areas following application over a wide area, with the result that the crack becomes visible for a very short time.

C.2 Thermographic Methods

All thermographic methods are based on detection of the infrared radiation emitted by the specimen. Point detectors, scanning infrared cameras or more recently infrared cameras in snapshot mode can be used for this purpose.

In addition to *passive* thermography, which is used especially in construction and enables the detection of poorly insulating windows, for example, another method is so-called *active* thermography, in which energy is deliberately introduced into the body and the time change in surface temperature registered.

The following sections are concerned exclusively with the different methods whereby energy can be introduced into the body in active thermography.

Figure C.1: Detection of an artificially generated fatigue crack in a gas turbine blade using fluorescing liquid penetrant. a. Optical image without penetrant application, b. After performance of steps required for FPI, c. As in b. but under UV lighting.

C.2.1 Flash Thermography

In this method, a flash lamp is used to heat the specimen (such as from professional photography, with a flash energy of several kJ). A thermal wave then penetrates into the object, which can be modeled as one-dimensional heat conduction due to symmetry) and the decrease in surface temperature T then follows a $t^{-1/2}$ law. Wall thickness examination makes use of the fact that the $T(t)$ curve flattens out when the heat pulse reaches the back wall. The time at which the temperature curve bends correlates to the wall thickness. Multiple-layer systems can also be analyzed with somewhat greater effort.

A further area of application is the detection of local detachment of coatings (delamination), where delayed heat conduction can be seen. The measurement limit is roughly 1 cm in steel due to the applied energy level.

C.2.2 Hot Air Thermography

Hot air thermography for wall thickness measurement of turbine blades has become established at Siemens AG in recent years. This is done by blowing hot air ($\approx 300^\circ\text{C}$) through the cooling air channels in the turbine blades. The air flow is switched on and off for phase determination. The subsequent evaluation is based on a lock-in analysis, although additional effects such as multiple reflection of the thermal wave on the wall surfaces must be accounted for in order to achieve acceptable accuracy.

Advantages over flash thermography are on the one hand the greater applicable heat input and on the other the fact that the thermal wave only has to pass through the wall once. The effect of both of these is that thicker walls can be measured at higher accuracy.

C.2.3 Induction Thermography

An induction heater can be used for heating (at least partially) conducting parts or layers. The skin effect causes the induced currents to flow close to the surface of the

object. Any (open vertical) cracks force the current to flow around the crack tip. This results in an increased current density, which is manifested in higher ohmic losses and thus in heating.

This method can be used to detect both cracks as well as delamination. The large advantage is the noncontacting nature of the method compared with acoustic thermography. This is offset by the generation of apparent indications due to heating of the entire specimen. The induced current is also strongly dependent on geometry. However, these effects can be reduced by optimization of the coil design.

Appendix D

Gas Turbine Construction

As the method of acoustic thermography has been investigated primarily on gas turbine blades in this study, the construction and special aspects of gas turbine components is examined briefly here.

Fig. D.1 shows a schematic of the construction of a 190 MW Siemens gas turbine. Air is drawn in through the air intake, is compressed in the compressor and is routed to the combustor, where the gas is admitted and combusted. This is followed by the blades of the actual turbine, which are driven by the hot combustion gases and are thus subjected to the greatest thermal and mechanical forces. The turbine is connected directly to the generator through the shaft and rotates at the grid frequency (USA: 60 Hz, Europe: 50 Hz).

There are two types of turbine blades, the rotor blades and the stator vanes, which are always in pairs. The latter are between the rotor blade rows and serve only to divert the gas flow. An example is shown in Fig. 1.3, right. The turbine rotor blades (turbine blades below) are subject to both thermal and mechanical loads.

Because of these high combined thermal and mechanical loads, the turbine blades (in contrast with the compressor blades) cannot be made of steel; instead high-strength alloys are used, primarily Inconel (nickel/cobalt-based alloys). A ceramic thermal barrier coating is also applied to reduce the thermal loads. In addition, the blades contain cooling channels through which air from the compressor is forced. Cooling air bores on the blade airfoil generate an air flow over the blade, which contributes effectively to cooling (Fig. D.2).

The blade roots are inserted in the wheel disks, which are in turn secured to the shaft. The blade root has a so-called fir-tree structure for this attachment. As the underside of the root is not subjected to any large forces, it has proven expedient to attach the exciter for acoustic thermography at this location.

Figure D.1: Gas turbine construction

Figure D.2: Photograph of an opened gas turbine and a gas turbine blade with the most important features

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